

D3.1 - MultiX perception system enablers v1

Focus on perception enablers design including AI and multi-technology, multi-static perception

MultiX

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Abstract:	<p>This deliverable introduces the initial version of the MultiX Perception System (MPS), a key enabler for Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) within heterogeneous Radio Access Network (RAN) environments. The MPS integrates sensing capabilities across diverse technologies—including 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) components (RU, DU, CU), User Equipment, and non-cellular systems such as Wi-Fi—to form a unified, scalable perception framework. Central to the architecture is the Measurement Sensing Processing Function (m-SePF), which collects, processes, and fuses sensing data to provide accurate, robust perception services.</p> <p>The deliverable is structured around three innovation pillars aligned with Tasks 3.1–3.3. The first pillar, Perception Enablers, develops foundational ISAC technologies such as joint communication–sensing channel models, advanced waveform design, and multi-band algorithms to enhance spectrum efficiency and sensing accuracy. The second pillar, Multi-Static, Multi-Technology Perception, explores cooperative and distributed processing through heterogeneous MIMO deployments, enabling coherent and non-coherent fusion of sensing information to improve spatial resolution, coverage, and robustness. The third pillar, Energy-Efficient, AI-Based Perceptive Networks, addresses the computational and energy challenges of AI-driven sensing by introducing neuromorphic approaches and lightweight models suitable for resource-constrained RAN nodes.</p> <p>Together, these pillars establish the MPS as a flexible, energy-efficient, scalable ISAC platform capable of supporting multi-technology deployments. The deliverable also reports the initial integration of the m-SePFs into the MultiX system and outlines the ethical considerations related to human-related data collection in compliance with project policies.</p>
Keywords:	MultiX perception systems, integrated sensing and communications, multi-band, multi-static, multi-technology, channel models, waveforms, energy-efficient AI, event-based processing

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

2D	two-dimensional
5G	5th Generation Communications
5GC	5G Core
6G	6th Generation Communications
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
AAE	Adversarial Autoencoder
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AoA	Angle of Arrival
AoD	Angle of Departure
AFDM	Affine Frequency- Division Multiplexing
BIC	Bayesian Information Criterion
BLER	Block Error Rate
BP	Backprojection
BProp	Belief Propagation
BS	Base Station
CN	Core Network
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CIR	channel impulse response
CFAR	Constant False Alarm Rate
CFR	Channel Frequency Response
CFO	Carrier Frequency Offset
CRLB	Cramér-Rao Lower Bound
CP	Cyclic-Prefix
CS	Compressed Sensing
CSI	Channel State Information
CSV	Comma Separated Values
CU	Centralized Unit
CWT	Continuous Wavelet Transform
DDA	Discrete Dipole Approximation
DP	Dynamic Programming
DSP	Digital Signal Processor
DU	Distributed Unit

DL Deep Learning

D2D device-to-device

DNN deep neural network

DRAM Dynamic Random Access Memory

DFT Discrete Fourier Transform

DTOA Difference of Time of Arrival

DMRS Demodulation Reference Signal

DVP Delay Violation Probability

DD Delay Doppler

DPIA Data Protection Impact Assessment

DWT Dcontinuous Wavelet Transform

EM Electromagnetic

EMPW Empirical Multiband Peak Width

ELU Exponential-Linear Unit

ESPRIT Estimation of Signal Parameters via Rotational Invariance Techniques

ETSI European Telecommunications Standards Institute

fps Frames per Second

FDMA Frequency Division Multiple Access

FFT Fast Fourier Transform

FI Fisher information

IFFT Inverse Fast Fourier Transform

FR1 Frequency Range 1

FR2 Frequency Range 2

FR3 Frequency Range 3

FMCW Frequency-Modulated Continuous-Wave

FPGA Field Programmable Gate Array

GAN Generative Adversarial Networks

gNB Next Generation Node B

GPS Global Positioning System

GenAI Generative AI

HB Histogram-based Gradient Boosting

HAR Human Activity Recognition

HHT Hilbert–Huang transforms

HARQ Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request

IoE Internet of Everything
IoT Internet of Things
ICT Information and Communication Technologies
IB Information Bottleneck
IDS Intrusion Detection System
IDA Intrusion Detection Agent
IP Internet Protocol
ISAC Integrated Sensing and Communications
ISG Industrial Specification Group
IDFT Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform
IF Intermediate Frequency
IMU Inertial Measurement Unit
IQ In-phase and Quadrature
JM JUMP-MUSIC
KD Knowledge Distillation
KPI Key Performance Indicator
KF Kalman Filter
LO Local Oscillator
LoS Line-of-Sight
L-GM Large margin Gaussian Mixture
MAC Medium Access Control
MAD Median Absolute Deviation
MIMO Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
MC Multiband Phase Coherence
MPC Multipath Components
MUSIC Multiple Signal Classification
mmWave Millimeter-Wave
 μ **D** micro-Doppler
ML Machine Learning
MoG Mixture of Gaussian
MPS MultiX Perception System
MBET Monostatic-to-Bistatic Equivalent Theorem
MEC Multi-access Edge Computing
MCS Modulation and Coding Scheme

N3IWF Non-3GPP Interworking Function
NLoS Non Line-of-Sight
NN Neural Network
NR New Radio
NMPM Normalized Multiband Peak Magnitude
OFDM Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
OMP Orthogonal Matching Pursuit
OR-CED Open-set Recognition based on Contrastive constraint and Ensemble-based out-of-distribution Detection
OSGR Open-set Gait Recognition
OSPA Optimal Subpattern Assignment
OTA Over-the-Air
OTFS Orthogonal Time Frequency Space
OCDM Orthogonal Chirp-Division Multiplexing
PAPR peak-to-average power ratio
PEC perfectly electric conducting
PER Packet Error Rate
PDF Probability Density Function
PDP Power Delay Profile
PMCW Phase Modulated Continuous Wave
PSLR Peak-to-Sidelobe Ratio
PO Phase Offset
PCAA Point Cloud Adversarial Autoencoder
PS Processing System
PL Programmable Logic
PoC Proof of Concept
PUCCH Physical Uplink Control Channel
PUSCH Physical Uplink Shared Channel
QoS Quality of Service
RADAR Radio Detection and Ranging
RAF Range Ambiguity Function
RAM Random Access Memory
RAN Radio Access Network
RAT Radio Access Technology
RCS Radar Cross-Section

RF Radio Frequency
RFSoc Radio Frequency System on a Chip
RIC RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RL Reinforcement Learning
RMSE Root-Mean-Squared Error
RU Radio Unit
RSRPP Reference Signal Received Power per Path
RS Reference Signal
RED Relative Echo Delay
SAR Synthetic Aperture Radar
SC Single Carrier
SCF Subcarrier Selection Function
SDR Software Defined Radio
SDN Software Defined Network
SDP Sensing Data Point
m-SePF Measurement Sensing Processing Function
SeRCF Sensing RAN Control FunctionSensing Data Broker Function
SINR Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio
SISO Single Input Single Output
SNN Spiking Neural Network
SNR Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SoC System-on-Chip
SPBP Subsets Product Backprojection
sps samples per second
SRx Sensing Receiver
SSB Synchronization Signal Block
STx Sensing Transmitter
SVM Support Vector Machine
TDMA Time Division Multiple Access
TO Timing Offset
TCCPN Temporal Convolution Point-Cloud Network
ToA Time of Arrival
ToF Time of Flight

UAV Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UE User Equipment
ULP Ultra Low Power
UPF User Plane Function
UCI Uplink Control Information
VAE Variational Auto-Encoders
VNA Vector Network Analyzer
WSN Wireless Sensor Network
WHT Walsh–Hadamard transforms

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the initial version of the MPS technological enablers. The MPS is designed to enable ISAC capabilities across heterogeneous RAN environments. It encompasses User Equipments (UEs), various RAN components, such as Radio Unit (RU), Centralized Unit (CU), and Distributed Unit (DU)), and non-cellular systems such as Wi-Fi, targeting a unified perception framework that supports multi-sensor, multi-band, multi-static, and multi-technology deployments.

At its core, the MPS focuses on the design and development of m-SePF within the RAN domain, responsible for collecting, processing, and fusing sensing data to deliver accurate and robust sensing capabilities to the 6th Generation Communications (6G) network.

The system is structured around three innovation pillars, each contributing distinct technological advancements and corresponding to Tasks 3.1–3.3 of the WP3 work plan.

Perception Enablers (Task 3.1). This pillar develops key enablers to enhance ISAC performance across multiple technologies, optimizing spectrum efficiency and sensing accuracy. It includes: (i) *fundamental channel modelling*, jointly considering communication and sensing across monostatic, bistatic, and multi-static configurations, (ii) *advanced modulation and waveform design*, to support ISAC operations in dynamic and interference-prone environments, and (iii) *multi-band ISAC algorithms*, exploiting intra-band and inter-band signal diversity for improved sensing resolution. These enablers form the algorithmic foundation for the MPS, enabling efficient processing and signal interpretation across different RAN domains.

Multi-Static, Multi-Technology Perception (Task 3.2).

This pillar focuses on cooperative and distributed ISAC processing to achieve high-resolution perception. The MPS leverages distributed Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) architectures and multi-technology integration (e.g., 3GPP and Wi-Fi) to fuse heterogeneous sensing information. Both coherent (phase-synchronized) and non-coherent cooperation strategies are explored, improving coverage, reliability, and robustness of the m-SePFs. The resulting multi-static signal processing methods allow the MPS to perceive complex environments with high spatial accuracy and extended range.

Energy-Efficient, AI-Based Perceptive Network (Task 3.3). This pillar addresses the energy and computational challenges of AI-driven sensing in resource-constrained RAN nodes. The MPS introduces neuromorphic computing approaches using event-based neural networks (spiking NNs) that process sparse data efficiently. By integrating lightweight AI models into the m-SePFs pipeline, MPS drastically reduces power consumption while maintaining high perception performance, enabling sustainable large-scale deployment of intelligent sensing functions.

Together, these three pillars position the MPS as a scalable, multi-technology, and energy-efficient ISAC platform that enhances the perceptive capabilities of next-generation RAN. This deliverable describes each pillar in a dedicated chapter. Then, it discusses the initial system development effort made by WP3 to integrate the MPS innovations into the MultiX by developing the m-SePFs. A final chapter discusses the ethical aspects of some activities involving the collection of human-related data, pointing to the relevant documentation in compliance with the MultiX policies.

1. Introduction

MULTIX proposes key wireless communication and signal processing enhancements to expand the perception capabilities of the 6G-RAN. At the physical layer of the communication network (PHY), these enhancements are embodied by the MPS, which includes a set of ISAC enablers for multi-band, multi-technology, and multi-static sensing, supported by energy-efficient AI functionalities.

The MultiX WP3 is responsible for the development and validation of the MPS, which will consist of three stages as shown in Fig. 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Overview of MultiX WP3 deliverables, covering the development of the MPS from enablers to system design and experimentation.

D3.1 lays the foundations of the ISAC framework in MultiX by focusing on the design and development of the *perception enablers* of the MPS. These include: new channel models and measurements that integrate the sensing and communication aspects into a single framework, new ISAC waveforms, multi-band ISAC algorithms, multi-static and multi-technology integration, and energy-efficient AI/GenAI architectures to enhance the sensing capabilities and handle ISAC resources.

D3.2 builds upon D3.1 and focuses on the system-level integration of the developed enablers. Although the latter has already started in D3.1, D3.2 will complete this process by implementing m-SePFs that encapsulate the sensing algorithms from D3.1 and make them available and usable within the MultiX architecture.

D3.3 will take inputs from D3.1 and D3.2 to detail the implementation of the MPS and the validation experiments conducted within WP3. The setup of experimental platforms and initial implementation has already started, as will be clear from some contributions in D3.1. In D3.3, the implementation will be finalized and demonstrated.

In the next section, we provide an overview of D3.1 and the document structure.

1.1. D3.1 overview and document structure

This deliverable addresses the four main research tasks that constitute WP3, each presented in a separate chapter (1 - 4). Each task is responsible for the development of different MPS enablers. Then, in chapter 5, we present our initial efforts towards system integration of such enablers.

1.1.1. Chapter 2 - Task 3.1: Perception enablers

Chapter 2 focuses on the fundamental building blocks of the MPS. To enable a solid integration of sensing functionalities into the RAN, the first step is to develop a joint communication and sensing channel model, which allows understanding their correlation. We address this problem by analytical modeling and real measurements, providing insights on targets Radar Cross-Section (RCS) and phase response in different frequency bands. Then, we explore new waveforms for ISAC beyond OFDM, analysing trade-offs and advantages of Orthogonal Time Frequency Space (OTFS), Frequency-Modulated Continuous-Wave (FMCW), and others. This represents a key step in identifying suitable signal models for ISAC in 6G to enable applications in diverse scenarios, e.g., low-mobility vs. high mobility. Finally, we formulate multi-band channel models and algorithms to achieve higher sensing performance, exploiting the frequency diversity of the different bands. We

approach the problem analytically and experimentally, proposing new algorithms for multi-band combination and developing testbeds to allow further experimentation in this task.

1.1.2. Chapter 3 - Task 3.2: Multi-technology, multi-static sensing integration

Chapter 3 addresses the problem of integrating sensing information from (i) multiple ISAC nodes operating with the same communications technology, (ii) multiple ISAC or sensor nodes using different technologies (e.g., Wi-Fi and 3GPP protocols). Our approach to (i) starts with developing synchronisation algorithms to remove timing, frequency, and phase offsets that affect distributed ISAC nodes. The proposed methods operate *over-the-air*, i.e., relying on the sole wireless signal without the need for complex and expensive disciplined oscillators or external synchronisation methods such as Global Positioning System (GPS). Then, we explore point (ii) by developing methods to fuse sensing information collected by 3GPP and non-3GPP ISAC nodes in the RAN in a flexible way. Preliminary tests have been conducted in an implementation of multi-technology RAN, showing promising results for the MultiX multi-technology vision. Finally, we focus on the development of multi-static sensing algorithms exploiting a non-coherent combination of the channel estimates obtained at different ISAC nodes. In this sense, attention has been put on addressing and exploiting near-field effects that may arise when considering spatially distributed sensors.

1.1.3. Chapter 4 - Task 3.3: AI-based energy efficient perception system

In Chapter 4, we present our activities on the development of new AI architectures and techniques to improve sensing performance while minimising energy consumption. On the one hand, we started developing energy-efficient Neural Network (NN) architectures for sensing, based on neuromorphic and event-driven computing. This allows reducing the energy cost of processing the huge amount of data produced by ISAC nodes. On the other hand, we leveraged standard NN architectures as optimisers and schedulers to allocate ISAC resources intelligently and in an energy-aware fashion. Finally, we began exploring the use of multi-modal sensing and GenAI to enhance the sensing accuracy and resolution by learning from data. The use of GenAI will be investigated in addition to multi-band and multi-static to solve the problem of non-contiguous channel estimates in frequency and space.

1.1.4. Chapter 5: Sensing processing functions

Chapter 5 focuses on our first efforts to integrate the sensing enablers developed in WP3 into the MultiX system. Specifically, we present a set of m-SePFs, based on the algorithms and methods presented in the previous chapters. We first detail a unified set of parameters that describe each function, then present the functions developed in WP3 up to M12 of MultiX that have reached a mature development stage.

1.1.5. Chapter 6: Ethical aspects

The research activities presented in this deliverable sometimes involve the collection of sensing data with human subjects. For this reason, there is a potential risk of misuse of such data that has been identified and prevented by taking preventive actions. Chapter 6 discusses the ethical aspects of the collection of human-related data, pointing to the relevant documentation in compliance with the MultiX policies.

2. Task 3.1: Perception enablers

Task 3.1 targets the MultiX objective SO3.1: *Develop a joint signal processing framework to enable communication and sensing, including multiband, OTFS-based, and programmable environments like Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS), and leveraging on disaggregated RAN architectures.* This task deals with the development and validation of perception enablers for a multi-band, multi-technology, and multi-static 6G ISAC network. Our action has targeted three enablers: ISAC channel models, new ISAC waveforms, and ISAC multi-band processing framework, corresponding to three main research activities we have defined:

1. **Channel Modeling and Measurements (Section 2.1).** This activity focuses on the fundamental understanding of ISAC channels, including the relationship between sensing and communication channels, the RCS modelling, and the impacts of the channel on sensing performance. The research outcomes will not only lay the foundation of designing ISAC systems, but also possibly contribute to standardisation activities such as European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)/3GPP.
2. **ISAC Waveforms (Section 2.2).** This activity investigates waveform options for ISAC systems, starting from OFDM, and then to OTFS. Furthermore, based on radar waveforms such as FMCW, this activity will explore the options when considering sensing-centric or communication-centric design principles.
3. **Multiband Processing (Section 2.3).** This activity focuses on a bottom-up research line, aiming at addressing the fundamental phase coherence problem when using a multiband system, proposing more efficient processing algorithms to enhance ranging performance and, finally, a multi-band measurement system will be established for further validations of both theoretical and algorithmic developments.

2.1. Channel modeling and measurements

The comprehensive understanding of wireless channels is the first step in designing radio systems, as well as the corresponding planning and optimization of networks. This subtask aims to provide both characterization and models of wireless channels for the MultiX project, which serves as the foundation for both the communication systems and perception networks. Several approaches will be used in channel modeling, where the measurement is one of the convincing ways to observe channels directly. However, due to the complexity in spectrum and functionality under the context of the project – Multi-Band, Multi-Static, the channel modeling becomes very challenging. First of all, we have to understand the new channel characteristics of the new spectrum, such as the upper mid-band (7-24 GHz, known as FR3). Then, radar deployment can be diverse, including monostatic, bistatic, and multi-static. A core problem for ISAC technologies is to understand the relation between sensing and communication channels, which is fundamental to designing such a system. In summary, this subtask is tightly following the development in 3GPP, where two urgent study items, including FR3 and ISAC channel modeling, are considered. In this task, we will further extend beyond the SOTA by investigating **1)** the FR3 for sensing, especially for its phase coherence, **2)** the relationship between sensing and communication channels, and **3)** RCS modeling in the target channels, as a part of ISAC channels. From the system level, we will further investigate **4)** the impacts of CSI on the realistic sensing performance by employing emerging technology like RIS and then, ultimately, **5)** explore the development of CSI-based digital twin systems. The abovementioned **five aspects** consist of the activities of this subtask up to date.

2.1.1. Target phase coherence metrics and measurements in FR3

There is a general consensus that Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) will be one of the key pillars of 6G cellular networks [1], endowing them with radar-like capabilities to sense the location and movements of objects and people in the environment. However, the limited spectrum availability and the non-contiguity of the frequency bands allocation represent a bottleneck that prevents the sensing accuracy and resolution of ISAC systems from achieving their cm-level theoretical value. These limitations have recently sparked the research on *coherent multi-band* ISAC [2, 3], which leverages the *carrier phase* information contained in the CSI acquired in multiple, possibly non-contiguous, frequency bands to increase the delay and range resolution. This line of work naturally aligns with the opportunities offered by the Frequency Range 3 (FR3) spectrum, spanning approximately 7-24 GHz.

The FR3 spectrum has emerged as a promising range for 6G, striking a balance between the favorable propagation characteristics of FR1 and the abundant bandwidth of FR2 mmWave bands [4]. Unlike sub-6 GHz, FR3 offers much larger contiguous and non-contiguous allocations, while its propagation loss and penetration characteristics remain far more manageable than those in mmWave, enabling coverage in urban and suburban areas with existing tower infrastructure [5].

A further opportunity lies in the inherent disaggregation of FR3 spectrum. Allocations are fragmented across multiple non-contiguous bands due to incumbent services such as satellites, radio astronomy, and radar. Rather than a drawback, the FR3 disaggregation can be turned into a feature. Coherent multi-band ISAC techniques can exploit non-contiguous FR3 bands to jointly enhance communication and sensing resolution by *aggregating* the available bands, thus increasing the total bandwidth with minimal spectrum occupation.

2.1.1.1. Challenges and contributions

Several challenges arise in using disaggregated wideband spectrum for coherent multi-band ISAC. The main one is that real targets exhibit frequency-dependent (*incoherent*) electromagnetic scattering properties when signals having very different carrier frequencies are used. Given the extremely wide span of FR3, sensing targets can not be modeled as *frequency isotropic*, i.e., idealized point-like scatterers that scatter the signal in the same way regardless of the carrier frequency, as commonly done in multi-band ISAC works [6, 7]. This means that the complex-valued coefficients of such targets in the channel impulse response (CIR) are not constant in frequency, which invalidates existing coherent multi-band algorithms and phase offset compensation techniques across bands. The incoherence becomes more significant in *high fractional bandwidth* scenarios, i.e., where the total bandwidth exceeds 20% of the carrier frequency. Unlike FR1 (low carrier frequency, narrow bandwidth) and FR2 (high carrier frequency, wide bandwidth), FR3 can reach over 100% fractional bandwidth if multiple disaggregated bands are combined.

To date, existing research has focused on modeling and experimentally characterizing FR3 for communications and ISAC [8] without considering the challenges of coherent multi-band sensing. Specifically: (i) *experimental characterization* of frequency anisotropy over FR3 band is lacking, so it is unclear when existing multi-band algorithms are applicable and when instead they are not, (ii) *metrics* to evaluate the *phase coherence* of common targets and the impact of high fractional bandwidth on multi-band ISAC algorithms are missing.

In this activity, which is associated with our paper [9], we tackle the above challenges by presenting the first experimental characterization for coherent multi-band ISAC over FR3, including novel coherence evaluation metrics and bandwidth aggregation algorithms. We focus on *ranging*, i.e., the measurement of a target's distance from the ISAC device, combining multiple frequency bands coherently. This is commonly the first step in ISAC systems, to localize the targets of interest, hence our results also apply to other, more advanced, sensing applications such as motion analysis and respiration monitoring, among others. Our contributions are summarized below.

1. We present the first experimental characterization of coherent multi-band ISAC over the FR3 band. Our analysis encompasses both the frequency anisotropy phenomenon and the impact of non-contiguous bands. The collected data is made available to the research community at [10].
2. We propose three novel metrics to evaluate the phase coherence of common targets, including humans, to check the applicability of existing multi-band ISAC algorithms and assess their performance.

Our findings point out that the high fractional bandwidth of FR3 and the frequency anisotropy of common targets is a neglected but key aspect to take into account in the design of multi-band ISAC algorithms and their integration in 6G. In addition, our results suggest that existing multi-band aggregation algorithms are unlikely to be effective when considering very wide portions of FR3 and real extended targets such as humans.

2.1.1.2. Use within MultiX

The measurement campaign and results presented in this section represent a first step towards enabling multi-band ISAC over wide FR3 bands. The multi-band aggregation algorithms discussed in Section 2.3 take into account the insights gathered from the measurement campaign. Therefore, the activity described in this section is essential for the development of m-SePF01. The obtained results suggest that existing algorithms for multi-band sensing of complex targets should either be applied over bands that are narrower than 2-3 GHz, or should be redesigned to account for the frequency anisotropy of the targets. The latter research direction

will be pursued in T3.3 by exploring the use of AI and generative AI to model the anisotropy in a data-driven way based on real measurements.

2.1.1.3. Signal model and preprocessing steps

We consider a multi-band Single Input Single Output (SISO) system with a transmitter (Tx) antenna and a receiver (Rx) antenna, which share the same Local Oscillator (LO). The SISO system operates on K subbands, each centered on a carrier frequency f_k and of bandwidth B_k . We collect the carrier frequencies and bandwidths in sets $\mathcal{F} = \{f_k\}_{k=0}^{K-1}$, and $\mathcal{B} = \{B_k\}_{k=0}^{K-1}$, respectively. We assume that L static scattering centers are present in the environment, indexed by $\ell = 1, \dots, L$, located at distances R_ℓ from the SISO ISAC terminal. Each sensing target may be composed of a single scattering center or *multiple* scattering centers (extended target, for example, a human body), which are only resolved by the ISAC system if sufficient bandwidth is available. Therefore, the number of sensing targets is, in general, lower than or equal to L .

The SISO ISAC system emits an OFDM signal over the K subbands, each subband having N_k subcarriers and fixed subcarrier spacing Δ_f . The propagation delay from the ℓ -th scattering center is $\tau_\ell = 2R_\ell/c$, with c being the speed of light and R_ℓ the distance between the scattering center and the ISAC device, respectively.

Each scattering center is characterized by a complex *frequency-dependent* RCS, $\rho_{\ell,k} e^{j\theta_{\ell,k}}$, whose magnitude $\rho_{\ell,k}$ and phase $\theta_{\ell,k}$ contain the effect of the combined path loss and scattering attenuation, and of the scattering phase response, respectively.

The baseband signal for the k -th OFDM symbol (hence for the k -th subband), assumed to have unit-power, is called $x_k(t)$, and its upconverted version to carrier frequency is $x_k^{\text{RF}}(t) = x_k(t)e^{j2\pi f_k t}$. The baseband Rx signal after downconversion is denoted by $y_k(t)$. Note that a complete model of the Rx signal should also include timing errors due to LO non-ideality. However, since we use a monostatic system, such errors can be neglected in our work as thoroughly explained in the associated paper [9].

In the next section, we detail the preprocessing steps applied to the baseband Rx signal to prepare it for coherent multi-band combination.

Preprocessing of the received signal. The received signal $y_k(t)$ is pre-processed before the extraction of the target's coherence metrics. The goal is to obtain the CIR for each subband, which requires the following steps:

1. **Sampling** with sampling interval $1/B_k$ and conversion to the frequency domain using a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT). Note that subsequent multi-band processing will require higher time granularity than $1/B_k$, thus requiring interpolation.
2. **Estimation of the SISO channel.** We estimate the Channel Frequency Response (CFR) in the frequency domain through elementwise division of the Rx symbols and the known Tx ones as

$$\tilde{H}_k(n\Delta_f) = \frac{Y_k(n\Delta_f)}{X_k(n\Delta_f)} = H_k(n\Delta_f)H_k^{\text{hw}}(n\Delta_f) + W_k(f), \quad (2.1)$$

where $\tilde{H}_k(n\Delta_f)$ is the ideal CFR, $H_k^{\text{hw}}(n\Delta_f)$ is the frequency response of the measurement device and $W_k(f)$ is a frequency domain noise term.

3. **Hardware calibration.** This step is needed to compensate for the frequency response of the measurement device in subband k , $H_k^{\text{hw}}(n\Delta_f)$, which may introduce distortion in the phase of the estimated channel. We estimate $H_k^{\text{hw}}(n\Delta_f)$ experimentally using a loopback cable connecting the Tx and Rx Radio Frequency (RF) chains. The calibration step divides $\tilde{H}_k(n\Delta_f)$ by the estimated hardware response.
4. **Estimation of the SISO CIR** by computing the Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform (IDFT) of $\hat{H}_k(n\Delta_f)$. This is a collection of scaled and shifted cardinal sine functions affected by the scattering phase $\theta_{\ell,k}$ of the ℓ -th scattering center in subband k . Moreover, an additional phase term due to the propagation of the carrier is present, $-2\pi f_k \tau_\ell$, which prevents a direct combination of the CIRs since it introduces a subband-dependent phase shift for that same delay τ_ℓ . The resolution of the CIR in distinguishing multiple scattering centers is limited by the bandwidth of a single subband. Specifically, the resolution is given by the width of the main lobe of the sinc functions, which is $1/B_k$ in delay units and $c/(2B_k)$ in range units.

Backprojection algorithm. To increase the resolution of the estimated CIR using K subbands we adopt the time-domain Backprojection (BP) algorithm used in [11], adapting it to one-dimensional multi-band ranging.

The pre-processing provides the CIRs of the subbands, which are still affected by the propagation carrier phase. The first step in BP is to isolate the target's scattering phase by compensating for the propagation-dependent carrier phase term $2\pi f_k \tau_\ell$. This is done by expressing the propagation delay τ_ℓ as a function of the scattering center's distance, i.e., $\tau_\ell = 2R_\ell/c$, and multiplying the CIR by a compensation term $e^{j\frac{4\pi f_k}{c}R}$. The resulting compensated CIR is called the *range profile* of subband k and denoted by $\eta_k(R)$. At $R = R_\ell$, the term $e^{j\frac{4\pi f_k}{c}R}$ cancels out the carrier phase term, so that the phase of the ℓ -th path in the range profile equals the phase of the scattering center's phase response $\theta_{k,\ell}$.

As a second step, BP sums the K range profiles obtained by the compensation step coherently, thus obtaining a combined range profile which we call $\eta(R) = \sum_{k=1}^K \eta_k(R)$. We use this combined range profile to evaluate the coherence of the targets of interest through the proposed metrics.

2.1.1.4. FR3 measurement system

To implement our experiment in FR3, we utilize a Software Defined Radio (SDR) platform in monostatic configuration, using 1 transmit and 1 receive chains. The SDR includes the following components

Digital baseband RFSoc: A Xilinx RFSoc 4x2 Kit equipped with a ZU48DR processor is used for baseband signal processing, including digital-to-analog (and vice-versa) conversion. The board is capable of generating RF signals up to 6 GHz, and therefore cannot directly generate FR3 signals. It is instead utilized to generate an Intermediate Frequency (IF) signal centered at 1 GHz that is up/down converted in a later stage.

RF transceiver Pi-Radio board: The IF signal generated by the RFSoc 4×2 Kit is up/down converted by a Pi-Radio TRX board, which translates the fixed-frequency IF to a configurable frequency in the 6-24 GHz range, enabling the frequency sweep. The up and down conversions are performed coherently, ensuring consistent phase measurements. More details of the board can be found in [12].

Vivaldi wideband antenna: The measurements are performed over a bandwidth of over 15 GHz centered around 14 GHz, which constitutes a fractional bandwidth greater than 100%. Such a fractional bandwidth is difficult to achieve with standard antennas such as patches or dipoles, which usually provide a percentage fractional bandwidth in the order of units to a few tens. To address this, we use a wideband Vivaldi antenna which, thanks to its exponentially tapered structure, can operate across the whole 6-24 GHz band.

2.1.1.5. Dataset

In our experimental campaign, we collect a dataset of 475 Over-the-Air (OTA) CFR measurements obtained with a multi-band monostatic transceiver spanning the frequency range 6-22 GHz. The dataset is available at [10]. The transceiver sweeps the full frequency range, transmitting OFDM pilot signals with a bandwidth of 500 MHz or 1 GHz with different carrier frequencies. From each CFR measurement, the corresponding CIR is obtained by applying an IDFT along the OFDM subcarriers dimension. The dataset consists of 200 calibration measurements, 150 single-target measurements, and 125 multi-target measurements. We consider three target types: a calibrated corner reflector, a metal plate, and humans, shown in Fig. 2.1. To evaluate the impact of using non-contiguous subbands, in some of our experiments, we extract *subsets* of the subbands collected in the frequency sweep that do not cover the full frequency range.

We consider the BP multi-band ISAC algorithm from the literature [13]. BP is used as the default algorithm in single-target measurements with contiguous subbands, since it is not affected by grating lobes in this case. This method is commonly used in the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) literature and has been used in ISAC in [11, 13]. It combines the subbands by oversampling the CIR of each subband, compensating for the propagation phase term of each CIR, and summing the CIRs coherently.

In our experimental results, we consider the following three types of targets.

- **Corner reflector:** We use a corner-cube reflector with 15 cm side length, as shown in the middle picture in Fig. 2.1. The corner reflector is calibrated for radar applications.
- **Metal plate:** We use a flat metal plate of dimensions 25×10 cm (Fig. 2.1). The thickness of the plate is a few millimeters.
- **Static human:** Human subjects are instructed to stand as still as possible in front of the measurement device. To mitigate the impact of respiration on the phase measurements, they are asked to hold their breath for 2-3 seconds during the data collection, which lasts 150 ms for the full frequency sweep.

Figure 2.1: Experimental testbed and considered targets. The Xilinx RFSoc generates the baseband signal and sends it to the Pi-Radio board for FR3 upconversion. The Vivaldi antennas enable wideband signal transmission.

2.1.1.6. Multi-band target coherence metrics

Our contribution is to propose novel metrics to evaluate: (i) the phase coherence of the target in the different measured subbands and (ii) the quality of the resulting multi-band range profile. We design three metrics, which are a function of the target index ℓ , detailed in the following. In the definitions below, we denote by R_ℓ the range value corresponding to target ℓ and by $\eta_k(R)$ the range profile in subband k evaluated at distance R . We consider a total of K combined subbands. The range profile is obtained from the CIR of subband k by compensating for the contribution of the carrier phase, as explained in detail in Section 2.1.1.3.

1. **Multipath Components (MPC).** The MC measures the spread of the scattering phases across the subbands as

$$\text{MPC}(\ell) = \left| \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} e^{j\angle\eta_k(R_\ell)} \right|, \quad (2.2)$$

where $\angle\cdot$ is the phase operator. The MC lies in $[0, 1]$ and equals 1 if the phases are all identical across the subbands, indicating maximal coherence. In this case, the terms $e^{j\angle\eta_k(R_\ell)}$ all add up coherently. Conversely, its value is 0 if the phases combine destructively, leading to a perfect cancellation of the $e^{j\angle\eta_k(R_\ell)}$ in the sum, indicating maximum incoherence. The target locations R_ℓ to be used in Eq. (2.2) are obtained by performing peak detection on the range profiles obtained in multiple subbands.

2. **Normalized Multiband Peak Magnitude (NMPM).** The NMPM evaluates the relative magnitude of the peak corresponding to a target in the combined range profile compared to the average magnitude of the same target across the single subbands. Denoting the multi-band combined range profile as $\eta(R)$, the NMPM in dB is

$$\text{NMPM}(\ell) = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{|\eta(R_\ell)|}{\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} |\eta_k(R_\ell)|} \right). \quad (2.3)$$

If, after combining multiple subbands, the magnitude of the target peak decreases relative to the mean peak magnitude across subbands, this indicates that the combined subbands are not coherent.

3. **Empirical Multiband Peak Width (EMPW).** This additional metric evaluates the empirical 3 dB peak width in the multi-band combined range profile. This is a direct measure (in meters) of the resolution of the range profile after multi-band processing, and can be compared to the theoretical resolution given by $c/(2B)$ where c is the speed of light and B is the bandwidth of the signal (either the single subband, B_k , or the total multi-band occupation). The EMPW is obtained as

$$\text{EMPW}(\ell) = \text{supp}_{-3\text{dB}}|\eta(R)| = \{R \mid \eta(R) \geq \eta(R_\ell)/2\}, \quad (2.4)$$

where $\text{supp}_{-3\text{dB}}$ denotes the -3 dB support of the range profile around target ℓ . Similar to NMPM, EMPW evaluates the quality of the multi-band range profile and is an indirect measure of the multi-band coherence.

2.1.1.7. Target phase coherence results

In Fig. 2.2, Fig. 2.3, and Fig. 2.4, we show our results for multi-band target coherence using the three targets described above, respectively. For each target, we show the three proposed metrics for different values of B_{tot} , which is the contiguous aggregated bandwidth, and carrier frequency. Specifically, each curve (with a different color) represents the result obtained by combining a different B_{tot} . Darker colors represent narrower B_{tot} while lighter colors represent wider B_{tot} . Each point in the curves is obtained with a different value of the carrier frequency, as specified by the x-axis. Note that curves corresponding to wider B_{tot} also contain fewer points, since there are fewer possibilities to fit a wide bandwidth in the considered frequency range of 6 – 22 GHz. All the results shown below are obtained by averaging 50 measurements taken consecutively, with a few seconds' pause between subsequent captures. A moving average smoothing filter along the frequency dimension, with a window of 3 points, is applied to the averaged curves with more than 5 points to improve readability.

Corner reflector: Fig. 2.2 shows that the corner reflector can be considered coherent over a very wide bandwidth, with slight differences depending on the carrier frequency. The phase coherence (MC metric) is above 0.8 for almost all the considered carrier frequencies and bandwidth values.

The main range profile peak magnitude loss with respect to the mean magnitude of the combined subbands (NMPM metric) does not fall below -2 dB regardless of the carrier frequency.

The EMPW results are coherent with the other metrics, showing that the main peak width of the target consistently shrinks when the combined bandwidth increases.

Figure 2.2: Coherence metrics of a metal plate target in the range 6-22 GHz. The bandwidth of a single subband is 0.5 GHz. We report metrics obtained for different carrier frequencies (on the x-axis) and different total combined bandwidth (corresponding to the different colored curves as specified in the colorbar).

Metal plate: Fig. 2.3 shows that the metal plate target has a similar behavior to the corner reflector, showing high coherence over a very wide bandwidth. The MC is above 0.8 for all the considered carrier frequencies and bandwidth values. The coherence obtained by combining 15 GHz of bandwidth is slightly lower than in the corner reflector case. The NMPM is also quite constant and shows the most significant degradation (2.1 dB) when combining 1 to 4 GHz of bandwidth around a carrier frequency of 17 GHz.

The EMPW shows that the main peak width of the target consistently shrinks when the combined bandwidth increases, except for very wide bandwidth values above 13 GHz. In this case, the resolution stops improving and slightly degrades, increasing the peak width. This can be appreciated in Fig. 2.3 by observing that the EMPW corresponding to $B_{\text{tot}} = 15$ GHz is higher than its $B_{\text{tot}} = 12$ GHz counterpart, meaning that the effective range resolution of the system degrades.

Human: In Fig. 2.4, we report our results for the human target, which include measurements with a person at 1 m and 1.2 m from the measurement device, performing frequency sweeps with 1 GHz bandwidth for a single subband. In this case, MC shows a decreasing trend with an increasing carrier frequency. This trend is consistent across multiple values of the combined bandwidth. A bandwidth of 2 GHz can be combined with a moderate decrease in the coherence, which is over 0.8 for all carrier frequencies. Conversely, combining

Figure 2.3: Coherence metrics of a metal plate target in the range 6-22 GHz. The bandwidth of a single subband is 0.5 GHz. We report metrics for different carrier frequencies (on the x-axis) and different total combined bandwidth (corresponding to the different colored curves as specified in the colorbar).

bandwidths over 3 GHz significantly degrades the phase coherence down to lower than 0.5. This indicates that a human does not provide a coherent point reflector-like response when increasing the resolution to the cm-level, differently from the corner reflector or metal plate targets. The NMPM and EMPW metrics are in agreement with the MC. The EMPW shows that the resolution gain for the human target is higher at lower carrier frequencies, which is consistent with the lower coherence of the subbands for higher carrier frequencies observed in the MC and NMPM. This could be because at higher frequencies the wavelength of the signal interacts differently with (i) body tissues due to the higher penetration depth compared to conducting materials, and (ii) the roughness of the targets, including clothes and different body parts.

Figure 2.4: Coherence metrics of a human target in the range 6-22 GHz. The bandwidth of a single subband is 1 GHz. We report the NMPM, EMPW, and the MC obtained for different carrier frequencies (indicated on the x-axis) and different total combined bandwidth (corresponding to the different colored curves as specified in the colorbar). For the EMPW we also report the single band and full band ideal resolutions with dashed black and red lines, respectively.

The **main takeaways** are summarized as follows.

1. Different targets exhibit different **frequency-dependent behavior** and have coherent responses over different carrier frequencies and bandwidths.
2. While corner reflectors and flat metal surfaces are coherent over wide frequency ranges (almost the whole FR3), **more complex targets** such as humans have an **incoherent response** if more than 3-4 GHz bandwidth is used.
3. Our experiments suggest that **higher carrier frequencies** (above 14 GHz) lead to a **less coherent response** for human targets. The carrier frequency dependency of the target response aspect is not considered in the current ISAC literature but is here shown to be significantly impacting the multi-band combination result. Further research is needed on this aspect to determine whether this is a characteristic of the target or a consequence of the slight movement of the person during the frequency sweep time, which leads to a larger phase variation at higher frequencies.

2.1.2. On Relation of Sensing Channels and Communication Channel

2.1.2.1. Introduction

To implement ISAC, existing studies predominantly focus on the allocation of shared spatial, frequency, or temporal resources, where communication beams, sub-carriers, or pilots are used simultaneously to detect targets or environmental changes. Architecturally, a monostatic sensing transceiver co-located with the communication transmitter (Tx) has gained popularity, where Tx and receiver (Rx) can be conceptualized as a bistatic architecture. In particular, monostatic sensing and bistatic communication can often use the same hardware and spectrum resources separately in time. Besides, when sensing and communication systems share the same environment, their respective channels are highly related because wireless channels for sensing and communication both depend on this environment. However, the geometric properties of this relationship remain unclear and require further investigation, which is the focus of this work.

2.1.2.2. SOTA and Contributions

To distinguish between sensing and communication channels, in the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), the ongoing study on ISAC channel modeling focuses on stochastic target channels and deterministic background channels within a bistatic setup [14]. To unify ISAC channel modeling, the RCS plays an important role in determining the reflection coefficient in the communication channels.

In the literature, there are some studies that have investigated this relationship between sensing and communication channels. In [15], the authors conducted channel measurements using a deployment in which the monostatic sensing radar was co-located with the communication Tx. This setup allowed them to characterize shared clusters of communication and sensing channels, but did not measure the channel surrounding the communication Rx. Additionally, [16] employed a similar setup to measure both sensing and communication channels, revealing that the sensing channels contained additional scatterers not observed in the communication channels, e.g., scatterers located around one node but hidden from the other node. This finding implies that, in certain configurations, the communication channel can be viewed as a subset of the sensing channels, i.e., only a subset of scatterers are exposed to both Tx and Rx. To address this limitation, [17] deployed two monostatic sensing transceivers for both Tx and Rx. This configuration ensured that the combined sensing channels included all scatterers in the environment, including those exposed to both Tx and Rx and those hidden from at least one of the nodes. In fact, given subcarrier spacing and bandwidth in wideband systems such as OFDM, both sensing and communication regions bounding the exposed scatterers can be geometrically determined. Consequently, the communication channel is a subset of the combined sensing channels, which facilitates the extraction of communication channels from high-resolution sensing data if we can determine the exposed subset of scatterers and eliminate the ones hidden from either Tx or Rx. In summary, our contributions include:

- We developed a framework for the geometry-based ISAC channel representation. From self-blockage detection to delay, angle, and power reconstruction, it efficiently constructs a communication channel from sensing channels.
- We conducted channel measurement and ray-tracing (RT) simulation to validate the proposed framework. Quantitative accuracy demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

Figure 2.5: An illustration of the considered ISAC geometry, including communication Tx and Rx, along with the detectable regions for both sensing and communication. The blue squares represent scatterers hidden in the communication channel, while the red circles indicate exposed scatterers.

2.1.2.3. Use within MultiX

The proposed framework aims to reveal the relationship of sensing and communication channels given certain configurations, such as monostatic sensing, and different subcarrier spacing between sensing and communication signals. It is the first step for the comprehensive ISAC channel modeling in T3.1 of MultiX, where we will consider the RCS, unified ISAC channel formulation, and more validations.

2.1.2.4. System model

In Fig. 2.5, we illustrate the considered ISAC geometry and the detectable regions constrained by frequency spacing. We denote the bandwidth and frequency spacing as B , Δf_c , and Δf_s , considering a general multi-carrier waveform with variable sub-carrier spacing that allows to ensure the sensing and communication regions to overlap.

In monostatic sensing, the detectable region is represented as a circle with a radius of $r_s = \tau_s^{\max} \cdot c$ where we have $\tau_s^{\max} = \frac{1}{2\Delta f_s}$ and c is the speed of light in vacuum. Taking into account the communication system parameters, the detectable region where scatterers are located becomes an ellipse, where scatterers are often called interacting objects (IO). The detectable excess delay for communication is denoted as $\tau_c^{\max} = \frac{1}{\Delta f_c}$, and the corresponding maximum distance of multipath is $r_c = \tau_c^{\max} \cdot c + d_{\text{LoS}}$, where d_{LoS} is the LoS distance. To be able to construct the entire communication channel, it is required that the sensing region covers the region determined by the communication channel's excess delay. The relationship between Δf_s and Δf_c is bounded as $\frac{1}{\Delta f_s} \geq \frac{1}{\Delta f_c} + \frac{d_{\text{LoS}}}{c}$. A slightly smaller Δf_s ensures the communication channel region is a subset of the combined sensing regions. For example, for $\Delta f_c = 120$ KHz, the maximum Δf_s is 119.76 KHz and 115.38 KHz, considering d_{LoS} is 5 m and 100 m, respectively. In the paper, we consistently use this maximum Δf_s for given Δf_c and d_{LoS} . We then calculate the lengths of the minor and major axes of the ellipse:

$$b = \sqrt{\left(\frac{r_c}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{d_{\text{LoS}}}{2}\right)^2}, \quad a = \sqrt{b^2 + \left(\frac{d_{\text{LoS}}}{2}\right)^2}. \quad (2.5)$$

The practical detectable areas are also related to other aspects, such as the minimum received power. To this end, we first consider the RCS of scatterers and then take into account the dynamic range of the system and the noise power.

Sensing channels: Considering the delay, angle, and amplitude, the sensing channels observed by the Tx in a single snapshot can be represented as follows:

$$h_T = \sum_{p=1}^P \alpha_p e^{-j2\pi f_c \tau_p} \delta(\tau - \tau_p) \delta(\phi_{\text{AoD}} - \phi_p), \quad (2.6)$$

where P is the number of detected scatterers, $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta function, and α_p denotes the channel gain of the p -th scatterer, which is related to the RCS and the distance to the scatterer. Moreover, f_c is the central frequency, τ_p is the round-trip delay of an echo, ϕ_p is the angle of departure (AoD). For the Rx side, the sensing channel can be expressed similarly as

$$h_R = \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k e^{-j2\pi f_c \tau_k} \delta(\tau - \tau_k) \delta(\phi_{\text{AoA}} - \phi_k), \quad (2.7)$$

where K is the number of scatterers, β_k represents the channel gain, and ϕ_k is the angle of arrival (AoA). To generalize the framework, we consider single-bounce propagation with point scatterers. Then, the received power of an echo in the Rx sensing channel is

$$P_r^s = \frac{P_t G^2 \lambda^2 \sigma_k}{(4\pi)^3 R_k^4}, \quad (2.8)$$

where P_t and G are the transmit power and antenna gain, respectively. In addition, λ and σ_k are the wavelength and RCS of the k -th scatterer, respectively. Lastly, the range is calculated by $R_k = \tau_k c/2$. As Tx is the same as Rx, the sensing channel around Tx can be represented similarly, assuming P instead of K scatterers. To generalize the framework, we allow describing the RCS with a probability density function. Considering a stochastic scattering environment without a dominant component in monostatic sensing, the RCS follows an exponential distribution [18]:

$$p_\sigma(\sigma) = \frac{1}{\bar{\sigma}} e^{-\frac{\sigma}{\bar{\sigma}}}, \quad (2.9)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}$ is the mean value of RCS. We found that the amplitudes α and β follow the Rayleigh distribution because of $\alpha = \sqrt{P_r^s} \sim \sqrt{\sigma}$. This reflects real-world propagation conditions, considering scatterers that create Non Line-of-Sight (NLoS) components in communication. The LoS component is added to the communication channel afterward because we assume d_{LoS} is known, and its power and delay are deterministic for a given frequency.

Communication channel: The channel impulse response (CIR) can be represented as a scatterer-based form, which is expressed by

$$h(\tau, \psi, \varphi) = \sum_{i=1}^C \eta_i e^{-j2\pi f_c \tau_i} \delta(\tau - \tau_i) \delta(\psi - \psi_i) \delta(\varphi - \varphi_i), \quad (2.10)$$

where τ , ψ , and φ represent the delay, AoD, and AoA of scatterers in the communication region. Moreover, the number of communication scatterers is denoted as C , excluding the LoS component. For the directional channels, the array patterns can be considered to filter out the scatterers outside the beams.

We then highlight **two types of channels**: *Channel impulse response*: We construct the communication CIR by leveraging two sensing channels, h_T and h_R , using a mapping function: $\mathbf{h} = \mathcal{F}(h_T, h_R)$ with exploiting scatterer selection, delay, angle, and power construction, thus resulting in a propagation channel $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^{C \times 1}$ where \mathbb{C} denotes complex value. *Channel state information*: To derive practical CSI, we take into account the system's bandwidth. Adjacent MPCs are combined within a delay bin. The total number of delay bins is given by $N = B/\Delta f_c$. The resulting CSI is then represented as $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$.

2.1.2.5. Construction Method

The following steps are conducted to determine \mathcal{F} : 1) Detection of blockage among scatterers and removal of blocked scatterers from h_T and h_R , 2) Determine communication scatterers $i \in \{1, \dots, C\}$ as a subset of the sensing scatterers $p \in \{1, \dots, P\}$ and $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, 3) Construct the bistatic communication delay τ_i from the detection of monostatic τ_p and τ_k , 4) Construct the communications angles ψ_i and φ_i from the sensing ϕ_p and ϕ_k , 5) Construct amplitude η_i from sensing α_p and β_k . The details are described as follows.

1. The blockage detection process consists of examining the potentially blocked scatterers and excluding them from the sensing channels. In a situation where two scatterers i and j have a very small difference between their AoDs (using a monostatic Tx sensor as an example), the farther scatterer will be blocked by the one nearer the sensor. In the end, we use an angular threshold ϕ_{th} to determine the proximity between the scatterers. We first examine all scatterers to see whether $|\phi_p^i - \phi_p^j| < \phi_{\text{th}}$, then remove the i -th scatterer from \mathbf{h}_T if $\tau_p^i - \tau_p^j > 0$. The same process is conducted at the monostatic Rx side for \mathbf{h}_R .

2. We then select the sensing scatterers relevant to the communication channel. Geometrically, we focus on scatterers located within the ellipse defined by the communication area. To do this, we first determine the delay τ_p^e that reaches the ellipse boundary for specific ϕ_p (similarly for ϕ_k). Effective scatterers for communications are then selected based on whether $\tau_p/2 \leq \tau_p^e$ holds.

Using the parametric equations of the ellipse, and taking the Tx as the origin in a local coordinate system, we can calculate the distance (d_p^e) between the Tx and the boundary of the ellipse as

$$d_p^e = \frac{a(1 - \epsilon^2)}{1 - \epsilon \cos(\phi_p)}, \quad d_k^e = \frac{a(1 - \epsilon^2)}{1 + \epsilon \cos(\phi_k)}. \quad (2.11)$$

where $\epsilon = \frac{d_{\text{LoS}}}{2a}$ is the eccentricity. Similarly, this distance at the Rx side is d_k^e above. Correspondingly, we have $\tau_p^e = d_p^e/c$ and $\tau_k^e = d_k^e/c$, then all C communication scatterers are determined as the subset $C \leq P + K$ for which $\tau_p/2 \leq \tau_p^e$ and $\tau_k/2 \leq \tau_k^e$ hold.

3. We consider the selected scatterers after Step 1 and 2, denoting $C = P' + K'$, where P' and K' are the numbers of scatterers chosen at Tx and Rx, respectively. We express their delays as $\tau_{p'}^t = \tau_{p'}/2$ and $\tau_{k'}^r = \tau_{k'}/2$, representing the incident and reflected delays of the first-order multipath in the communication channel, respectively. Some scatterers may be located in the overlapping area of two sensing circles, in which case the overall delay is the sum of $\tau_{p'}^t$ and $\tau_{k'}^r$. When only one delay is known, for $\tau_{p'}^t$ and $\tau_{k'}^r$, we can calculate the other delay, respectively, expressed as:

$$\tau_{p'}^r = \frac{1}{c} \sqrt{d_{\text{LoS}}^2 + (c\tau_{p'}^t)^2 - 2cd_{\text{LoS}}\tau_{p'}^t \cos(\phi_{p'})}, \quad (2.12)$$

$$\tau_{k'}^t = \frac{1}{c} \sqrt{d_{\text{LoS}}^2 + (c\tau_{k'}^r)^2 - 2cd_{\text{LoS}}\tau_{k'}^r \cos(\phi_{k'})}. \quad (2.13)$$

Finally, the delay for each scatterer is given by $\tau_i = \tau_{p'}^t + \tau_{p'}^r$ and $\tau_i = \tau_{k'}^t + \tau_{k'}^r$ with $i = 1 \dots C$.

4. We determine the AoD ψ and AoA φ of the resolved communication multipath based on $\phi_{p'}$, $\phi_{k'}$ and the delay information. Note that ψ and φ range from 0 to 2π , representing a counterclockwise rotation along the LoS starting from the right sides of Tx and Rx.

If the AoA or AoD is known for a single MPC, the missing angle can be calculated. Specifically, for $\phi_{p'}$, the corresponding AoA is computed by

$$\varphi_{p'} = \begin{cases} \pi - \arcsin\left(\frac{\tau_{p'}^t}{\tau_{p'}^r} \sin(\phi_{p'})\right), & \phi_{p'} \in [0, \pi), \\ \pi + \arcsin\left(\frac{\tau_{p'}^t}{\tau_{p'}^r} \sin(2\pi - \phi_{p'})\right), & \phi_{p'} \in [\pi, 2\pi). \end{cases} \quad (2.14)$$

Similarly, for $\phi_{k'}$, we have $\psi_{k'}$ that can be calculated by

$$\psi_{k'} = \begin{cases} \arcsin\left(\frac{\tau_{k'}^r}{\tau_{k'}^t} \sin(\pi - \phi_{k'})\right), & \phi_{k'} \in [0, \pi), \\ 2\pi - \arcsin\left(\frac{\tau_{k'}^r}{\tau_{k'}^t} \sin(\phi_{k'} - \pi)\right), & \phi_{k'} \in [\pi, 2\pi). \end{cases} \quad (2.15)$$

Thus, for each MPC i , the AoD ψ and AoA φ are given by merging two sets of angles, expressed by $\psi_i = \{\phi_{p'}, \psi_{k'}\}$ and $\varphi_i = \{\varphi_{p'}, \phi_{k'}\}$.

5. We first extract the monostatic RCS of each selected scattering path k' from Eq. (2.8). The monostatic RCS is expressed as

$$\sigma_{k'} = \frac{\alpha_{k'}^2 (4\pi)^3 R_{k'}^4}{P_t G^2 \lambda^2}. \quad (2.16)$$

Note that the calculation of $\sigma_{p'}$ is similar to $\sigma_{k'}$. We then denote $\sigma^i \in \{\sigma_{p'}, \sigma_{k'}\}$. In [19], it is shown that the bistatic RCS can be derived from the monostatic RCS. We use the following simplified equivalence from [20] to estimate the bistatic RCS,

$$\sigma_B^i = \sigma^i \cos\left(\frac{\Theta_B^i}{2}\right), \quad (2.17)$$

Figure 2.6: Measurement setup with $B = 1.76$ GHz and $\Delta f_c = 13.75$ MHz, where the system operates at 62.64 GHz with a bandwidth of 1.76 GHz. The system adheres to the IEEE 802.11ay protocol, where the channel estimation field (CEF) consists of complementary Golay sequences of length 128, included in the preamble for channel estimation. This results in a frequency spacing of $\Delta f_c = 13.75$ MHz ($B/128$).

where the bistatic angle Θ_B^i is given by $\Theta_B^i = \varphi_i - \psi_i$ for $\varphi_i \in [0, \pi)$ and $\Theta_B^i = \psi_i - \varphi_i$ for $\varphi_i \in [\pi, 2\pi)$ according to the geometry.

Substituting the delay, we can obtain the received power of the i th communication scatterer:

$$P_r^i = \frac{P_t G_t G_r \sigma_B^i}{(4\pi)^3 (\tau_t^2 \tau_r^2) c^2 f_c^2}, \quad (2.18)$$

where τ_t represents $\{\tau_{p'}^t, \tau_{k'}^t\}$ and τ_r is $\{\tau_{p'}^r, \tau_{k'}^r\}$. G_t and G_r represent antenna gains at Tx and Rx, respectively. The amplitude of the communication channel gain is given by $\eta_i = \sqrt{P_r^i}$.

After completing all the steps, we can generate the complex communication CIR, with the phase calculated as $2\pi f_c \tau_i$.

2.1.2.6. Validation

To validate the proposed framework, we first evaluate it using a standard measurement system operating at 62.64 GHz with a bandwidth of 1.76 GHz, where the channel estimation field (CEF) consists of complementary Golay sequences of length 128, ensuring that the channel is accurately estimated from the Golay correlator. As shown in Fig. 2.6, the experimental setup involves both monostatic and bistatic configurations to characterize the multipath channel in an indoor environment with $d_{\text{LoS}} = 4$ m. In the monostatic configuration, the Tx and Rx are co-located on a rotating platform covered with radio-frequency absorbers to mitigate the reflections from the platform. As the platform rotates precisely, this setup allows angular scanning in $[-60^\circ, 60^\circ]$ with a step of 5° to obtain both AoD and AoA. In addition, we use the narrow beam generated by an array 8×8 , with a half-power beamwidth (HPBW) of 12° .

In the bistatic configuration, Tx and Rx are spatially separated at the two monostatic locations. Moreover, a wide HPBW of 120° is used to capture a quasi-omnidirectional communication channel. The measurement environment includes some reflective surfaces, such as a metallic plate, a cylinder reflector, walls, and other scattering elements, which contribute to the observed multipaths.

As shown in Fig. 2.7, power delay profiles (PDPs) for monostatic sensing at certain angles and bistatic communication are included. First, we observe strong reflections from the metal plate, wall, cylinder reflector, and other potential scattering from air conditioning and other laboratory facilities. These scatterers are located based on the relative delay compared to LoS and verified by a laser distance meter. However, in the measured communication channel, although the beam is wide, we only observe two strong reflections in addition to the LoS, due to the limited dynamic range (around 45 dB). We then locate these two reflections from the metal plate and the wall, with relative ground-truth delays of $\tau_{\text{metal}} = 3.977$ ns and $\tau_{\text{wall}} = 11.932$ ns, respectively.

We then employ the measured monostatic channels as input for the proposed framework. As both locations at Monostatic 1 and 2 can see the wall's reflection at $\phi_{\text{AoD}} = \phi_{\text{AoA}} = 55^\circ$, we can simply add the delays and obtain the constructed (relative) delay $\tau_{\text{wall}}^{\text{cons.}} = 11.952$ ns. However, the metallic plate's reflection was only seen at Monostatic 1 at $\phi_{\text{AoD}} = -40^\circ$ (or 320°), we then utilize Step 3 in the construction method to calculate

Figure 2.7: Channel measurement validation where there are two strong reflections in the bistatic channel with delays $\tau_{\text{metal}} = 3.977$ ns and $\tau_{\text{wall}} = 11.932$ ns.

Figure 2.8: Power angular delay profiles for two monostatic measurements, where the profiles are calibrated by shifting LoS to the delay of 0.

another delay from the plate to the location of Monostatic 2, resulting in a relative delay $\tau_{\text{metal}}^{\text{cons.}} = 3.944$ ns in the communication channel. The perfect alignment confirms the feasibility of the proposed framework.

2.1.2.7. Future work

Although we have constructed communication channels using sensing channels in specific directions, the angular profiles that cover a large range of directions are still the future focus. It not only impacts on multi-antenna system performance of communication, but also relates to the sensing performance. As shown in Fig. 2.8, we show comprehensive power delay angular profiles for two monostatic measurements. In the same environment, the MPC distributions for two locations present distinct characteristics. Moreover, by continuously capturing the channel in the angular domain, we found the birth and death process of multipath, which is another important characteristic for cluster-based channel modeling, adopted in the 3GPP.

2.1.3. Target RCS Modelling in ISAC Channel

2.1.3.1. Radar Cross Section: Parameters, Dependencies, and Modeling Boundaries

The RCS is a key parameter in the radar and ISAC fields, formally defined in ETSI TS 103 789 V1.1.1 [21] as the cross-sectional area of a perfectly reflecting sphere that produces the same reflected signal strength as the target under consideration. More generally, it represents the ratio of power backscattered per steradian in the radar direction to the incident power density intercepted by the target. In essence, RCS quantifies the detectability of an object under electromagnetic illumination and is central to ISAC system modeling, since different target classes interact with incident fields in distinct ways. RCS depends on several interrelated parameters. These include the frequency and polarization of the incident radio signal, the angle of incidence relative to the object's surface normal, the scattering angle toward the receiver, and the antenna pattern. Target-specific features such as size, shape, orientation, material composition, motion, and micro-motion also play a defining role. Because of these dependencies, RCS should not be treated as a fixed scalar value but rather as a dynamic property that reflects the joint influence of both the target and the system setup. The frequency dependence of RCS can be broadly categorized into three regions based on the ratio of object size to wavelength [22] [23]. In the Rayleigh region ($2\pi l/\lambda \ll 1$), scattering is dominated by dipole interactions. The Mie region ($2\pi l/\lambda \approx 1$) exhibits complex resonances that are sensitive to geometry and material. In the geometric region ($2\pi l/\lambda \gg 1$), scattering aligns with optical approximations. While most literature assumes high-frequency operation, ISAC applications may require modeling across all three regimes. Accurate modeling also requires distinguishing between near-field and far-field conditions. RCS theory generally assumes far-field plane-wave illumination, which requires the target to be located at distances greater than $(2D_{ant}^2)/\lambda$ from the transmitter (Tx) or the receiver (Rx), where D_{ant} is the largest dimension of the antenna physical aperture [21] of either the Tx or the Rx. Additionally, the Tx and the Rx to be considered in the far-field of the object, the distance to the object should be greater than $(2D_{max}^{obj})/\lambda$, where D_{max}^{obj} is the object's maximum dimension [24]. In the near-field, these assumptions break down, and the representation of the target (as single- or multi-point scatterers) significantly influences RCS predictions. Assessing the sensitivity of RCS models to near- and far-field effects is therefore critical in practical deployments. Another distinction lies between monostatic and bistatic scenarios. In monostatic configurations, the transmitter and receiver are co-located, while in bistatic setups they are spatially separated. Most existing models and measurements focus on monostatic RCS, but bistatic RCS can often be derived using the Monostatic-to-Bistatic Equivalent Theorem (MBET) [24]. This capability is especially important for distributed and cooperative ISAC systems. Finally, the geometry and material composition of a target strongly shape its RCS. Closed-form formulations exist for canonical shapes such as spheres, plates, and trihedrals [24], but complex geometries generally require decomposition into simpler primitives, whose scattering contributions can be combined [24–26]. Material properties also matter: while perfect conductors provide an upper bound on reflectivity, realistic materials can be approximated by scaling the perfect-conductor RCS with their reflectivity factor [27]. These considerations allow for practical yet accurate modeling of real-world objects.

2.1.3.2. Approaches for Modeling Object RCS

The modeling of object RCS can broadly be categorized into two methodological paradigms: top-down and bottom-up approaches. In the top-down approach, the RCS is derived empirically by evaluating the ratio of the scattered to the incident electric fields associated with the object under investigation. These field values can be obtained through controlled measurement campaigns, Electromagnetic (EM) numerical simulations, or deterministic ray-tracing techniques. The RCS is formally expressed as:

$$\sigma = \lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} 4\pi R^2 \frac{|E_s|^2}{|E_i|^2} \quad (2.19)$$

where R denotes the distance from the receiver to the target (i.e., the point at which the scattered field is observed), and E_s , E_i represent the scattered and incident electric fields, respectively. Conversely, the bottom-up approach is rooted in electromagnetic propagation theory, wherein closed-form expressions for both incident and scattered fields are derived analytically. While such formulations provide a rigorous basis for canonical geometries (e.g., spheres, plates, dihedrals), practical deployment often necessitates calibration against empirical measurements or high-fidelity numerical simulations to ensure validity under real-world conditions. Each approach presents distinct advantages and limitations. Top-down methods are particularly suited for complex and irregular targets, such as humans or vehicles, where analytical formulations are intractable. However,

Figure 2.9: RCS at different aspect angles and separation distances from the sensing receiver

the resulting models are often scenario-specific, with limited generalizability beyond the measured context. Bottom-up methods, on the other hand, offer scalability across frequencies, materials, and object dimensions, making them highly adaptable for canonical shapes. Their main drawback lies in the difficulty of extending these formulations to arbitrarily complex geometries without significant approximations. A potential avenue for reconciling the two modeling paradigms is the adoption of multipoint representations of the target. In this context, we propose two methodologies for multipoint RCS modeling: (i) the segmentation-based approach and (ii) the electromagnetic-based approach.

2.1.3.3. Segmentation approach

Segmentation constitutes one approach for constructing multipoint representations of a target in RCS modeling [24, 27]. The principle is to decompose a complex object into a set of simpler canonical components, each with well-established RCS characteristics. For instance, in [24], a traffic sign is represented by two basic elements: a cylindrical segment modeling the supporting pillar, and a rectangular segment modeling the sign plate. Formally, the target object is partitioned into N segments, with each segment assigned an RCS value σ_i . The value of σ_i depends on the segment's geometric shape (e.g., circular, rectangular), its dimensions, and the operating frequency. The overall average RCS of the composite object, σ_{obj} , can then be expressed as [13]:

$$\sigma_{obj} = \left| \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\sigma_i} e^{j\phi_i} \right|^2 \quad (2.20)$$

where N is the number of the object segments and ϕ_i is the phase difference between the i -th segment and the first segment. ϕ_i can be calculated as $\phi_i = k\Delta d_i$ where k is the wave-vector number, and Δd_i is the difference in the signal propagation path length between the i -th segment and the 1st reference segment.

The computation of an object's RCS critically depends on whether the incident and scattered electromagnetic waves can be approximated as plane waves. This approximation holds only if the far-field condition is satisfied [24]. If the condition is violated, the plane-wave assumption is invalid, and an alternative representation is required. In such cases, a segmentation-based approach is employed. The scattering object is decomposed into N segments, where N is constrained to lie within the range $[N_{min}, N_{max}]$. The lower bound, N_{min} , is determined such that the maximum dimension of each segment, D_{max}^{seg} , satisfies the far-field requirement that can be formulated as:

$$\min(r_{Tx-seg}, r_{seg-Rx}) > \frac{2(D_{max}^{seg})^2}{\lambda} \quad (2.21)$$

where r_{Tx-seg}, r_{seg-Rx} are the distance between the Tx and Rx to the target segment, respectively and λ is the carrier wavelength. Conversely, the upper bound, N_{max} , is established to ensure that D_{max}^{seg} remains larger than the carrier wavelength, thereby preserving the physical relevance of each segment in the scattering model. Fig. 2.9 illustrates the RCS of a metallic plate evaluated across varying aspect angles and separation distances relative to the sensing receiver. The aspect angle is defined as the mean of the incidence and scattering angles,

both measured with respect to the plate's surface normal. The results demonstrate a fast-fading behavior, with pronounced fluctuations in RCS as the aspect angle changes. This indicates that the RCS exhibits a fading component that is highly sensitive to angular variation—specifically the Angle of Arrival (AoA) and Angle of Departure (AoD) relative to the sensing cluster. Accordingly, the RCS of a sensing target, expressed in dBsm, can be decomposed into two principal components: RCS^{SF} and RCS^{FF} , representing the slow-fading and fast-fading contributions, respectively. The slow-fading component (RCS^{SF}) is governed by intrinsic target characteristics (e.g., shape, size, material composition, and separation distance from the Tx/Rx) as well as certain signal parameters (e.g., carrier frequency, polarization). The fast-fading component (RCS^{FF}) depends on the incidence and scattering angles and varies dynamically with changes in target orientation relative to the Tx/Rx. In this sense, RCS^{FF} can be interpreted as a model of the target's directional RCS gain in a given angular direction. Within the ETSI ISAC Industrial Specification Group (ISG) framework, it has been proposed that both RCS components be incorporated into the ISAC channel model: the slow-fading component should be mapped to the channel's large-scale parameters, while the fast-fading component should be reflected in its small-scale parameters.

2.1.3.4. Electromagnetic based approach

For scenarios involving multiple targets located within close proximity relative to the carrier wavelength, the average RCS can be approximated using a segmentation-based approach in which each target is treated as an independent segment. However, this formulation neglects mutual interactions—both among the constituent segments of a single target and between distinct targets when they are closely spaced.

Discrete scattering models approximate wave–target interactions (electromagnetic, acoustic, etc.) by discretizing continuous media or structures into finite elements such as point dipoles, grids, voxels, or surface currents [14][15]. A widely used example is the Discrete Dipole Approximation (DDA) [15], in which the target is represented as an array of closely spaced point dipoles. Each dipole corresponds to a small volume element of the original structure and scatters incident energy according to its polarization response.

In this subsection, we adopt a related methodology by subdividing a 2D object into regular elements for analyzing multi-scattering-point problems. Each element is modeled as an infinitely long cylinder with its axis aligned along the z-direction in Cartesian coordinates. This configuration enforces translational symmetry, thereby restricting electromagnetic interactions to the transverse (x–y) plane. As a result, the problem reduces to 2D scattering while preserving the essential physical mechanisms of wave interaction. The scattered field from each cylindrical element is derived analytically, and the total scattered field is obtained by coherently summing the contributions of all elements while accounting for their mutual interactions. Within the electromagnetic approach, we first derive the expression for the scattered electric field generated by a single perfectly electric conducting (PEC) cylinder.

Consider a single PEC cylinder of radius a , illuminated by a TM-polarized electromagnetic wave. A current filament parallel to the cylinder axis carries time-harmonic current I_t , located at $\rho_t = (\rho_t, \varphi_t)$. In this scenario, the scattered electric field at $\rho = (\rho, \varphi)$ can be expressed as:

$$E_z^s \approx -\frac{\omega\mu_0}{4} I_t \left(-\frac{J_0(k_0 a)}{H_0^{(2)}(k_0 a)} \right) H_0^{(2)}(k_0 \rho_t) H_0^{(2)}(k_0 \rho). \quad (2.22)$$

where E_z^s is the scattered electric field, ω is the angular frequency, μ_0 is the free space permeability, $J_0()$ and $H_0^{(2)}()$ are Bessel function of the first kind and Hankel function of the second kind, respectively, k_0 is the wave vector. Regarding the case of two cylinders, consider two PEC cylinders with radii a and b , located at positions ρ_1 and ρ_2 respectively. The system is excited by a current filament at ρ_t carrying current I_t . Each cylinder generates equivalent secondary currents:

- Cylinder 1: I_1^S
- Cylinder 2: I_2^S

The total received field at ρ_r is:

$$E_z^r = I_t \left(T_5 + \frac{T_1 T_3 + T_2 T_4 + T_1 R_{12} T_4 + T_2 R_{21} T_3}{1 - R_{12} R_{21}} \right) \quad (2.23)$$

with signal flow parameters:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_1 &= \Gamma_0(k_0 a) H_0^{(2)}(k_0 \rho_{1t}), & T_2 &= \Gamma_0(k_0 b) H_0^{(2)}(k_0 \rho_{2t}), \\
 T_3 &= -\frac{\omega \mu_0}{4} H_0^{(2)}(k_0 \rho_{r1}), & T_4 &= -\frac{\omega \mu_0}{4} H_0^{(2)}(k_0 \rho_{r2}), \\
 T_5 &= -\frac{\omega \mu_0}{4} H_0^{(2)}(k_0 \rho_{rt}), \\
 R_{12} &= \Gamma_0(k_0 a) H_0^{(2)}(k_0 \rho_{12}), & R_{21} &= \Gamma_0(k_0 b) H_0^{(2)}(k_0 \rho_{12}).
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.24}$$

where $\Gamma_0(\cdot) = -J_0(\cdot)/H_0^{(2)}(\cdot)$. The proof of the equation (2.23) can be found in [28]. Using equation (2.23), we propose the enhanced RCS formula of the two-cylinders taking into account the electromagnetic interactions between the two cylinders. The enhanced RCS can be expressed as:

$$\sigma = \frac{4}{k_0} \cdot \frac{|\Gamma_a + \Gamma_b e^{-2jk_0 d \cos \theta} + H_{12} e^{-jk_0 d \cos \theta} (\Gamma_a^2 + \Gamma_b^2)|^2}{|1 - \Gamma_a \Gamma_b H_{12}^2|^2} \tag{2.25}$$

where $H_{12} = H_0^{(2)}(k_0 d)$, and $\Gamma_a = \Gamma_0(k_0 a)$, $\Gamma_b = \Gamma_0(k_0 b)$. When the mutual coupling is negligible ($H_{12} \rightarrow 0$) and the radii of the two cylinders are not significantly different. $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma_{\text{seg}}$ demonstrating backward compatibility with the segmentation method.

2.1.3.5. Numerical Results

In this section, we aim to examine the discrepancy in 2D RCS calculations between the proposed EM-based method and the conventional segmentation approach. In the simulations, we consider operation in both 28 GHz and 15 GHz frequency bands, corresponding to wavelengths of $\lambda_0 = 10.7$ mm and $\lambda_0 = 20$ mm, respectively. For sensing target modelling, we consider two cylinders with identical radii of $0.04\lambda_0$ (0.428 mm).

To further investigate the impact of the inter-cylinder distance d on the RCS, we fix the incidence angle θ at 45° and analyze the RCS variation as a function of d . The inter-cylinder distance can represent the inter-distance between two targets or the inter-distance between two scattering points that belong to the same target.

As shown in Fig. 2.10, the results clearly reveal a critical limitation of conventional non-coupled analysis methods — by neglecting mutual coupling effects between scattering points, these methods exhibit significant discrepancies exceeding 20 dB at certain values of d when compared to our discrete scattering method across both frequency points, demonstrating that strong near-field coupling between adjacent components can induce pronounced interference effects in the composite scattered field.

Different incident angles will lead to different RCS results. Therefore, to further explore the relationship between mutual coupling effects and d , we compute the root-mean-square error (RMSE) between the segmented and EM-based RCS models as shown in (2.26) over multiple observation angles.

$$RMSE(d) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M [\sigma_{\text{seg}}(\theta_m, d) - \sigma_{\text{EM}}(\theta_m, d)]^2} \tag{2.26}$$

where $M = 180$ represents the total number of angular samples covering the full azimuthal range from 0° to 180° , θ_m denotes the m -th incidence angle, while $\sigma_{\text{seg}}(\theta_m, d)$ and $\sigma_{\text{EM}}(\theta_m, d)$ correspond to the 2D RCS (in dBm) obtained from the segmentation method and EM scattering method, respectively, for each angle θ_m at separation distance d . This metric systematically evaluates the angular-averaged deviation between two models, thereby quantitatively characterizing their distance-dependent discrepancies arising from mutual coupling effects.

Fig. 2.11 illustrates the variation of RMSE with separation distance d , where the decreasing RMSE with increasing d indicates a gradual weakening of mutual coupling effects. This trend can be derived from (2.25): the inter-cylinder coupling is described by Hankel functions $H_0^{(2)}(kd)$, whose magnitudes decay asymptotically as $|H_0^{(2)}(kd)| \sim \sqrt{2/(\pi kd)}$ for large kd . Accordingly, the coupling strength diminishes as d increases, in line with the observed RMSE reduction. Moreover, an exponential fitting model—represented by the dashed curve in the figure—quantitatively captures this behavior, confirming that the coupling-induced deviation decays exponentially with d .

(a) 28 GHz

(b) 15 GHz

Figure 2.10: Variation of 2D RCS with respect to d at 28 GHz and 15 GHz

Figure 2.11: Variation of RMSE with respect to d .

2.1.4. ISAC channel modelling for phone case effect

2.1.4.1. Motivation

ISAC systems leverage wireless signals for both communication and environmental sensing. While extensive research has been conducted on ISAC channel modeling, the influence of mobile device accessories, particularly phone cases, has largely been overlooked. We investigate the impact of phone cases on monostatic sensing, where self-interference caused by reflections from the phone case may significantly degrade sensing performance. We conduct channel measurements with and without various phone cases and propose a channel modeling methodology to account for their effects. The proposed model captures the altered channel characteristics due to phone case reflections, providing insights for ISAC system design and optimization.

2.1.4.2. Introduction

The increasing demand for ISAC technology has led to extensive research in channel modeling. However, conventional models fail to consider the impact of device accessories such as phone cases, which can introduce significant self-interference in monostatic sensing scenarios. We aim at addressing this gap by analyzing experimental results and developing a modeling framework that accurately represents phone case effects. Most mobile phone users use protective cases for durability and aesthetic purposes. Despite their widespread use, phone cases have not been systematically considered in ISAC channel modeling. The presence of a phone case alters the electromagnetic properties of the device, introducing additional reflections and modifying the propagation characteristics of the transmitted and received signals. In monostatic sensing, these effects are particularly pronounced due to the strong self-interference caused by signal reflections from the phone case. This can severely impact the ability of ISAC systems to accurately detect desired targets, leading to degraded sensing performance. Therefore, a dedicated modeling approach is necessary to understand and mitigate these effects, ensuring robust ISAC operation in real-world scenarios.

2.1.4.3. Measurement Setup

To analyze the influence of phone cases on ISAC channel characteristics, we conducted controlled channel measurements in a laboratory setting. The measurements involved:

- **Carrier Frequency:** 28 GHz
- **Bandwidth:** 3.35 GHz
- **Measurement Scenarios:**
 - Without phone case (reference scenario)
 - Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU) phone case
 - Silicon phone case
- **Target:**
 - **RCS:** tetrahedral corner reflector has RCS=2.07 dBsm
 - **Distance:** 31 cm, 52 cm

Figure 2.12 illustrates the measurement setup.

2.1.4.4. Phone case effect channel modeling

We firstly consider the channel model without phone case effect as illustrated in Figure 2.13. This figure represents a monostatic ISAC channel model, illustrating how transmitted signals interact with a target and the resulting reflections affect the received signals.

Key Components can be summarized as follows:

1. Target Transmit Path:

- The transmitted (Tx) signal is generated and sent through a transmitter.

Figure 2.12: Illustration of measurement setup

- The signal undergoes path loss and delay from Tx to target, representing the attenuation of the signal as it propagates through the channel.
- The signal reaches the target, where the RCS characterizes the target's reflection properties.

2. Target Reflection Paths:

- After hitting the target, the signal reflects and travels through multiple paths toward the receiver equipped with multiple Rx antennas.
- Each reflect path consists of:
 - A reflected signal, processed through a receiver.
 - Path loss and delay which account for additional attenuation and delay in different reflection paths.

3. Received Signals (Rx Signal 1 to Rx Signal N):

- The reflected signals from the target are received by different receiver paths.
- Each received signal is affected by additive noise, which represents environmental noise and system imperfections.
- The received signals at different paths contribute to the overall sensing and communication performance of the ISAC system.

2.1.4.4.1 Channel measurement results – self interference

We measure self-interference power and phase based on the setup described in Section 2.1.4.3. Tab. 2.1 presents measured self-interference power and phase for different phone cases (including bare – without phone case). The self-interference occurs due to the short distance between the antenna and the phone case. Due to the limited sensing resolution, there is no delay in time tap for the self-interference, but there is a phase change from the phone cases. We calculate the estimated sensing distance based on phase values, i.e., $d = \frac{\phi\lambda}{4\pi}$, where ϕ and λ denote phase value and the wavelength, respectively. The estimated distance from the phase is on the same order of the phone case thickness. Based on this measurement, depending on the phone case, an increase in self-interference of more than 10 dB than the bare phone case was observed, and the phase of the corresponding tap can have different phase values depending on the thickness of the phone case. Note that the phone case-induced self-interference increase is relative to the bare case. To incorporate this measurement into the channel model, the self-interference level needs to be represented with a negative dB value relative to the transmit power. We measured that the self-interference increases by 12.4 dB and 10.66 dB for the silicone and TPU cases, respectively, when compared to the bare case. In [29], the RF isolation ranges for radar or full duplex radio in mmWave are approximately -25 dB to -50 dB¹. For instance, assuming that the

¹<https://microharmonics.com/mm-wave-circulator-with-high-transmitter-and-receiver-isolation/>

Figure 2.13: Channel model without phone case

Table 2.1: Self-interference power and phase

Phone Case	Self-interference power (dB)	Self-interference phase (rad)	Estimated distance (mm) from phase (+2 pi when it is minus value)
Bare	-6.69	1.3217	0.225
Silicone	5.71 (+12.4dB from bare)	-1.4779	0.819
TPU	3.97 (+10.66dB from bare)	-0.7621	0.941

bare case exhibits an Tx-Rx RF isolation of -30 dB, the corresponding self-interference levels for the silicone and TPU cases would be -17.6 dB and -19.34 dB, respectively.

So, we can conclude that:

1. Depending on the phone case, an increase in self-interference of more than 10 dB than the reference scenario (i.e., bare case) was observed.
2. The self-interference channel can be modeled as a single tap static channel with zero delay, and the corresponding tap's phase depends on the phone case's thickness.
3. To incorporate this measurement into the channel model, the self-interference level due to the phone case is increased from the bare case's RF isolation level.

2.1.4.4.2 Channel measurement results – impact on target channels

Tab. 2.2 summarizes the measured results in terms of target channels. To check the change with distance, we placed tetrahedral corner reflectors at a distance of 31 cm and 52 cm, respectively, and checked how much the phone case attenuated the target channel. The silicone case observed about 3 dB of attenuation irrespective of the target distance, which corresponds to two ways (tx-target and target-rx), so it is 1.5 dB attenuation in

Table 2.2: Target channel degradation

Phone Case	target channel power (dB) in 31 cm	target channel power (dB) in 52 cm
Bare	-19	-28
Silicone	-22 (+3dB from bare, 1.5dB for one way)	-31 (+3dB from bare, +1.5dB for one way)
TPU	-23 (+4dB from bare, +2dB for one way)	-32 (+4dB from bare, +2dB for one way)

Figure 2.14: Revised channel model with phone case

one way. The TPU case observed about 4 dB of attenuation regardless of distance, which is 2 dB attenuation in one way.

So, we can say that the silicone case caused 1.5 dB attenuation for one way (3 dB for two ways) and the TPU case caused 2 dB attenuation for one way (4 dB for two ways), with attenuation remaining consistent regardless of distance.

Based on the above findings, we can modify the channel model to reflect the impact of the phone case as follows. Figure 2.14 shows the revised channel model with a phone case. Here are key components of the revised channel model with phone case:

1. Target Transmit Path

- It's similar with the original model.
- However, before reaching the target, the transmitted signal is already affected by the phone case, introducing attenuation.

2. Self-Interference Path

- A self-interference path is explicitly included, which was missing in the original model without the phone case effects.
- Some of the transmitted signal leaks and interacts with the phone case due to its proximity to the antenna.
- This leaked signal undergoes additional path loss and contributes to unwanted self-interference.
- The self-interference is a major issue in monostatic sensing, as it can obscure the desired target reflection.

3. Target Reflection Paths

- After hitting the target, the signal propagates back along different receiver antenna paths.
- The reflected signal undergoes additional attenuation and phase shifts caused by the phone case before reaching the receiver.
- Different phone cases will introduce different levels of attenuation and phase distortion.

4. Received Signals

- The received signals consist of a combination of target reflections and self-interference.
- Additive noise is present in each received signal, representing environmental and system noise.
- The updated model highlights that the phone case affects not only the target reflections but also the self-interference.

Key differences from the original model are:

1. Explicit Inclusion of Self-Interference Path

- Fig. 3 introduces an additional self-interference path caused by the short distance between the phone case and the antenna.
- This leakage was not explicitly modeled in the original figure but is a critical issue for accurate ISAC channel modeling.

2. Impact of Phone Case on both the Transmit and Receive Paths

- The phone case attenuates and changes the phase of the transmitted signal before it reaches the target.
- The reflected signal from the target also undergoes additional attenuation and phase changes before being received, which was not explicitly highlighted in the previous version.

3. More Realistic Representation of Mono-Static ISAC Challenges

- The revised figure captures a more realistic self-interference issue in ISAC applications.
- In monostatic sensing, the large self-interference from the phone case can obscure the actual target reflection, making it harder to distinguish objects.

Figure 2.14 represents how self-interference generated from a phone case creates different signal paths, leading to self-interference and target channel attenuation. This model helps understand how reflections and noise influence target detection performance in ISAC systems, particularly when accounting for phone case-induced interferences in monostatic sensing setups. based on these measurements and studies following two aspects for ISAC channel model need to be improved:

1. The self-interference is modeled as a single tap static channel with zero delay, and the corresponding tap's amplitude and phase depend on the phone case.
2. The target channel has an additional attenuation due to phone case.

2.1.5. Localization using channel state information inferred from optimal RIS configuration

2.1.5.1. Context and Motivation.

A central objective for MultiX is to endow the radio infrastructure with embedded localization capabilities capable of performing sensing avoiding as much as possible disrupting the communications with intrusive procedures such as extra pilots or dedicated sweeps. Existing RIS-aided localization often requires time slots reserved for sensing, exhaustive codebook scans that degrade throughput, or complicated orchestration. In contrast, our contribution leverages the very RIS configuration $\bar{\theta}$ already optimized for communication as a means for localization. The key insight is that the configuration selected by the RIS controller is a deterministic (though noisy) function of the channel state information, dependant on the user's position u ; therefore, RIS configurations encode spatial information that can be opportunistically harvested without altering or reducing the performance of the communication loop. This paradigm, which we term *opportunistic ISAC*, promises low overhead and excellent compatibility with existing RIS control planes.

2.1.5.2. System Model and Assumptions.

We consider a RIS-assisted communication channel in which the RIS (modelled as a uniform planar array with $N=N_y N_z$ elements) is configured by a RIS controller running a standard communication-centric optimizer (e.g., coherent-path or AI-driven search). For each served UE, the controller outputs the optimized per-element phase configuration $\bar{\theta} \in [0, 2\pi)^N$. COLoRIS runs as an auxiliary module (which can be located in the RIS controller, on a co-located microcontroller, or in any other suitable point of the infrastructure) passively receiving $\bar{\theta}$ whenever the controller updates the surface for communication purposes. No changes to waveform, frame structure, or scheduler are required. We assume prior knowledge of the Base Station (BS)/RIS deployment (positions, panel layout, phase quantization) and acknowledge that controller-side CSI and actuation are noisy and quantized.

Figure 2.15: Schematic representation of COLoRIS

2.1.5.3. Problem Formulation and Feasibility.

We seek to infer u from a noisy observation of $\bar{\theta}$. To make an initial study of the feasibility of this objective, we employ the Fisher information (FI). Let $f_{\bar{\theta}}(\bar{\theta}; u)$ denote the likelihood of observing configuration $\bar{\theta}$ when the UE is at u . The FI matrix $J(u) = \mathbb{E}[\nabla_u \ln f_{\bar{\theta}}(\bar{\theta}; u) \cdot \nabla_u \ln f_{\bar{\theta}}(\bar{\theta}; u)^H]$ quantifies how sensitively the selected configuration reacts to perturbations of u . Its inverse lower-bounds the achievable error covariance through the Cramér-Rao Lower Bound (CRLB), $\text{cov}(\hat{u}) \succeq J^{-1}(u)$. In practice, the scalar $\sigma_{u, \text{CRLB}}(u) = \sqrt{\text{tr}(J^{-1}(u))}$, based on the trace of the inverse of the FI matrix, provides a meaningful metric for the limits of the achievable localization accuracy, allowing us, among other analysis, to map the accuracy bound as a function of the UE position. This metric also decompose additively over elements ($J(u) = \sum_{n=1}^N J_n(u)$), enabling per-element informativeness analysis that we exploit for model compression and embedded deployment.

2.1.5.4. Opportunistic ISAC Workflow.

The COLoRIS workflow (Fig. 2.15) is designed as a drop-in co-processor: each time the controller emits a new $\bar{\theta}$ to the RIS, a copy is forwarded to COLoRIS. Internally, COLoRIS implements (i) a *position estimator* $\hat{u}(\bar{\theta})$ and (ii) an *uncertainty estimator* $\hat{\sigma}_u(\bar{\theta})$ that provides the confidence in the position estimate. This additional figure allows COLoRIS to operate within an architecture focused on data fusion or sensor selection, both governed by the quality of the available measurements.

2.1.5.5. Learning-Based Estimator Design.

We produce our estimations $\hat{u}(\bar{\theta})$ with a deep neural network (DNN) that directly regresses coordinates from $\bar{\theta}$: an N -neuron input layer (one per element), two to four small hidden layers with hyperbolic tangent activation, and a D -neuron linear output layer (with $D=2$ or 3 , to represent UE positions in a plane or in 3D space). A second DNN is fed with the inaccuracies of the $\hat{u}(\bar{\theta})$ estimations, predicting $\hat{\sigma}_u(\bar{\theta})$. We test the robustness of

this setup across propagation regimes, as LoS vs. NLoS, and far- vs. near-field. Training data are obtained through simulations of UE positions across a field, and for each position a RIS configuration is generated, affected by noise but optimised solely for communication purposes. This information is divided in subsets to train the localization neural network, to train the error-estimation neural network, and to test the complete setup.

2.1.5.6. Use within MultiX

The COLoRIS module provides always-on, low power consumption localization from communication-optimized RIS configurations. It consumes those RIS configurations $\bar{\theta}$ and is able to expose UE localization estimates (and the expected errors). This enables ISAC without penalising throughput, contributing towards the objective of achieving sensing with minimal performance reduction in communications.

2.2. ISAC waveforms

Emerging ISAC applications place new demands on waveform design beyond those of conventional data transmission. Depending on the application and deployment scenarios, ranging from human and environmental sensing to UAV localization and tracking, ISAC waveforms may be sensing-centric, communication-centric, or jointly optimized. Classical radar waveforms (e.g., FMCW/PMCW) offer high sensing fidelity but limited data rates, whereas communication waveforms such as OFDM provide high spectral efficiency and flexibility but face challenges in Doppler resolution, ambiguity, and, in simultaneous transmit-and-receive operation, self-interference. More recently, OTFS has emerged as a promising jointly optimized waveform, particularly suited to high-mobility scenarios such as Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) networks, due to its sparse delay–Doppler representation and inherent reuse of communication pilots for sensing. Within this broad design space, the work summarized here focuses on communication-centric OFDM-based mmWave ISAC systems, addressing SI and its cancellation method. In addition, an enhanced OFDM processing pipeline is provided, in accordance with New Radio (NR). Together with complementary OTFS-based and sensing-centric approaches used for UAV localization, this highlights how different waveform options and processing strategies can be tailored to diverse 6G ISAC scenarios, rather than relying on a one-size-fits-all solution.

2.2.1. Self-interference cancellation in OFDM-ISAC systems

2.2.1.1. Introduction and Motivation

ISAC technology is one of the potential drivers of next-generation wireless networks (6G) that is expected to improve the quality and efficiency of wireless communications by integrating radar functionality with communications [30]. Pure communication systems favor time- and frequency-division duplexing schemes, meaning transmission and reception occur in different time slots or on different carrier frequencies. On the other hand, monostatic sensing requires simultaneous transmission and reception (STAR) in the same frequency band. Although more common to radar systems, STAR has also found its way in wireless communication systems under the name of in-band full duplex (IBFD) communications [31]. The main challenge with STAR, however, is self-interference (SI) – the over-the-air transmit signal coupling into the receiver path. The presence of strong SI can lead to saturation of the receive chain or reduce receiver’s dynamic range, lowering its gain and masking of weak signals that are reflected from the surroundings. Traditional approaches to mitigating SI in IBFD systems include passive attenuation (increasing the separation between transmit and receive antennas) and the implementation of an RF SI cancellation (SIC) circuits, supported by SI cancelers in the analog and digital baseband stages. However, these approaches are difficult to implement in existing communication systems without hardware modifications or the development of new hardware. This is particularly true for mmWave ISAC employing phased-array systems with large number of antennas. Implementing RF SIC between all transmit-receive antenna pairs would be extremely challenging and costly. Recently, a method for SI cancellation in antenna array systems, called null space projection (NSP), was introduced in [32]. The method uses the SI channel information to optimize the antenna weights (amplitude and phase of phase shifters) to reduce the amount of SI while still directing the beam in the desired direction. In this work we study the SI problem in beamforming mmWave OFDM-ISAC systems and analyze the sensing performance with and without SI cancellation.

2.2.1.2. System Model

A mmWave phased-array system equipped with transmit and receive uniform linear arrays (ULAs), each with N_a antennas, is considered, as shown in Fig. 2.16. The system is capable of full-duplex operation, performing communication and monostatic sensing in time-slotted manner. We assume a communication-centric ISAC system, where an OFDM waveform is used for both communication and sensing. In sensing time slots, beam scanning of the environment is performed such that the OFDM signal is transmitted in every beam direction and the signal reflected from the surroundings is processed by the receiver. In addition to the reflected signal, the received signal contains self-interference caused by the coupling of the transmitted signal due to the proximity of the Tx and Rx ULAs.

Figure 2.16: Beamforming mmWave OFDM-ISAC system.

After DFT processing at the receiver, the received signal at the k -th subcarrier in the beam direction θ_m reads

$$Y_k^m = \mathbf{w}_m^H \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{f}_m S_k + \mathbf{w}_m^H \mathbf{H}_{si,k} \mathbf{f}_m S_k + \mathbf{w}_m^H \mathbf{n}_k \quad (2.27)$$

where S_k denotes the pilot-data symbol used for channel estimation, \mathbf{n}_k is the N_a -length noise vector, whereas \mathbf{f}_m and \mathbf{w}_m represent the transmit and receive beamforming vectors in the angular direction θ_m which, for the case of monostatic sensing, read

$$\mathbf{w}_m = \mathbf{f}_m = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_a}} [1, e^{j\phi_m}, \dots, e^{j(N_a-1)\phi_m}]^T, \quad (2.28)$$

where ϕ_m is the phase shift that is related to the beam angle θ_m via the following expression $\phi_m = \pi \sin(\theta_m)$. Furthermore, in (2.27), $\mathbf{H}_{si,k}$ denotes the SI channel matrix of size $N_a \times N_a$ at subcarrier k and \mathbf{H}_k represents the P point target reflection channel, which can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{H}_k = \sum_{p=0}^{P-1} \alpha_p e^{-j2\pi k F_s K^{-1} \tau_p} \mathbf{a}_r(\theta_p, \lambda_k) \mathbf{a}_t^H(\theta_p, \lambda_k) e^{-j2\pi \frac{k p}{K}}. \quad (2.29)$$

In the above expression, $\alpha_p = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_k^2 \sigma_k^p}{(4\pi)^3 d_p^4}}$ denotes the gain factor expressed based on the RADAR equation, with λ_k , σ_k^p , and d_p denoting the wavelength, the radar-cross section (RCS), and the distance of the p -th target, respectively. The variable θ_p represents the azimuth angle associated with the target p , while \mathbf{a}_t and \mathbf{a}_r denote the transmit and receive array response vectors, respectively, which for an ULA with N_a antennas and half-wavelength inter-antenna spacing can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{a}(\theta, \lambda_k) = [1, \dots, e^{j\pi \frac{\lambda_c}{\lambda_k} \sin(\theta)}, \dots, e^{j\pi \frac{\lambda_c}{\lambda_k} (N_a-1) \sin(\theta)}]^T, \quad (2.30)$$

where λ_k and λ_c denote the k -th subcarrier wavelength and the carrier wavelength, respectively. Note that index t/r is omitted for convenience. The variable $l_p = \lfloor \tau_p F_s \rfloor$ refers to the p -th target delay measured in units of the sampling time, with $\tau_p = 2d_p/c_0$ being the true two-way propagation delay and F_s is the sampling frequency. In (2.29), K is the number of subcarriers.

Then, after applying channel-estimation approach using element-wise division, the estimated reflection channel at the k -th subcarrier and the spatial angle θ_m can be expressed as

$$\hat{H}_k^m = \mathbf{w}_m^H \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{f}_m + \mathbf{w}_m^H \mathbf{H}_{si,k} \mathbf{f}_m, \quad (2.31)$$

where the first term represents the reflection channel, the second term is the SI channel, and with the noise term being omitted for simplicity.

The basic idea of SI cancellation is to cancel the second term in (2.31) by optimizing the transmit or receive beamforming vector. Owing to the work in [32], the antenna weights can be optimized for SI attenuation using the NSP method. The method leverages the SI channel knowledge, and, by placing a certain number of frequency zeros in the spectrum of the SI channel, generates the receive beamforming vector according to the following expression [32]

$$\mathbf{w}_m = \frac{\mathbf{Q}_m \mathbf{a}_r(\theta_m, \lambda_c)}{\|\mathbf{Q}_m \mathbf{a}_r(\theta_m, \lambda_c)\|}, \quad (2.32)$$

where $\mathbf{Q}_m = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Z}_m \mathbf{Z}_m^\dagger$ with $\mathbf{Z}_m = [\mathbf{H}_{si,k_1} \mathbf{f}_m, \mathbf{H}_{si,k_2} \mathbf{f}_m, \dots, \mathbf{H}_{si,k_{N_z}} \mathbf{f}_m]$, $\mathbf{a}_r(\theta_m)$ is given in (2.30), and N_z denotes the number of frequency zeros placed at the subcarriers k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{N_z} . These null tones may correspond to subcarrier indices that are evenly distributed across the SI channel spectrum.

2.2.1.3. Preliminary Results

SI channel and cancellation

To obtain the SI channel and extract its amplitude and phase frequency characteristics, we direct to full-wave electromagnetic (EM) simulations. A linear array of 16 rectangular patches (see Fig. 2.17a) with inter-antenna spacing of half wavelength at 60 GHz is created and simulated in HFSS. The first eight antennas represent transmit antenna array, while the remaining eight form the receiving array. From the simulated scattering parameters (S) of the 16-port array, assuming perfect port matching, the SI channel can be expressed as [33]

$$H_{si,ij}(f) = \frac{S_{i(j+8)}}{2} \quad (2.33)$$

$$i = 1, \dots, 8, j = 1, \dots, 8.$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{si}(f)$ models the coupling channel between different antennas of the Tx and Rx arrays and S_{mn} denotes the transmission coefficient between antennas (ports) m and n . The SI channel magnitude for all 64 coupling

Figure 2.17: (a) 8-element Tx and Rx arrays. (b) Magnitude of coupling channels between Tx and Rx antennas.

channels over frequency is depicted in Fig. 2.17. Obviously, the strongest coupling appears between antenna 8 of the transmitting array and antenna 1 of the receiving array and is lower for other Tx-Rx antenna pairs.

Figure 2.18: (a) Example of SI cancellation by placing a single frequency zero. (b) SI channel power gain over beam angle as a function of the number of frequency zeros.

Leveraging the SI channel knowledge, the complex weights of the beamforming vectors can be set using the NSP method to suppress the SI signal, as discussed in the previous section.

An example of SI cancellation is shown in Fig. 2.18a). By placing a single frequency zero in the spectrum of the SI channel, the SI can be significantly attenuated. The impact of the number of frequency zeros on the SI channel attenuation across beam angle is shown in Fig. 2.18b). The frequency zeros are placed equidistantly in the spectrum of the crosstalk channel. It can be noted that the SI suppression is improved as the number of null tones is increased (about 20 dB per frequency zero). The attenuation of approx. 23 dB is achieved using one null tone. By placing 4-5 frequency zeros, attenuation of SI in the order of 80-100 dB is feasible. Furthermore, increasing the number of frequency zeros beyond five does not bring significant improvement.

Sensing performance

The results of sensing performance with and without SI cancellation are analyzed via simulation. We consider a scenario with a mmWave ISAC system performing monostatic sensing of environment, where four targets, with radar cross sections (RCS) of {30, 23, 40, 18} dB, are placed at different 2D positions in space. These are located at {3.4, 5.1, 6.9, 9.7} meters distance from the sensing device, and at the angles of {-36, 15, 0, 20} degrees, respectively.

We consider communication-centric sensing by employing an OFDM waveform and extracting sensing information from channel state information. The 1024-point Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) bandwidth is 2160 MHz. With 828 used subcarriers the effective signal bandwidth is about 1828 MHz. To combat channel effects, a cyclic prefix (CP) of 256 samples is used. For the given OFDM parameters, the range resolution equals 6.94 cm and the maximum sensing range is 17.78 meters. The transmit and receive antenna arrays consist of 8 elements each. The peak gain of the single antenna is set to 5 dBi, as discussed above. The maximum Tx power per element is 15 dBm, while the combined transmit power is 24 dBm. With an array gain of 14 dBi, the effective isotropic radiated power (EIRP) equals 38 dBm. The power back-off of 10 dB assumed.

To model the impact of SI on receiver sensitivity and consequentially sensing performance, a receiver dynamic range of 70 dB is assumed, meaning the RX gain can be varied between -10 and 60 dB. The receiver noise figure (NF) is set to 8 dB (typical value for 60 GHz phased array receivers). With a channel bandwidth of 2 GHz, the receiver noise floor amounts -73 dBm. Furthermore, an analog-to-digital converter (ADC) with a resolution of 12 bits and an effective bit number of 8.5 bits (ENoB) is considered. The full-scale ADC input level is 0 dBm. The automatic gain control (AGC) loop in the receiver's front end automatically adjusts the gain based on the received signal power.

Figure 2.19 compares the results of OFDM-based sensing with and without SI suppression. The left figure shows the sensing performance in the presence of SI. One can visually notice that the echoes are of lower intensity. Moreover, the echo from the fourth object is not visible. The reason is that the dynamic range of the receiver is reduced due to the strong crosstalk between arrays, limiting the receiver gain and masking echo

Figure 2.19: Sensing performance (a) without, and (b) with SI cancellation.

signals. Therefore, signals that are reflected from distant objects or objects with a smaller RCS become faint or almost invisible. The figure on the right presented the sensing performance when using antenna weights that are optimized for SI suppression. When compared to the figure left, it can be noted that the echo responses are of higher intensity. In addition, the echo from the fourth object that was not previously visible is visible now. By suppressing the SI, the dynamic range of the receiver is improved, which leads to improved object detection performance.

2.2.1.4. Conclusion and Future Work

We have analyzed the detection performance of beamforming mmWave OFDM-ISAC systems in the presence of self-interference. Simulation analysis has revealed that strong self-interference can reduce the receiver sensitivity, leading to reduced detection range, masking of reflective targets, and poor sensing performance. By optimizing the beamforming weights, self-interference can be attenuated, and detection performance improved without significantly affecting the beam directivity and shape. Self-interference suppression is leveraging the full knowledge (i.e., amplitude and phase frequency characteristics) about the SI channel. However, in practical phased array systems, finite signal bandwidth is used, which is not sufficient to capture small delays associated with short distances between the elements of the transmitting and receiving antenna arrays. In these cases, all delays fall within one OFDM symbol duration. Addressing this problem will be the focus of future work. Another research direction to follow is the practical implementation and evaluation of SI interference cancellation in beamforming mmWave ISAC systems.

2.2.1.5. Use within MultiX

This work aims to develop SI-free beam codebooks for mmWave ISAC nodes, thereby improving their sensing performance. These can then be implemented in mmWave ISAC devices, which will be used for demonstration purposes in the later phase of PoC2.

2.2.2. OTFS-based Joint communication and sensing for UAV localization

This contribution investigates a joint network communication and sensing framework for a swarm of UAVs operating under high mobility and rich multipath. Communication among UAVs adopts OTFS signaling; furthermore, UAVs communicate with a server at the network edge. The approach leverages the delay–Doppler domain channel estimates inherently produced by OTFS to infer information about the networked agents, i.e., positions and velocities, while avoiding stringent network-wide time synchronization. The key enabler is the definition and systematic use of Relative Echo Delay (RED) profiles, constructed from LoS and NLoS components observed on each communication link, which turns multipath from a nuisance into a source of observability. This makes the method compatible with plesiochronous networks and improves robustness in dynamics where conventional waveforms and estimators are prone to failure.

The rationale for using OTFS is twofold. First, delay–Doppler processing provides a sparse representation of time-varying multipath channels and resolves paths that share the same delay but have distinct Doppler shifts, which improves velocity estimation. Second, the pilots required for reliable communication can be reused for sensing, i.e., the same physical layer artifacts deliver both connectivity and perception without additional hardware, or spectrum and power consumption. In contrast, OFDM receivers, operating primarily in the time–frequency domain, tend to merge such paths, which degrades Doppler discrimination and results in larger velocity errors in fast-time variations.

The information extracted from the OTFS channel estimates is organized around a minimal set of physical relationships. For a propagation path of length d , the echo delay is

$$\tau = \frac{d}{c},$$

where c is the speed of light. For a reflector with radial relative velocity v_{rel} at carrier wavelength λ , the Doppler shift satisfies

$$\nu \approx \frac{v_{\text{rel}}}{\lambda}.$$

The RED for a link is the difference between an NLoS path delay and the corresponding LoS delay,

$$\Delta\tau \triangleq \tau_{\text{NLoS}} - \tau_{\text{LoS}},$$

which eliminates dependence on absolute time bases and reduces synchronization requirements. Joint use of $\Delta\tau$ and ν across links yields range- and velocity-consistent measurements that can be fused across the network.

From a system perspective, the delay–Doppler profiles measured on inter-UAV links are collected at the edge server. Because each NLoS component must be attributed to the UAV that generated the reflection, the problem entails a global path-to-UAV assignment over redundant RED measurements. The solution adopts probabilistic data association using belief propagation to exploit inter-link dependencies, followed by an iterative refinement stage that improves position estimates and subsequently derives velocities from Doppler.

Within the broader research landscape, related work on OTFS-enabled ranging and cooperative positioning has demonstrated advantages over OFDM in high-mobility and NLoS conditions. However, typical approaches rely on absolute time-of-arrival or tightly synchronized time-difference-of-arrival, often discarding multipath. The present contribution differs by exploiting multipath through RED profiles to reduce synchronization requirements, while retaining compatibility with practical bandwidths and pilot structures.

Our solution [34] leverages the information that UAVs send to the edge server and envisions a method through which the edge server can compile a list of REDs and associates each of these values with the ID of the UAV that originated that reflected path. Importantly, REDs and radial velocities satisfy algebraic relations across quadruples of distinct UAVs. In noise-free conditions, suitable alternating sums of REDs over four-node configurations vanish, and analogous linear relations hold for the radial velocities. These equalities couple entries belonging to different links, constraining admissible assignments μ . Under measurement noise, the equalities become approximate, i.e., residuals must remain compatible with the DD resolution and estimation variance. These cross-link relations supply the check constraints used by the association engine.

Given a swarm of N UAVs, including a number of anchor UAVs whose positions and velocities are known, we cast the association problem on a factor graph. Variable nodes represent triple-indexed assignment variables, one per reflector and ordered link, and check nodes enforce the four-node RED and Doppler relations. Messages flow between variable and check nodes to approximate the maximum-a-posteriori association under the noise model. Practical initialization encodes the LoS constraint by fixing the first entry in each list. Complexity scales polynomially in N per Belief Propagation (BProp) iteration, as opposed to the factorial growth of exhaustive association. The BProp output for each link (i, j) is a probability matrix whose maximum-weight non-conflicting selection yields $\hat{\mu}_{i,j}$. Heuristics handle ties caused by quantization, with consistency checks across neighboring links to resolve ambiguities.

Once an estimate $\hat{\mu}$ of the μ assignments is available, the RED/velocity pairs are attributed to specific reflectors, producing, for each reflector k , a set of path-wise constraints over multiple links. These constraints are then consumed by the subsequent estimation stage to recover the position and velocity $(\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{v}_i)$ of all non-anchor UAVs. The estimation and tracking procedures, including iterative refinement and exploitation of reciprocal links, are specified in [34] and follow after the association step.

The formulation assumes: i) single-bounce dominance with UAVs as the only reflectors, ii) sufficient SNR for OTFS Delay Doppler (DD) peak detection on LoS and NLoS components, and iii) swarm kinematics that

keep path separations resolvable on the adopted DD grid. Under these conditions, the UAVs' measurements, together with the cross-link consistency relations, provide observability of positions and velocities up to the usual rigid-body symmetries eliminated by anchors.

Problem statement.

Given: the set of DD profiles $\{\mathcal{D}_{i,j}, \mathcal{V}_{i,j}\}_{i \neq j}$ extracted from OTFS pilots, the anchor states, and the single-bounce model above, determine i) the reflector association maps $\hat{\mu}$ that satisfy the cross-link consistency relations within the error tolerances, and ii) the 3D positions and velocities of all non-anchor UAVs that jointly satisfy the estimations for the associated paths. The output of this stage are the discrete associations and a consistent set of geometric constraints, ready to be ingested by the subsequent estimation and tracking modules.

The solution we propose for the estimation stage after association is as follows. Given: i) the RED and Doppler entries extracted from the OTFS DD profiles, ordered per reflector by the estimated maps $\hat{\mu}$, and ii) the set of anchor nodes, the task is to recover the 3D positions and velocities of the non-anchor UAVs in a single global frame.

The solutions consists of the following steps.

Position estimation via RED fitting.

Positions are obtained by minimizing the mismatch between measured REDs and the REDs implied by a tentative configuration $\mathbf{t} = [t_{1,x}, t_{1,y}, t_{1,z}, \dots, t_{N,x}, t_{N,y}, t_{N,z}]^\top$, with anchors kept fixed. The estimate solves

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{t}} \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{t}), \quad (2.34)$$

where the objective is the global sum of squared RED residuals

$$\mathcal{E}(\mathbf{t}) \triangleq \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^N \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq i,j}}^N (\tilde{\delta}_{i,j,k} - \theta_{i,j,k}(\mathbf{t}))^2. \quad (2.35)$$

Here $\tilde{\delta}_{i,j,k}$ is the measured RED for link (i, j) attributed to reflector k by $\hat{\mu}$, and $\theta_{i,j,k}(\mathbf{t})$ is the RED implied by \mathbf{t} ,

$$\theta_{i,j,k}(\mathbf{t}) = \|\mathbf{t}_j - \mathbf{t}_k\| + \|\mathbf{t}_k - \mathbf{t}_i\| - \|\mathbf{t}_i - \mathbf{t}_j\|. \quad (2.36)$$

The minimization in (2.34) is carried out with gradient descent using analytical gradients of (2.35). Anchors remain fixed throughout the iterations. Initialization uses either prior positions in tracking mode or random draws. The stopping rule enforces a relative decrease of \mathcal{E} or a maximum iteration cap.

Because $\mathcal{E}(\mathbf{t})$ is non-convex, a restart test is applied. Under correct associations and perfect convergence, the residual energy is dominated by delay quantization on the OTFS grid. Modeling the RED error as i.i.d. uniform with variance $\sigma_\eta^2 = c^2/(12B^2)$ yields the bound $E_b = N(N-1)(N-2)\sigma_\eta^2$. After each run of (2.34), if $\mathcal{E}(\hat{\mathbf{p}})$ exceeds the threshold $\tilde{E}_b = \beta E_b$ (with $\beta > 1$), the solver is restarted from a new cold-start guess. The process repeats up to a retry budget. This heuristic rejects local minima that are inconsistent with the OTFS resolution.

Velocity estimation from Doppler.

With $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ available, velocities are estimated from Doppler by solving, for each reflector k , a linear least-squares problem that stacks all links where k appears as a reflector. After removing known terms due to the transmit and receive nodes on each link, the corrected Doppler vector satisfies

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}} = (\hat{\mathbf{U}}\hat{\mathbf{U}}^\top)^{-1}\hat{\mathbf{U}}\hat{\omega}^*, \quad (2.37)$$

where each row of $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ is built from unit vectors along the segments (k, i) and (j, k) evaluated at $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$, i.e., $\mathbf{u}_{k,i}(\hat{\mathbf{p}})$ and $\mathbf{u}_{j,k}(\hat{\mathbf{p}})$, for the corresponding directed link (i, j) . This decouples the recovery of \mathbf{v}_k across nodes and enforces consistency with the measured radial velocities.

2.2.2.1. Use within MultiX

Our contribution aligns with MultiX's objectives on integrated sensing and communication in 6G RANs. By extracting situational awareness from communication pilots and fusing it at the edge, the proposed method supports a perceptive RAN that is multi-static and multi-technology aware, without imposing additional sensing overheads.

2.2.3. Joint waveform design for ISAC

Existing 5G NR waveforms i.e., OFDM and DFT-S-OFDM are designed for communications only. In tightly coupled signal-based integration, the waveform can be designed for both sensing and communications. In general, ISAC waveform candidates can be categorized as sensing-centric waveforms, communication-centric waveforms, and jointly optimized waveforms.

2.2.3.1. Sensing-Centric Waveform

Sensing-centric waveforms have been extensively studied in radar community. The classical sensing waveforms generally contain no signaling information but extract potential information or parameters from the echoes reflected by different targets. In the following, we will describe three basic types of sensing waveforms: frequency-modulated continuous waveform (FMCW) [35], phase-modulated continuous waveform (PMCW) [36], and phase-coded frequency modulated continuous waveform (PC-FMCW) [37].

An FMCW radar transmits a signal called a "chirp", which is a sinusoid whose frequency increases linearly with time. One FMCW pulse can be expressed as

$$X_{FMCW} = e^{-j(2\pi f_c t + \pi k t^2)}, \quad t \in [0, T] \quad (2.38)$$

where f_c is the carrier frequency, B is the bandwidth, T is the pulse duration, k is the frequency sweep slope and $k = B/T$.

For monostatic FMCW based sensing, a series of FMCW chirps is fed to the Tx antenna and mixer at the receiver. After mixing the transmitted signals and the received signals reflected from the target, the beat signal is generated, which has a frequency proportional to the delay corresponding to the distance between the radar and the target. The beat signal is passed through a low pass filter and ADC for further signal processing implementation, e.g., target detection or sensing parameter estimation. The major attractive feature of FMCW is its simplified hardware components and low-cost receiver. This is thanks to the required low sampling-rate ADC, the cheap power amplifier, and the low PAPR of FMCW.

In PMCW, the transmission carrier is modulated using a code sequence, e.g.,

$$X_{PMCW} = s(t)e^{-j2\pi f_c t}, \quad t \in [0, T] \quad (2.39)$$

where

$$s(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}} \sum_{m=1}^M s_m \prod \left[\frac{t - (m-1)t_b}{t_b} \right] \quad (2.40)$$

$s_m = e^{j\phi_m}$ and the set of M phases $\{\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_M\}$ is the phase code associated with $s(t)$. There can be different sequence options for s_m , e.g., BPSK, chirp-like sequence, Golay, etc. The selection of s_m is crucial for the sensing performance of PMCW.

The receiver side processing of PMCW based sensing includes conversion to baseband, ADC, matched-filter and FFT processing for range and doppler estimation. Depending on the code rate, the required ADC sampling rate can be high.

Compared to FMCW sensing signals, PMCW signals show good properties in terms of interference mitigation. However, due to the high instantaneous bandwidth, digitally modulated waveforms in PMCW sensing signals raise high sampling rate in ADC, which increases the cost of implementation. To leverage the benefits of both FMCW and PMCW, PC-FMCW has been proposed, which applying phase coding to FMCW signals. PC-FMCW can be expressed as

$$X_{PC-FMCW} = s(t)e^{-j(2\pi f_c t + \pi k t^2)}, \quad t \in [0, T], \quad (2.41)$$

where k is the frequency sweep slope and $k = B/T$,

Figure 2.20: TDM between sensing and communication signals using PMCW

Figure 2.21: Frequency-domain OFDM sensing

$$s(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{T}} \sum_{m=1}^M s_m \Pi \left[\frac{t - (m-1)t_b}{t_b} \right] \quad (2.42)$$

is the transmitter phase code signal with code bandwidth B_c and chip duration t_b . Similarly with PMCW, $s_m = e^{j\phi_m}$ and the set of M phases $\{\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_M\}$ is the phase code associated with $s(t)$.

The receiver side processing is similar with FMCW, except that after ADC, the phase code signal (i.e., $s(t)$) needs to be removed first before the legacy FMCW FFT processing for range and doppler estimation.

In terms of joint communication and sensing, the design aspect of sensing-centric waveforms is how to convey information bits using the sensing-centric waveforms.

To carry information bits over FMCW, the PC-FMCW can be applied as was presented above in the equation for PC-FMCW, in that $s(t)$ modulates phase changes inside a chirp to carry information bits.

To convey information bits using PMCW, a typical way is the time-domain multiplexing, as illustrated in Fig. 2.20. More specifically, there are M repetitions of a selected sequence. There is TDM between sensing signals (X_s) and joint sensing and communication signal (X_{sc}), where one modulation symbol is carried per X_{sc} (Fig. 2.20). Although the sensing-centric waveforms can indeed be applied to convey information bits, the supported data rate is in general very low.

2.2.3.2. Communication-Centric Waveform

OFDM has been the dominating waveform for wireless communication systems, given its robustness against multipath fading and simple receiver design, as well as its capability to support high data rates. In fact, OFDM can be applied to sensing as well, where the key design aspect is how to enable sensing functionality using OFDM waveform.

In general, there can be time-domain OFDM sensing and frequency-domain OFDM sensing. For the time-domain method, the classic time-domain correlation-based processing is applied. It, however, has limited performance (due to the imperfect autocorrelation property of the OFDM baseband signal) and high complexity. On the other hand, frequency-domain OFDM sensing has become popular recently, where the operations are in the 'modulation symbol' domain and thus independent of the correlation property of the baseband signal [38]. Frequency-domain OFDM sensing can be performed through 2D-FFT processing and can be based on RS only or both RS and data, as illustrated in Fig. 2.21. For RS-only methods, they can work for both monostatic and bistatic sensing, which, however, have less processing gain, while for the methods jointly utilizing data and RS, they can have higher processing gain but are most suitable for monostatic sensing.

As a matter of fact, it can be shown that with appropriate parameterization, OFDM can achieve the same/similar sensing performance as sensing-centric waveforms in terms of delay and Doppler estimation. Fig. 2.22 illustrates the system parameters, and Tab. 2.3 provides the qualitative comparison. In Tab. 2.3, f_{ADC} denotes

Figure 2.22: System parameters

the ADC sampling rate of the FMCW-based sensing receiver, f_c indicates the carrier frequency, and c is the speed of light.

Table 2.3: Waveform comparison in terms of sensing performance

	FMCW / CP-FMCW	PMCW	OFDM
Max. Unambiguous range	$\frac{f_{ADC} T_c}{2B}$	$\frac{T_{PRI} c}{2}$	$\frac{c}{2\Delta f}$
Range resolution	$\frac{c}{2B}$	$\frac{c}{2B}$	$\frac{c}{2B}$
Max. unambiguous velocity	$\frac{c}{4f_c T_{PRI}}$	$\frac{c}{4f_c T_{PRI}}$	$\frac{c}{4f_c T_{PRI}}$
Velocity resolution	$\frac{c}{2f_c T_{PRI} N}$	$\frac{c}{2f_c T_{PRI} N}$	$\frac{c}{2f_c T_{PRI} N}$

Note that the maximum unambiguous range of OFDM sensing also depends on the CP length. If the round-trip delay is longer than the CP length, there is ISI for sensing signals. Nevertheless, the ISI will not entirely prevent it from functioning as long as it is lower than a certain threshold.

The high-level ISAC performance comparison between sensing-centric and communication-centric the waveforms is given in Tab. 2.4.

2.2.3.3. Jointly Optimized Waveform

In addition to sensing-centric and communication-centric waveforms discussed above, there are also other more advanced waveforms which can be considered to jointly improve both sensing and communication, e.g., OTFS [39], Orthogonal Chirp-Division Multiplexing (OCDM) [40] and Affine Frequency- Division Multiplexing (AFDM) [41].

2.2.3.4. Use within MultiX

This section provides a fundamental understanding of waveform design in the MPS, directly demonstrating the performance limits for various sensing metrics, including range and velocity resolution and ambiguity.

2.2.4. Waveform Processing for Enhanced Sensing Performance

2.2.4.1. Limitations of OFDM Waveforms for Sensing

New Radio (NR) waveform design primarily adopts cyclic prefix OFDM for both downlink and uplink, with discrete Fourier transform spread OFDM (DFT-s-OFDM) additionally supported in uplink under coverage-limited

Table 2.4: Qualitative comparison of ISAC waveform characteristics

	FMCW / CP-FMCW	PMCW	OFDM
Sensing accuracy	+	+	+
peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) (or sensing range)	+	+	-
Comm. data rate	-	-	++
Cost	++	+	~

conditions. The use of Cyclic-Prefix (CP)-OFDM with flexible numerologies preserves backward compatibility while enabling improved performance in terms of data rate, reliability, error resilience, and time–frequency resource allocation. In contrast, waveform requirements for sensing—encompassing target detection, target tracking, environmental monitoring, and scene reconstruction—are governed by different metrics, notably sensing accuracy, range resolution, and velocity resolution.

OFDM modulates data in the frequency domain and transmits it in the time domain via the IDFT. A cyclic prefix mitigates inter-symbol interference from multipath fading channels. While OFDM offers high spectral efficiency and flexibility, which make it effective for communications, its sensing performance is mixed. Specifically, OFDM provides fine range resolution and strong frequency diversity, but exhibits limited velocity resolution and range ambiguity. Furthermore, it suffers from a high peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) and is sensitive to phase noise and frequency offsets, particularly under high-mobility conditions. Thus, waveform suitability for sensing is best assessed using a comprehensive set of metrics, including range and velocity resolution, unambiguous range, PAPR, and other task-specific performance indicators.

In contrast to communications, which is fundamentally a data transmission and decoding process, sensing is formulated as an estimation and detection problem, where the objective is to extract environmental information rather than user data. The received signals, reflected from one or multiple targets, are processed to infer key parameters such as time delay, range resolution, and velocity. These parameters serve as the foundation for higher-level sensing tasks, including localization, tracking, and environmental reconstruction. In Tab. 2.3, we introduce a simple comparison between communication centric waveforms (e.g., OFDM) and sensing centric waveforms (e.g., FMCW and Phase Modulated Continuous Wave (PMCW)), showing the advantages/disadvantages of employing each waveform.

A central challenge in employing OFDM for sensing stems from its inherent design rigidity. Specifically, the selection of subcarrier spacing establishes a direct trade-off between time and frequency resolution, which in turn constrains range and velocity estimation accuracy. For example, finer subcarrier spacing improves range resolution but simultaneously increases symbol duration, thereby limiting the system’s capacity to resolve high Doppler shifts. Conversely, larger subcarrier spacing enhances velocity resolution but degrades range precision. This coupling between design parameters and sensing performance introduces fundamental limitations for applications requiring simultaneous optimization across multiple sensing dimensions.

To address these constraints, advanced signal processing techniques have been proposed to enhance the sensing capability of OFDM waveforms. Transform-domain methods, such as wavelet transforms or time–frequency representations, enable the selective emphasis of specific dimensions (e.g., time versus frequency), thereby improving estimation accuracy for the parameter of interest. Similarly, adaptive filtering, sparse recovery techniques, and parametric estimation frameworks have been explored to mitigate resolution trade-offs and to exploit additional diversity in the received signal.

Despite these advances, there is currently no unified framework for systematically tuning OFDM waveform parameters to meet sensing requirements. Existing approaches often address isolated aspects of the problem, such as improving range resolution or Doppler estimation, without offering a holistic methodology that accounts for the diverse metrics relevant to sensing. Developing such a framework remains an open research challenge, with implications for the integration of ISAC in next-generation wireless systems.

2.2.4.2. Enhanced OFDM Processing for ISAC

To overcome the structural limitations of conventional OFDM, we propose a framework that enables alternative waveform configurations for UE within an ISAC system. Unlike conventional designs that exclusively rely on the Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT)/Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) pair, the proposed approach introduces configurable transformations that extend the design space of OFDM-based waveforms. Specifically, each

UE may be provisioned with a set of transformation options—such as wavelet transforms, Walsh–Hadamard transforms (WHT), or Hilbert–Huang transforms (HHT). These transformations provide unique advantages, such as improved time–frequency localization, enhanced resolution, or robustness to non-stationary signal components, thereby offering new performance trade-offs tailored to sensing tasks. The enhanced waveform processing can be realized through two complementary modes of operation:

1. Transformation Substitution. In this mode, the conventional IFFT/FFT stage is entirely replaced with an alternative transformation kernel. For example, wavelet-based modulation allows multi-resolution analysis, enabling simultaneous fine-grained time localization and coarse frequency resolution. Similarly, WHT provides low-complexity orthogonal decomposition suitable for fast implementations, while HHT is advantageous for adaptively analyzing nonlinear or non-stationary signals. Substitution fundamentally alters the modulation domain, allowing the system to exploit resolution properties not achievable with FFT-based OFDM.

2. Hybrid Transformation with OFDM. Alternatively, transformations may be integrated into the OFDM pipeline while preserving the conventional IFFT/FFT backbone. This hybrid approach offers flexible enhancement of specific signal characteristics:

- Frequency-domain processing: Transformations can be applied selectively to subsets of subcarriers prior to the IFFT stage. For example, wavelet processing may be introduced to a set of subcarriers, where for specific time–frequency resources the wavelet transformation may be incorporated, as expressed in the following equation:

$$x(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{k=0}^{N_f-1} s(k, m) e^{j2\pi f_k t} a_{k,m} \Psi_{k,m}(t) \quad (2.43)$$

This selective design enables improved resolution of narrowband reflections without modifying the entire waveform.

- Time-domain processing: Transformations may also be applied to specific time intervals of the OFDM signal, such as designated symbols or symbol segments, thereby enabling targeted enhancement of temporal features.

Figure 2.23: RMSE of range estimation for multiple system that employ waveform processing

In both modes, the applied transformation is mapped to a defined set of time–frequency resources. For interoperability, the exact allocation—specifying which OFDM symbols and subcarriers are subject to transformation—must be communicated to the UE. Figure 2.23 illustrates this mapping, where the transformation mask defines the time–frequency locations for enhanced processing. Moreover, given a target located at a range R_r from the receiver, the RMSE of the range estimation can be derived as:

$$\text{RMSE}(R_r) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{i=1}^{N_t} (\widehat{R}_r[i] - R_r)^2} \quad (2.44)$$

where, $\widehat{R}_r[i]$ represents the estimated range value that corresponds to frequencytime symbol i . This equation quantifies the performance gain achievable through the proposed transformation-aided design. Ensuring that this configuration is known to both transmitter and receiver is essential for coherent interpretation of the waveform.

The proposed enhancement expands the waveform design space for ISAC systems by allowing adaptive, task-oriented configuration. For example, wavelet-based processing may be selected for high-resolution sensing in cluttered environments, while WHT may be applied in scenarios requiring fast processing with low complexity. Such configurability not only addresses the rigid trade-offs of traditional OFDM but also establishes a pathway toward a dynamic ISAC framework where waveform properties are tuned in real time to balance communication reliability with sensing accuracy.

2.2.4.3. Waveform De-Processing at the Receiver

Figure 2.24: Waveform processing based on wavelet is introduced to an OFDM-based signal as (a) wavelet transformation is introduced to replace the OFDM waveform, (b) wavelet transformation is introduced before OFDM, and (c) wavelet transformation is introduced after OFDM modulation.

In existing communication systems, the transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) operate under the assumption of a fixed, standardized waveform—typically OFDM—such that both ends inherently agree on the modulation and processing structure. In contrast, the proposed framework introduces a paradigm shift: the Rx must explicitly acquire information about the waveform processing techniques applied at the Tx in order to correctly decode the received data and exploit the enhanced sensing features. This additional signaling ensures synchronization between Tx and Rx when alternative transformations, beyond the conventional IFFT/FFT, are employed. At the receiver, the UE utilizes the waveform processing information provided in the configuration to perform de-processing, i.e., the inverse operation of the transformation applied at the transmitter. To enable this, the UE extracts from the configuration at least one of the following elements:

- Waveform processing metadata, including the time window, bandwidth, and subcarrier indices over which the transformation was applied.
- Processing domain information, specifying whether the transformation was executed in the frequency or time domain, as exemplified in Figure 2.24.
- Transformation parameters, such as the chosen wavelet function, scaling factors, or decomposition levels, which are required to apply the inverse operation accurately.

By applying de-processing, the UE can reconstruct the original signal structure while maintaining the sensing gains introduced at the Tx. As shown in Figure 2.23, introducing wavelet transformations leads to a marked improvement in the root mean square error (RMSE) of range estimation compared with conventional CP-OFDM signals. The performance of the sensing system is further influenced by the specific configuration of the wavelet transform. For instance, Daubechies wavelets provide compact support and good frequency localization, the Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT) offers fine resolution for non-stationary signals, while the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) ensures efficient multi-resolution decomposition. Selecting the appropriate wavelet configuration thus becomes a key design parameter, enabling optimization of sensing accuracy and robustness across diverse deployment scenarios within ISAC systems. In addition to applying network-provided configurations, the UE may also proactively suggest waveform processing strategies to the network based on its own sensing measurements. Such recommendations can be incorporated into the uplink signaling exchange—either through dedicated bits in the Uplink Control Information (UCI) field, indices referencing pre-defined lookup tables, or implicitly via the selection of specific uplink resources. For instance, the UE may request the introduction of a particular waveform processing method, such as a wavelet transform, when a target sensing accuracy is associated with specific time–frequency resolution requirements. Similarly, the UE may recommend a specific wavelet family and scaling factor, or indicate the bandwidth and time window over which waveform processing is required to achieve certain sensing Key Performance Indicator (KPI). This feedback mechanism establishes a closed-loop interaction between the UE and the network, enabling the dynamic adaptation of waveform design to real-time sensing conditions within ISAC frameworks.

2.2.4.4. Conclusion

This work has proposed a transformation-aided enhancement to conventional OFDM, designed to overcome the structural rigidity that limits its applicability to sensing within ISAC frameworks. By introducing configurable waveform processing techniques—such as wavelet, Walsh–Hadamard, or Hilbert–Huang transforms—our approach enables flexible adaptation of the waveform at the UE level. The ability to apply transformations in either the frequency or time domain, and to dynamically configure them based on time–frequency resources, creates a significantly larger design space than traditional CP-OFDM. Furthermore, the possibility for the UE to provide feedback and recommend waveform configurations based on local measurements establishes a closed-loop system, where sensing accuracy and communication reliability can be jointly optimized in real time. Compared with alternative approaches that advocate a complete replacement of OFDM with entirely new waveforms, the proposed method is inherently more practical. A full waveform redesign requires fundamental changes to transceiver architecture, hardware implementations, and standardization processes, which significantly increase cost and deployment complexity. In contrast, our framework builds upon the existing OFDM structure, introducing targeted enhancements through configurable transformations. This approach minimizes disruption to established systems while still unlocking substantial performance improvements for sensing tasks.

The implications of this design philosophy for future 6G standards are substantial. By decoupling sensing performance from the rigid subcarrier spacing and symbol duration constraints of OFDM, the proposed framework enables high-resolution range and velocity estimation while maintaining backward compatibility with existing NR-based designs. This flexibility will be critical in supporting the diverse requirements of next-generation sensing tasks, including multi-target detection, fine-grained tracking, environmental monitoring, and scene reconstruction. Moreover, the introduction of configurable and UE-driven waveform processing aligns naturally with the broader 6G vision of adaptive, AI-assisted, and service-oriented networks.

Looking ahead, the ability to dynamically tune waveform transformations and to integrate this configurability into standardized signaling protocols could serve as a cornerstone of 6G ISAC systems. Such a capability not only enhances the performance of individual sensing tasks but also enables the simultaneous support of multiple tasks and targets, thereby moving beyond the limitations of communication-centric waveform design.

Ultimately, this technology has the potential to transform 6G into a truly unified platform where communication and sensing co-exist as first-class services, driving new applications across intelligent transportation, autonomous systems, industrial automation, and beyond.

2.3. Multi-band processing

Spectrum diversity has been an increasing trend in 6G systems, in which 5G FR1 and FR2 will be continuously used, and new bands like upper mid-band (FR3) will be explored and potentially considered. In this way, multiple available bandwidths provide an opportunity for high-precision sensing, which requires much effort in the processing algorithms and their implementation. This subtask will then address the challenges in 1) the phase coherence in FR3, 2) OFDM-based multi-band processing, as well as 3) the multi-band measurement system. The multi-band fundamentals and testbed development pave the way for the MultiX PoC validation.

2.3.1. Coherent multi-band target ranging in FR3

The use of disaggregated spectrum in coherent multi-band processing introduces *grating lobes* in the range profile obtained by aggregating multiple bands. This is because uniform sampling in the frequency domain, i.e., without gaps, is a necessary condition to obtain an impulse-like range profile for sensing targets. This significantly degrades the sensing results, introducing ambiguity in the targets' detection and nullifying the multi-band resolution gain.

In this section, we evaluate the multi-target resolution capabilities of multi-band processing with non-contiguous subbands. This problem is introduced in Section 2.1.1 and discussed here in detail.

2.3.1.1. Challenges and contribution

For the above reasons, an important challenge is to analyse and devise *countermeasures for the grating lobes* due to non-contiguous bands, which are still in their early stages, and no results are available for FR3 considered allocations yet. In this activity, which is associated with our paper [9], we propose a heuristic algorithm, named Subsets Product Backprojection (SPBP), for coherent multi-band combination that mitigates the grating lobes due to the use of non-contiguous subbands and outperforms existing approaches like BP and OMP on our data.

2.3.1.2. Use within MultiX

The multi-band combination results presented in this section serve as a guideline for developing coherent multi-band sensing algorithms in MultiX, especially when considering FR3. These are essential for the development of m-SePF01, pointing a new research direction in non-linear combination of range profiles obtained with different sets of subbands to mitigate the impact of non-contiguous bandwidth allocation.

2.3.1.3. Coherent multi-band combination algorithms

We consider two multi-band ISAC algorithms from the literature, BP and OMP, and propose a third one, called SPBP, to mitigate the impact of grating lobes due to non-contiguous subbands. The algorithms are listed in the following, and SPBP is explained in more detail in Section 2.3.1.4.

- **BP**: This method is commonly used in the SAR literature and has been used in ISAC in [11, 13]. It combines the subbands by oversampling the CIR of each subband, compensating for the propagation phase term of each CIR, and summing the CIRs coherently. Grating lobes due to non-contiguous subbands affect the result since no mitigation is performed.
- **OMP**: This algorithm is based on Compressed Sensing (CS) [42] and it was previously used in multi-band sensing in [6]. It tackles the combination of the subbands as a sparse reconstruction problem. It is well-suited to mitigate the grating lobes due to non-contiguous subbands. However, the nominal multi-target resolution of OMP is hard to estimate and certainly lower than that of BP. Moreover, OMP is an *on-grid* method, meaning its performance heavily depends on the granularity of a pre-defined grid of possible range values.

- **SPBP**: This method is based on BP but attempts to mitigate the grating lobes by using non-linear processing on the multi-band range profile (see Section 2.3.1.4). Specifically, SPBP splits the available subbands into two sets, optimized to have grating lobes at different locations, then applies BP to each of them and takes the product of the resulting combined CIRs. As a result, grating lobes are strongly attenuated by the product while the targets persist.

2.3.1.4. Subsets Product BP algorithm

Consider the output range profile of the BP algorithm, which can be expressed as follows (neglecting noise terms).

$$\eta(R) = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \eta_k(R) = \sum_{\ell=0}^L \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \rho_{\ell,k} e^{j\theta_{\ell,k}} \chi_k(R - R_{\ell}) e^{j\frac{4\pi f_k}{c}(R - R_{\ell})}, \quad (2.45)$$

where $\chi_k(R) = \text{sinc}(2B_k R/c)$ is called Range Ambiguity Function (RAF) if the single subband k and represents the single band response to a point target. Under the assumption that the scattering centers are isotropic, the total RAF of the multi-band combination using the subbands of widths collected in set $\mathcal{B} = \{B_k\}_{k=0}^{K-1}$ with carriers $\mathcal{F} = \{f_k\}_{k=0}^{K-1}$, is given by

$$\Psi_{\mathcal{F},\mathcal{B}}(R) = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \chi_k(R) e^{j\frac{4\pi f_k}{c}R}. \quad (2.46)$$

If the subbands are non-contiguous, the combined RAF in the above equation is affected by *grating lobes*. We design a heuristic modification of the BP algorithm to mitigate the impact of grating lobes in the RAF, called SPBP. The key idea is that different sets of subbands will produce grating lobes at different locations, since the portions of the spectrum occupied by the subbands are different. Conversely, targets will appear at the same ranges regardless of the subbands' location in the frequency domain. We exploit this property to cancel out grating lobes by taking the *product* of the magnitude of range profiles obtained using different sets of subbands. Consider two different subsets of the set of indices of the available subbands $\mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, K-1\}$, termed \mathcal{K}_0 and \mathcal{K}_1 , respectively, and denote by $\Psi_{\mathcal{X}}(R)$ the multi-band RAF obtained by combining the subbands whose indices are in set \mathcal{X} . We select \mathcal{K}_0 in such a way that the corresponding subbands have the same total bandwidth as the original set of subbands, to ensure the nominal resolution is the same. This is done by including in \mathcal{K}_0 the first and last indices of the subbands, namely 0 and $K-1$. The remaining elements of \mathcal{K}_0 are selected randomly from \mathcal{K} , keeping a cardinality equal to $|\mathcal{K}_0| = K-1$. This is done to include the maximum number of possible subbands, thus reducing the gaps in the frequency domain, without taking $\mathcal{K}_0 = \mathcal{K}$.

Once \mathcal{K}_0 is selected, we numerically compute the corresponding RAF $\Psi_{\mathcal{K}_0}(R)$ as

$$\Psi_{\mathcal{K}_0}(R) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_0} \chi_k(R) e^{j\frac{4\pi f_k}{c}R}. \quad (2.47)$$

Then we construct all the possible subsets of \mathcal{K} , which are collected in the product set $\Pi(\mathcal{K})$. SPBP searches for the set $\mathcal{K}_1 \in \Pi(\mathcal{K}) \setminus \mathcal{K} \setminus \mathcal{K}_0$ that has a RAF whose product with $|\Psi_{\mathcal{K}_0}(R)|$ (in magnitude) leads to the minimum Peak-to-Sidelobe Ratio (PSLR) [13]. The PSLR evaluates the ratio between the peak of the RAF and the maximum magnitude of its sidelobes, intended as the set of peaks outside of the main lobe.

The RAF product of the two subsets is

$$\Gamma_{\mathcal{K}_0,\mathcal{K}_1}(R) = |\Psi_{\mathcal{K}_0}(R)\Psi_{\mathcal{K}_1}(R)|, \quad (2.48)$$

and the minimization of the PSLR can then be written as

$$\mathcal{K}_1 = \min_{\mathcal{K}' \in \Pi(\mathcal{K}) \setminus \mathcal{K} \setminus \mathcal{K}_0} \left(\frac{|\Gamma_{\mathcal{K}_0,\mathcal{K}'}(0)|}{\max_{R \in [-R_{\max}, R_{\max}] \setminus \Omega} |\Gamma_{\mathcal{K}_0,\mathcal{K}'}(R)|} \right), \quad (2.49)$$

where R_{\max} is the maximum range of interest and Ω is the main lobe region of the RAF. Eq. (2.49) is solved by exhaustive search since $|\mathcal{K}|$ is small in practice due to the non-ideal coherence of the target, which limits the number of subbands that can be combined. Further conditions can be imposed on the candidate sets considered in the search to speed it up, e.g., restricting to subsets with at least a certain number of elements or that have at least a certain spectral coverage.

The final magnitude of the range profile obtained with SPBP is

$$|\eta_{\text{SPBP}}(R)| = \left| \left(\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_0} \eta_k(R) \right) \left(\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_1} \eta_k(R) \right) \right|. \quad (2.50)$$

One drawback of SPBP is that the product in Eq. (2.50), besides strongly attenuating sidelobes, also relatively attenuates weak scatterers with respect to stronger ones. Therefore, if some targets are significantly weaker than others, they may be canceled out and become undetectable. In our results, this phenomenon was not significant, as shown in Section 2.3.1.5, but further research is needed to mitigate this problem.

2.3.1.5. Coherent combination of non-contiguous subbands

We present experimental results using spectrum portions being considered for FR3 frequency allocations by 3GPP [4, 43], discussed at the World Radio Congress in 2023. Specifically, we consider the spectrum portions 7.125 – 10.5 GHz, 12.7 – 13.25 GHz, and 14.8 – 17.35 GHz, divided into 5 subbands determined by the frequency intervals $S_1 = [7.125, 8.5]$ GHz, $S_2 = [8.5, 10.5]$ GHz, $S_3 = [12.7, 13.25]$ GHz, $S_4 = [14.8, 15.35]$ GHz, and $S_5 = [15.35, 17.3]$ GHz. Our measurement system collects CFR measurements with 0.5 or 1 GHz bandwidth granularity, depending on whether we consider object targets (corner reflector or metal plate) or human targets, respectively. Therefore, in the following experiments, we approximate the 3GPP intervals with sets of subbands collected by our system that include them, but do not match exactly the 3GPP bands. We verified that this approximation does not significantly change the resulting target response.

Figure 2.25: 3GPP FR3 considered frequencies (top) and our considered subbands in case of human targets (bottom).

In Fig. 2.26, we show the average number of targets and OSPA over 100 tests obtained using two targets: a corner reflector and a metal plate. Targets are located around 1.2 m from the measurement device and spaced by $d_{\text{trg}} = 0.2$ m. The ground truth target locations are obtained with a laser telemeter. Since these measurements contain a systematic bias with respect to the exacted reflection points of the radio signal on the target, we align the final obtained range profiles to the ground truth with a rigid translation along the range dimension.

We use different combinations of the 5 subbands S_k , with $k = 1, \dots, 5$, and a cardinality penalty $\mu = d_{\text{trg}}$, so that in the OSPA errors larger than the distance between the two targets are penalized as a missed detection. OMP only detects one target in most of the tests. For this reason, it achieves the worst OSPA performance, as it is almost always penalized due to outputting the wrong cardinality for the set of targets. The unsatisfactory performance of OMP is due to the fact that even a slight incoherence among the subbands introduces a model error in the OMP formulation, which assumes perfect coherence. This results in unpredictable effects in the OMP reconstruction and in a loss of resolution.

When using contiguous sets of subbands, i.e., S_1 and S_2 or S_4 and S_5 , only S_1 , SPBP is not used since the grating lobes due to non-contiguous subbands are not present. Hence, in these cases, SPBP is represented with the same performance as BP.

BP works well with contiguous subbands, obtaining an accurate estimate of the number of targets and 5 cm OSPA with $S_1 \cup S_2$, and 7.5 cm OSPA with $S_4 \cup S_5$. This shows that the multi-band range profile correctly reconstructs the number and locations of the two targets.

Conversely, BP has degraded performance when non-contiguous subbands are used. Using $S_1 \cup S_2 \cup S_3$ and $S_3 \cup S_4 \cup S_5$ BP detects on average 3.15 ± 0.57 and 3.18 ± 0.90 targets, respectively, showing that even a smaller frequency gap can lead to the wrong estimation of the number of targets. The resulting OSPA reflects this, increasing with respect to the contiguous case to 7.15 ± 2.1 cm and 9.33 ± 2.3 cm, respectively. SPBP instead estimates on average 2.20 ± 0.40 and 2.34 ± 0.53 targets with $S_1 \cup S_2 \cup S_3$ and $S_3 \cup S_4 \cup S_5$, respectively, which well approximate the real number. The resulting OSPA outperforms that of BP

Using all subbands S_1, \dots, S_5 introduces strong grating lobes, caused by the non-contiguity of the subbands, degrading the performance of all methods. In this case, BP detects on average 9.19 ± 0.87 targets, with an OSPA of over 15 cm. SPBP only provides a slight gain but is also not able to estimate the correct number or targets, detecting 8.62 ± 1.17 targets on average.

Figure 2.26: Average number of targets (left) and OSPA (right) obtained by BP, OMP, and the proposed SPBP on corner reflector and metal plate targets. The black whiskers represent one standard deviation. SPBP outperforms the other two algorithms by better reconstructing the correct number of targets and obtaining the lowest OSPA. When using the full set of subbands S_1, \dots, S_5 , none of the algorithms can correctly detect the two objects.

In Fig. 2.27, we show the mean number of targets and OSPA over 25 tests obtained using two human targets. The two subjects are located approximately 1 m from the measurement device and spaced by 30 cm. Since human targets exhibit degraded coherence over very wide combined bandwidth, as shown in Section 2.1.1.7, we consider narrower frequency ranges as shown in the bottom plot in Fig. 2.25.

Cases 1 and 4 represent contiguous 4 GHz bandwidth allocations, which, according to Fig. 2.4, give a target coherence of above 0.75. From this, we expect humans to cause a single dominant peak in the multi-band range profile, which would not be the case for a wider bandwidth combination. The remaining cases are non-contiguous bandwidth allocations obtained by removing 1 GHz bandwidth chunks, at different locations, from cases 1 and 4.

Fig. 2.27 shows that BP overestimates the number of targets in all cases, with an average of 3.75 ± 0.31 across all cases. Conversely, OMP has the same problem observed with the corner reflector and metal plate, i.e., it can not resolve the two targets in most cases. Notably, since the subjects are more spaced apart than in the corner reflector and metal plate case, OMP performs slightly better. SPBP obtains a more accurate estimation of the real number of targets, with an average of 2.46 ± 0.68 detected targets over all cases.

Fig. 2.27 confirms that SPBP outperforms both BP and OMP on our measurements. Averaging over all tests, SPBP has an OSPA of 12.25 ± 1.54 cm, compared to the 15.45 ± 1.19 and 16.01 ± 1.34 cm of BP and OMP, respectively. Fig. 2.27 also agrees with the results in Fig. 2.4, showing that humans are less coherent at higher frequencies. This can be seen from the fact that the OSPA in cases 4 – 6 (frequencies from 14 to 18 GHz) of BP is slightly higher than that of cases 1 – 3 (frequencies from 7 to 11 GHz).

Our results with the proposed SPBP algorithm suggest that (i) using non-contiguous bands with **intermediate aperture sizes**, and (ii) combining **different subsets** of the available subbands in a **non-linear** fashion to cancel out the grating lobes represent interesting research directions to enable coherent multi-band ranging in FR3.

Figure 2.27: Number of targets (left) and OSPA (right) obtained by BP, OMP, and the proposed SPBP on two human targets. The black whiskers represent one standard deviation. SPBP outperforms the other two algorithms by better reconstructing the correct number of targets and obtaining the lowest OSPA.

2.3.2. PSF-aware multi-band OFDM Sensing with Coherent CLEAN Algorithm

2.3.2.1. Motivation and Contribution

Non-contiguous multi-band operation can synthesize a large virtual bandwidth, while the missing spectral components deterministically shape a point-spread function (PSF) that broadens the mainlobe and elevates sidelobes in the delay domain. This work recasts multi-band OFDM ranging as a **PSF-centric** problem and applies coherent deconvolution to remove PSF-induced artifacts in the range profile through the CLEAN algorithm [44]. The central message is that sensing performance is PSF-limited: the subband selection pattern determines the PSF, which in turn governs separability and the effectiveness of CLEAN.

2.3.2.2. PSF-centric Signal Model

Let an OFDM grid with K subcarriers cover a total span B with spacing $\Delta f = B/K$. With a binary Subcarrier Selection Function (SCF) $W[k] \in \{0, 1\}$, the frequency response is

$$H[k] = \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} \alpha_l W[k] e^{-j2\pi k \Delta f \tau_l}, \quad (2.51)$$

where α_l and τ_l denote the complex gain and round-trip delay of path l . After an IDFT, the delay profile reads

$$R[n] = \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} \alpha_l (w * D_K)[n - \tau_l'], \quad \tau_l' = \frac{\tau_l}{T_s}, \quad (2.52)$$

with $w[n] = \text{IDFT}\{W[k]\}$, $D_K[\cdot]$ the Dirichlet kernel on the full grid, $T_s = 1/B$, and $*$ the discrete convolution. Thus, for the same number of active subcarriers, different $W[k]$ yield different PSFs (mainlobe width and sidelobe level). A design that is purely bandwidth-driven is therefore insufficient; it must be PSF-aware.

2.3.2.3. Method: Coherent CLEAN for multi-band OFDM

CLEAN iteratively identifies the dominant residual component and subtracts a shifted/scaled copy of the known PSF. Let $h_{\text{PSF}}[n] = (w * D_K)[n]$ and $(\hat{\alpha}_j, \hat{n}_j)$ be the peak estimate at iteration j . The residual update is

$$R^{(j+1)}[n] = R^{(j)}[n] - \gamma \hat{\alpha}_j h_{\text{PSF}}[n - \hat{n}_j], \quad 0 < \gamma \leq 1, \quad (2.53)$$

and the reconstructed profile after J iterations is

$$\hat{R}_{\text{clean}}[n] = \sum_{j=0}^{J-1} \hat{\alpha}_j g[n - \hat{n}_j], \quad (2.54)$$

where $g[n]$ is a clean kernel (e.g., windowed sinc) targeting a resolution close to $1/B$. Because the subtraction kernel matches the PSF induced by $W[k]$, the selection pattern directly affects clean performance.

Figure 2.28: PSF-aware comparison under different subband selections. The selection pattern $W[k]$ (SCF, top) determines the resulting PSF (bottom): contiguous selection yields a wider mainlobe with milder sidelobes, while spread multi-band selection narrows the mainlobe but increases sidelobes, directly impacting sensing separability and artifact risk.

2.3.2.4. PSF-aware Design Principle

As shown in Figure 2.28, for a fixed number of active subcarriers, a contiguous selection typically produces a wider mainlobe with milder sidelobes, which limits separability; a spread non-contiguous selection narrows the mainlobe at the cost of stronger sidelobes, which increases artifact risk unless CLEAN effectively cancels them. The design objective is to select subbands that yield a PSF with a mainlobe narrow enough for the required separation and sidelobes sufficiently low (or spatially structured) for stable CLEAN subtraction.

2.3.2.5. Simulation Result

We evaluate the proposed multi-band OFDM sensing framework via simulation. The OFDM waveform uses a carrier frequency of 5.2 GHz and a total bandwidth of 320 MHz. A subcarrier spacing of 312.5 kHz is employed, yielding $N = 1024$ subcarriers over the full band.

To emulate a sparse multi-band setting, the 320 MHz bandwidth is partitioned into 16 non-overlapping subbands of 20 MHz each (64 subcarriers per subband). Only four subbands are activated for sensing, for a total of 256 active subcarriers and an effective sensing bandwidth of 80 MHz. This configuration reflects practical scenarios with fragmented spectrum where only a subset of subbands is available.

The target scene contains 15 static point reflectors arranged in three clusters, with intra-cluster spacings close to the nominal resolution. Additive white Gaussian noise is added to achieve $\text{SNR} = 10$ dB.

Metrics. (i) *Hit rate*: a detection is recorded when a peak in the processed profile falls within one delay bin of a ground-truth target and its amplitude is within ± 3 dB of the target's true amplitude. The hit rate is the fraction of ground-truth targets that are detected. (ii) *Distributional robustness*: empirical CDFs of the hit rate are reported under two ensembles: (a) 100 random subband selections with a fixed target scene; (b) a fixed subband pattern with 100 random target layouts (Fig. 2.30).

Figure 2.29 indicates that, under the contiguous pattern, CLEAN suppresses sidelobes but the wide mainlobe still limits separability; under the spread pattern, CLEAN removes most artifacts and resolves closely spaced

Figure 2.29: Range profiles with and without CLEAN under two PSFs.

Figure 2.30: Hit-rate CDFs showing PSF dependence and layout sensitivity; *PSF-aware* selection is essential.

clusters owing to the narrower mainlobe. Figure 2.30 summarizes the distributional behavior: across 100 random subband patterns, CLEAN consistently improves the hit rate yet the dispersion remains significant, implying strong PSF dependence; with the PSF fixed and the location of targets randomized, CLEAN again dominates while retaining sensitivity to target geometry.

Our results show that, in fragmented-spectrum settings, sensing accuracy is governed by the PSF induced by the subband pattern $W[k]$, in particular its mainlobe width and sidelobe level. For the same effective bandwidth, different choices of $W[k]$ yield distinct PSFs and measurably different performance, as evidenced by the range profiles and hit-rate CDFs. The design implication is direct: schedule subbands to produce a narrow mainlobe with controlled sidelobes, and apply CLEAN as a post-aggregation stage.

2.3.2.6. Use within MultiX

This work aims to employ the CLEAN algorithm to improve the range profile in the sensing processing framework, where results show that the performance under the sparse band with CLEAN is comparable to that in the full band sensing. It can therefore serve as one of the SePFs in the MultiX project. Besides, the insights of the subband selection can be used in the design time of ISAC systems.

2.3.3. Coherent Multi-band capable measurement system

In current 5G deployments, multi-band operation is typically handled by independent carrier aggregation, where different frequency bands (sub-6 GHz and Millimeter-Wave (mmWave)) are processed separately and then combined at higher layers. While this approach is sufficient for throughput aggregation, it falls short when coherent processing is required. In such cases, sub-6 GHz and mmWave systems must share a common timing and frequency reference, enabling phase-coherent joint signal processing across bands. Without coherence, impairments such as residual Carrier Frequency Offset (CFO), phase drift, and misaligned timestamps can lead to significant distortion, severely limiting the possibility of joint estimation, tracking, or ISAC functionalities. Within MultiX, we provide a multi-band measurement system built on RFSoc platform capable of driving both sub-6 GHz and mmWave interfaces in a synchronized manner. The system distributes a common reference clock and triggers to all converters, enabling sample-level alignment across bands. By employing multiple high-speed ADCs and DACs, the design is inherently MIMO-capable, allowing simultaneous multi-band and multi-antenna experimentation. This contribution establishes the core hardware and synchronization framework needed for the project's multi-band objectives, ensuring cross-band processing, joint channel estimation, and ISAC functionalities.

2.3.3.1. Challenges and contributions

Most existing sub-6 GHz and mmWave platforms are designed as standalone systems, each relying on its own local oscillators and triggering mechanisms. This separation makes it impossible to distribute a common reference clock or aligned triggers, and therefore prevents their direct use for coherent multi-band experiments. Even with synchronization, differences in oscillator stability, interface standards, and hardware drift introduce residual misalignments that degrade or even invalidate joint processing.

To address these limitations, within MultiX we developed a multi-band measurement system based on RFSoc firmware that distributes a shared reference clock and generates synchronized triggers for both sub-6 GHz and mmWave front-ends. This guarantees that signal acquisition and transmission across bands are fully aligned, enabling true coherent processing. The design also exploits the multiple high-speed ADCs and DACs available in the RFSoc to support MIMO operation, thereby extending coherence to multi-antenna setups. Importantly, the synchronization plane is integrated into our existing RFSoc-based testbeds, allowing direct comparison between conventional non-coherent operation and the new coherent multi-band mode. This dual capability provides the foundation for the cross-band sensing and communication objectives of MultiX.

2.3.3.2. Use within MultiX

This contribution acts as a key enabler for the multi-band objectives of WP3. By providing a measurement system that aligns sub-6 GHz and mmWave interfaces at the physical layer level, it creates the necessary foundation on which other multi-band contributions within this task can be validated. Algorithms for ISAC processing critically depend on a hardware platform where signals across frequency ranges are somehow coherent. Without this capability, their experimental validation would be limited or inconclusive.

Beyond its enabling role within WP3, the system also plays a central part in the MultiX PoC2, focused on contact-free eHealth monitoring in the home environment. Here, the ability of combining the robustness of sub-6 GHz signals with the fine spatial resolution of mmWave becomes essential to reliably monitor vital signs and detect small-scale movements without the need for wearable devices. The multi-band platform ensures that the sensing and communication functions envisioned in PoC2 can be jointly demonstrated under realistic experimental conditions

2.3.3.3. Platform Architecture

The experimental platform is built around an RFSoc device (AMD Xilinx ZCU111 [45]), which provides native flexibility to operate with mmWave front-ends at 28 GHz and 60 GHz as well as with any sub-6 GHz carrier frequency through the board's direct up- and down-conversion capabilities. The multiple high-speed ADCs and DACs integrated into the RFSoc enable parallel multi-stream operation, a prerequisite for the platform's intended multi-band functionality. The architecture is organized into two independent transmitter and receiver sub-systems, allowing operation in monostatic configurations as well as more general multi-static setups.

To maximize efficiency, the design leverages the dual nature of the RFSoc, with its Processing System (PS) handling high-level control and coordination, and its Programmable Logic (PL) implementing low-latency, high-

throughput signal generation and processing. This combination ensures that the platform can support the demanding requirements of coherent multi-band experimentation while maintaining flexibility for rapid reconfiguration and extension.

2.3.3.3.1 Programmable Logic (PL)

The PL integrates both the Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) fabric, where digital baseband operations are implemented, and the high-speed AD/DA converters, which provide direct RF signal processing. A single 122.88 MHz reference clock is distributed across the platform to drive both sub-6 GHz and mmWave subsystems, eliminating frequency and phase deviations that would otherwise hinder coherent multi-band processing. All converters are configured to operate at a 3932.2 MHz sampling frequency, with multi-tile synchronization ensuring sample-level alignment across channels. The PL is organized into two fully independent sub-systems dedicated to transmission and reception. This separation not only simplifies the design but also enables true monostatic operation, allowing signals to be transmitted and received simultaneously without mutual interference at the FPGA level. This architectural choice is central to supporting a wide range of configurations, from single-link monostatic setups to more complex multi-static deployments.

Transmitter sub-system: At the core of the transmitter chain is a loop-back memory (LBM) module that sequentially outputs pre-generated I/Q samples, enabling controlled and repeatable signal playback. A dedicated state machine manages sample retrieval, ensuring precise timing of releases from both sub-6 GHz and mmWave paths to their respective DACs. The design supports up to four concurrent sub-6 GHz transmissions and up to two mmWave transmissions, with flexibility to operate in any intermediate combination depending on the experimental needs. The subsystem further enables dual-bandwidth operation through configurable $\times 4$ up-sampling filters, each with a bypass option. This allows seamless switching between approximately 400 MHz and 1600 MHz of bandwidth for mmWave operation, and between 40 MHz and 160 MHz for sub-6 GHz operation. Such dynamic reconfigurability provides significant flexibility when adapting the platform to different multi-band scenarios. Fig. 2.31 presents the complete transmitter architecture, including both the internal RFSoc signal chain and the external components required for sub-6 GHz and mmWave transmission. To support advanced mmWave experimentation, the subsystem also integrates a dedicated mmWave Antenna Controller IP block [46]. This controller enables deterministic, high-speed beam updates, making it possible to implement real-time beam scanning and adaptive beamforming frameworks. This feature is central to MultiX use cases where fast beam management and ISAC functionalities are required.

Figure 2.31: Transmitter sub-system

Receiver sub-system: It is designed for memory-based data acquisition with full multi-tile synchronization, enabling the simultaneous and synchronous operation of up to two mmWave receivers and up to four sub-6 GHz receivers, or any combination in between. Each receiver chain integrates signal detection capabilities based on Synchronization Signal Blocks (SSBs), allowing the system to autonomously align to incoming transmissions.

Once a valid SSBs is detected in any stream, the remaining streams are automatically synchronized and locked to capture data concurrently. This mechanism is particularly valuable in scenarios where the mmWave link is blocked or suffers from severe attenuation, as it allows the platform to rely on more robust sub-6 GHz detection to ensure fully synchronized multi-band acquisition. For extended-duration experiments, the platform incorporates up to 4 GB of on-board RAM, enabling temporary storage of large volumes of received data before offloading to external systems for offline processing. This makes it possible to perform long measurement campaigns without interruption. A key feature of the receiver sub-system is its ability to synchronize data capture with the transmitter sub-system, a requirement for monostatic experiments. By means of a dedicated triggering mechanism, the transmitter can directly initiate data storage on the receiver side. This eliminates reliance on signal detection to start recording and leverages the deterministic latency of the architecture, ensuring that received data is stored with precise timing alignment. Such capability guarantees reproducibility and robustness even in cases where packet detection might otherwise introduce non-deterministic delays. The complete receiver architecture is illustrated in Fig. 2.32, which highlights both the internal RFSoc signal chain and the synchronization mechanisms that enable operation across sub-6 GHz and mmWave receivers.

Figure 2.32: Receiver sub-system

2.3.3.3.2 Processing System (PS)

The PS acts as the control bridge between the host PC and the PL, ensuring efficient communication and overall system coordination. It manages the testbed’s hardware resources, enabling seamless interaction between software-controlled components and the FPGA-based digital signal processing chain. A primary responsibility of the PS is the configuration of the phase-locked loops (PLLs) that generate and distribute the synchronized clock signals across the platform. This guarantees that all subsystems, including both sub-6 GHz and mmWave chains, operate on a common timing reference. The PS also configures and initializes the ADC and DAC converters, ensuring that they are properly synchronized and prepared for accurate data acquisition and transmission. In addition, the PS oversees the multi-tile synchronization procedure, which aligns the operation of multiple ADCs and DACs distributed across different processing tiles. This step is fundamental for enabling coherent, sample-level alignment of parallel data streams and is therefore critical to achieving the multi-band sensing and communication objectives of the platform.

2.3.3.4. Example of a Measurement system

The platform is designed to operate in a multi-band configuration and supports monostatic, bistatic, and, more generally, multi-static deployments by interconnecting multiple nodes. To illustrate its versatility, we describe here a representative scenario involving two multi-band nodes, where one operates as a transmitter and the other as a receiver. In this configuration, the transmitter node integrates a single 60 GHz mmWave transmitter and a single 2.4 GHz transmitter. The receiver node combines a single 60 GHz mmWave receiver with four 2.4 GHz receivers, enabling AoA estimation through Difference of Time of Arrival (DTOA) techniques across

the sub-6 GHz antenna array. In this example scenario, the mmWave transmitter is configured to sweep across different BPs, enabling AoD estimation, while the receiver operates in an omnidirectional mode to capture reflections from multiple directions. This setup allows the system to jointly exploit the directional resolution of mmWave beams and the robustness of sub-6 GHz links. Fig. 2.33 illustrates this two-node setup, where the main hardware components are:

- 2 × AMD Xilinx ZCU111 RFSoc platforms
- 2 × 60 GHz phased-array mmWave front-ends (Sivers Semiconductors)
- 5 × 2.4 GHz omnidirectional antennas
- Low-noise amplifiers, low-pass and band-pass filters, and DC blocks for signal conditioning

Figure 2.33: Example of a multi-band deployment

2.3.3.4.1 Synchronization Considerations

The two nodes can operate in different synchronization modes, depending on the experimental objective. In the unsynchronized mode, each node relies on its own local oscillators, mimicking a realistic system where impairments such as carrier frequency offset, timing misalignment, and phase drift are present. This mode requires the application of compensation techniques, as described in [47], and is useful for validating synchronization and correction algorithms under practical conditions.

Alternatively, a partially synchronized mode can be achieved by sharing a single low-frequency local oscillator between the two mmWave front-ends. This reduces oscillator drift while still preserving some residual offsets. Finally, a fully synchronized mode can be configured by deriving this oscillator from the RFSoc's reference, ensuring common timing across both nodes. Such a setup is particularly useful for experiments focused solely on validating multi-band algorithms, as it isolates the evaluation from hardware-level impairments.

2.3.3.4.2 Deployment Considerations

The geometric deployment of the nodes has a direct impact on the system's sensing resolution. In bistatic configurations such as the one illustrated in Fig. 2.33, the angle formed between the transmitter, the target, and the receiver determines the accuracy of parameter estimation. Wider bistatic angles can improve the system's ability to resolve target position and motion, while narrower angles may favor coverage but reduce spatial resolution. This flexibility allows the platform to be tuned depending on the experiment: for example, a configuration with small bistatic angles may be sufficient for communication-oriented validation, while wider geometries—as in the case of the illustrated scenario—are particularly valuable for sensing tasks such as contact-free monitoring of movement or vital signs.

2.3.3.5. Future Work

Building on the capabilities of the coherent multi-band platform, our next step is to exploit it for unambiguous Doppler estimation using multi-band CIR. The high-level idea is to leverage the complementary properties of sub-6 GHz and mmWave carriers to resolve the inherent ambiguities of Doppler estimation when using a single frequency band. At mmWave, the wide bandwidth and high carrier frequency provide fine temporal and spatial resolution, but also lead to rapid phase wrapping, which can make Doppler estimation ambiguous. In contrast, sub-6 GHz signals experience much slower phase evolution due to their lower carrier frequency, offering a more reliable but less precise Doppler reference. By coherently combining CIR measurements across both bands, it becomes possible to align and disambiguate the Doppler shifts observed at mmWave using the sub-6 GHz reference, while still benefiting from the high resolution of the mmWave band.

3. Task 3.2: Multi-technology, multi-static sensing integration

Task 3.2 targets the MultiX objective SO3.2: *Integrate multi-technology Radio Access Technologys (RATs) in the MultiX perception system, proposing algorithms for synchronization of multi-static systems and fusion of distributed raw sensing data.*

The goal of this task is to develop novel signal processing algorithms that leverage the advantages of distributed, multi-technology deployments of transmitter–receiver pairs. These algorithms will account for the heterogeneous characteristics of the participating nodes, including differences in bandwidth, channel representation, and timing constraints, enabling coherent exploitation of their sensing capabilities. Task 3.2 acts as a key enabler for multi-band processing (Task 3.1), while also benefiting from the propagation and sensing models developed therein.

To achieve this objective, we define four main activities that collectively fulfill the requirements of this task.

1. **Over-the-Air Synchronization for multi-static ISAC (Section 3.1).** This activity focuses on techniques to compensate for hardware-induced asynchronies among distributed transmitter–receiver pairs. It also investigates how to coherently combine their outputs to estimate the aggregate Doppler signatures of moving targets across multiple nodes.
2. **Multi-technology Sensing Integration (Section 3.2).** This activity explores how sensing information can be extracted from non-3GPP technologies and fused with 3GPP-compliant sensing data in a non-coherent manner, enabling cross-RAT situational awareness.
3. **Non-Coherent Mono/multi-static Sensing Fusion (Section 3.3).** This activity investigates fusion methods that combine monostatic and multi-static sensing observations to obtain multi-view representations of targets, enhancing robustness and spatial coverage without requiring phase-coherent links.
4. **Near-Field Processing (Section 3.4).** This activity aims to develop algorithms that exploit the near-field characteristics arising at high carrier frequencies and with large antenna apertures. These algorithms will enable fine-grained spatial sensing and high-precision localization capabilities.

3.1. Over-the-air synchronization techniques for multi-static ISAC

This sub-task develops over-the-air methods to handle independent oscillators and mobility in distributed transmitter-receiver pairs, targeting the estimation/cancellation of CFO and Phase Offset (PO) and the recovery of micro-Doppler without external references. We validate the approach in dynamic multi-antenna settings and outline its role as a calibration m-SePF. Within this sub-task, we carried out the following two research activities:

- Integrated Sensing and Communications with Asynchronous Moving Devices (Section 3.1.1). A model and algorithmic framework to separate Doppler from oscillator offsets in multi-static links with moving nodes, including optional Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) integration to bridge gaps in static-path references.
- Coherent multi-static imaging of moving point scatterers (Section 3.1.2). A coherent imaging method based on multiple base stations cooperating to compute a high-resolution representation of the environment.
- Over-the-air synchronization for multi-antenna dynamic ISAC deployments (Section 3.1.3). A multi-antenna OTA scheme that jointly processes LoS and target paths to cancel common CFO / PO and retrieve micro-Doppler and transmitter velocity in highly dynamic scenarios.

3.1.1. Integrated Sensing and Communications with Asynchronous Moving Devices

One of the key uses of ISAC concerns the estimation of the Doppler frequency caused by a moving target, which also reveals its velocity. On the one hand, Doppler estimation enhances the sensing resolution of the system, as it allows distinguishing targets moving at different speeds [48]. On the other hand, the Doppler effect can be leveraged by a wide range of fine-grained cellular and Wi-Fi sensing applications, such as person

identification based on gait [49], fall detection [50], drone monitoring [51], and human movement classification for smart homes and remote healthcare [52, 53].

Compared to indoor radar systems, Doppler estimation in ISAC poses several challenges. First, ISAC transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) devices are spatially separated (bistatic), so they rely on *asynchronous* LOs to generate the carrier signal, which is consequently affected by a time-varying relative drift [54]. This causes Timing Offset (TO), CFO, and a random PO across different transmissions. CFO and PO prevent the coherent processing of channel measurements across time, which is required for the estimation of the Doppler frequency [47].

We consider a Tx/Rx pair where one of these two devices is mobile, and the target is also moving. For this setup, differently from what is commonly assumed in ISAC research, an *additional* Doppler frequency contribution appears on the reflected signal due to the movement of the Tx or Rx device.

3.1.1.1. Challenges and contribution

The key challenge in *jointly* addressing clock asynchrony and moving Tx/Rx devices descends from the different properties of CFO/PO and from the motion-induced Doppler component of the Tx/Rx device, which adds up to the Doppler caused by the target. In fact, the noise due to CFO/PO is the same for all propagation paths [55] (spatial domain), but changes across subsequent communication packets (time domain), whereas the device Doppler changes slowly over time but causes a different frequency shift on each propagation path. We underline that existing techniques based on cross-antenna processing, [54], or reference paths, [55, 56], cannot concurrently cope with these different spatial and temporal dynamics. In fact, existing solutions only address the following scenarios: (i) *moving* monostatic radar systems, which are not affected by CFO and PO [57–59] and only need to compensate for the device Doppler shift, or (ii) asynchronous ISAC systems with *static* devices [47, 55, 60], which are only affected by CFO and PO. Either case poses stringent assumptions to the application scenario, limiting the range of use of previous solutions.

To address the above problems, we develop and validate AsyMov, a method for estimating the Doppler frequency of a target and the device velocity in bistatic mobile ISAC setups using only the wireless signal. This activity is associated with our paper [61].

Our approach obtains phase measurements at the Rx from different multipath reflections across time in the channel impulse response (CIR). Hence, it removes CFO and PO by leveraging their invariance across the received propagation paths. Then, since each multipath component is *differently* affected by the Tx or Rx motion, we exploit this as a source of *diversity* to reduce the number of unknowns in the phase measurements model. As a result, we can successfully cast the Doppler frequency estimation of the target as a non-linear system of equations that can be solved if at least two multipath components from static scatterers are available. In such a case, the target's Doppler and the ISAC device velocity are jointly estimated via a newly proposed and efficient alternating minimization algorithm that operates on time-averaged phase measurements. As an additional feature, AsyMov can seamlessly integrate measurements of any moving device velocity obtained with an onboard IMU, which may be available on mobile devices.

The contributions of this activity are summarized as follows.

1. We solve the problem of estimating the Doppler frequency of a target and the Tx/Rx device velocity in bistatic ISAC with asynchronous *moving* devices. Our solution uniquely relies on the analysis of the received wireless signal by means of an original CIR phase measurements differencing step and a new alternating minimization algorithm.
2. We evaluate AsyMov performance on real measurements, collected with a 60 GHz IEEE 802.11ay testbed in different setups. Our results show that AsyMov achieves median estimation errors as low as 3 Hz for the Doppler frequency, 3° for device movement direction, and 2 cm/s for the device speed.
3. We demonstrate improvements over existing MUSIC-based methods [62], combined with JUMP [55] for asynchrony compensation. Moreover, AsyMov is more accurate than a benchmark algorithm that estimates the device movement with an onboard IMU sensor, and it can be easily integrated with IMU measurements when the number of multipath components in the CIR is insufficient.

In the following sections, we report our main results and refer to the original paper for a more detailed discussion [61].

3.1.1.2. Use within MultiX

This activity represents a first step towards multi-static synchronization for coherent processing, serving as an enabler for T3.2 and for PoC2. The proposed method achieves over-the-air synchronisation under device movement for bistatic pairs of devices. This can be applied to each bistatic pair in a multi-static setting, obtaining global synchronisation which is also robust to device movement, in case some of the devices are, e.g., UEs. Moreover, AsyMov represents an example of multi-modal sensor integration in ISAC networks due to its capability to combine wireless signals and IMU measurements.

3.1.1.3. System and signal models

Consider two ISAC devices acting, respectively, as transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx), located on a 2-dimensional (2D), horizontal Cartesian plane. Denote by t the continuous time variable, and refer to $\mathbf{x}^{\text{tx}}(t)$ and $\mathbf{x}^{\text{rx}}(t)$ as the time-varying locations of the Tx and Rx devices, respectively. In the following, without loss of generality, we consider the Tx to be mobile, while the Rx is static, i.e., $\mathbf{x}^{\text{rx}}(t) = \mathbf{x}^{\text{rx}}$. We call $v^{\text{tx}}(t)$ and $\eta(t)$ the Tx speed and movement direction with respect to the LoS segment between Tx and Rx.

Figure 3.1: Reference scenario and multipath geometry. The time dependency is omitted for better visualization.

We consider Q static or mobile scatterers in the environment, indexed by $q = 1, \dots, Q$, each at location $\mathbf{x}_q(t)$. Mobile scatterers have a velocity $v_q(t)$, as shown in Fig. 3.1. We aim to estimate the bistatic Doppler frequency caused by a moving scatterer of interest, called *target* using channel estimates obtained by the Rx as part of normal communication and AoD estimates.

Consider the wireless signal transmitted by the Tx device. We call $\lambda = c/f_c$ the wavelength of the transmitted signal carrier, with c being the speed of light and f_c the carrier frequency. We consider a multipath channel including Q delayed, Doppler-shifted, and attenuated copies of the transmitted signal, caused by the Q scatterers in the environment.

3.1.1.4. Doppler frequency model

The Tx movement causes the following instantaneous Doppler shift on the q -th path

$$f_{\text{D},q}^{\text{tx}}(t) = \frac{1}{\lambda} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \|\mathbf{x}^{\text{rx}} - \mathbf{x}^{\text{tx}}(t)\| \approx \frac{v^{\text{tx}}(t)}{\lambda} \cos \xi_q(t), \quad (3.1)$$

where $\xi_q(t)$ is the angle between the segment connecting the q -th scatterer to the Tx and the Tx velocity vector. The approximation in Eq. (3.1) holds for short processing intervals, during which we consider the movement of the Tx to be well approximated by a constant-velocity model [63]. We remark that the Doppler due to the movement of the Tx or Rx is not modeled in recent works that tackle asynchronous bistatic ISAC systems, e.g., [55, 64].

The movement of the target causes an additional Doppler shift on the reflected signal. Specifically, due to the separation of the Tx and Rx devices in the 2D space, we consider the bistatic Doppler shift, $f_{\text{D},q}(t)$. We do not estimate the moving velocity vector of the target, but only the aggregate Doppler shift $f_{\text{D},q}(t)$.

3.1.1.5. CIR estimate model

In Single Carrier (SC) systems, e.g., IEEE 802.11ay, the Rx estimates the CIR directly using cross-correlation of the received signal with a known pilot sequence such as complementary Golay sequences which exhibit

perfect autocorrelation property with no frequency shift. In OFDM systems, e.g., 5G-NR, an estimate of the CFR is computed at the receiver by exploiting a known preamble. The CIR can then be obtained via IDFT of the estimated CFR.

As a consequence of the finite bandwidth of the ISAC system, two or more scatterers may be closer than the delay resolution, given by $\Delta_\tau = 1/B$ where B is the Tx signal bandwidth. Hence, we consider a multipath channel including $M(t) \leq Q$ resolvable components, indexed by $m = 1, \dots, M(t)$. The estimated CIR is discretized in the delay domain with granularity Δ_τ and the discrete delay grid is given by $l\Delta_\tau, l = 0, \dots, L - 1$, where L is the grid span.

The CIR estimation is repeated across multiple time frames, indexed by k , at instants $t_k, k = 0, \dots, K - 1$, where K is the number of frames and we consider $t_0 = 0$ s. We denote the inter-frame spacing by $T_k = t_k - t_{k-1}$. Note that the inter-frame spacing can be irregular, i.e., channel estimation does not need to happen on a regular sampling grid.

Using a common assumption in ISAC and radar processing, we consider a short processing window of duration t_{K-1} [65], where the parameters, $M(t), \tau_m(t), f_{D,m}(t), \alpha_m(t), A_m(t), \eta(t), \xi_m(t), v^{\text{tx}}(t)$, and consequently the Tx motion-induced Doppler shift $f_{D,m}^{\text{tx}}(t)$ can be considered constant.

The offsets caused by the asynchrony of Tx and Rx, i.e., TO, CFO, and PO are denoted by $\tau_o(t), f_o(t)$, and $\psi_o(t)$, respectively. All the nuisance parameters, $\tau_o(t), f_o(t), \psi_o(t)$, are *time-varying* within the window.

The noise-free estimated CIR at the k -th frame is

$$h[k, l] = e^{j\psi_o(t_k)} \sum_{m=1}^M A_m e^{j\vartheta_m[k]} \chi(l\Delta_\tau - \tau_m - \tau_o(t_k)), \quad (3.2)$$

where $\vartheta_m[k] = 2\pi(f_{D,m} + f_o(t_k) + f_{D,m}^{\text{tx}})t_k$. In Eq. (3.2), $\chi(l\Delta_\tau)$ is the point-target response of the limited bandwidth system (e.g., a sinc function in OFDM systems).

In our scenario, we consider that the M propagation paths can be partitioned as follows: (i) a LoS path, which represents the direct propagation from the Tx to the Rx, (ii) a single moving target path, (iii) S static scatterers paths for which $f_{D,m} = 0$. Point (ii) is not a requirement for AsyMov, but simplifies the derivation. If multiple targets are present, AsyMov should be applied on each corresponding peak in the CIR. Note that assumption (i) simplifies the description of the algorithm, but is not strictly required. In fact, AsyMov is still applicable when the LoS is not available, by replacing the LoS path with a reference static path caused by a strong scatterer or reflector.

Next, we focus on estimating the target Doppler frequency under the nuisance due to the CFO, PO, and the Tx motion. Hence, we assume that the Rx can detect and separate the M multipath components and extract their phase across time. To this end, the TO can be compensated for by obtaining *relative* delay measurements with respect to the LoS, as done in [55].

To obtain phase measurements, we extract the phase of the CIR paths as follows. We group the CFO and PO terms, which are the same on all propagation paths, into $\Psi_o(t_k) = \psi_o(t_k) + 2\pi f_o(t_k)t_k$. Moreover, we use subscripts \cdot_{LoS} and \cdot_t to refer to quantities related to the LoS and to the target-induced paths, respectively, as shown in Fig. 3.1. For the paths caused by static scatterers, we use index $s = 1, \dots, S$, where S is the number of resolvable static scatterers detected in the processing window, with $S = M - 2$. The phase of the LoS, neglecting noise, is

$$\phi_{\text{LoS}}[k] = \Psi_o(t_k) + \angle A_{\text{LoS}} + 2\pi t_k \left(\frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} \cos \eta \right), \quad (3.3)$$

where $\angle \cdot$ is the phase operator, $\xi_{\text{LoS}} = \eta$. The noise-free phase of the target-induced path is affected by both the Doppler shift caused by the target, $f_{D,t}$, and by the Tx motion, v^{tx} , as

$$\phi_t[k] = \Psi_o(t_k) + \angle A_t + 2\pi t_k \left(f_{D,t} + \frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} \cos \xi_t \right), \quad (3.4)$$

where ξ_t is the angle between the segment connecting the target to the Tx and the Tx velocity vector. The phase of the s -th static multipath component is

$$\phi_s[k] = \Psi_o(t_k) + \angle A_s + 2\pi t_k \left(\frac{v^{\text{tx}}}{\lambda} \cos \xi_s \right), \quad (3.5)$$

From the CIR, the Rx measures $\text{mod}_{2\pi}(\phi_i[k])$ where $i \in \{t, \text{LoS}, s\}, k = 0, \dots, K - 1$, and $\text{mod}_{2\pi}(\cdot)$ is the modulo 2π division, whose result is in $[0, 2\pi)$. Note that while we presented the measurement model in the absence of noise, we consider it in our algorithm as further detailed in [61], where we also carry out a theoretical analysis of identifiability and CRLB of our model.

3.1.1.6. AsyMov algorithm

In this section, we introduce AsyMov, which estimates the bistatic Doppler frequency of the target from the phase measurements in Eqs. (3.3-3.5). The phase measurements are extracted from the CIR estimate as described in the previous section and shown in the left part of Fig. 3.2. The processing steps carried out by AsyMov are shown in the yellow block in Fig. 3.2 and summarized in Alg. 1.

Figure 3.2: Block diagram of the AsyMov algorithm.

A. CFO and PO cancellation. The phase offsets component, Ψ_o , is common to all propagation paths. Hence, we can subtract the phase of the LoS path from the other phase measurements, by *canceling out* Ψ_o , as done in line 2 of Alg. 1. This step does not require a direct estimation of the phase offsets, enabling coherent processing of the multipath components with minimal complexity.

B. Time-domain phase differencing. By computing time-domain phase differences *for each path*, we cancel out the path-specific phase terms due to the complex path amplitudes, $\angle A_i$, with $i \in \{t, \text{LoS}, s\}$. The resulting phase differences only depend on the Doppler shifts due to the Tx and the target. This is done in line 3 of Alg. 1.

C. AoD-based simplification. We leverage AoD estimation at the Tx and the multipath geometry to make a key simplification in the phase measurements model. Specifically, we notice that $\cos \xi_j = \cos(\eta - \alpha_j) = \cos(\alpha_j - \eta)$, with $i \in \{t, s\}$. This substitution removes the dependency on the unknown and path-dependent angle ξ_j . The new dependency on $\alpha_j - \eta$, for $i \in \{t, s\}$, is easier to handle since the Rx estimates α_j and the unknown term η is independent of the propagation paths. This reduces the number of unknowns, thus enabling the estimation of the target Doppler frequency if at least 2 static multipath components are detected.

D. Doppler frequency estimation. We normalize the simplified phase measurements (line 4 of Alg. 1). Then we formulate the estimation of the target's Doppler frequency as a non-convex optimization problem across the multipath components. First, the measured phase differences are averaged over time, obtaining $\bar{\Delta} = \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \tilde{\Delta}[k]/(K-1)$ (line 6 in Alg. 1). Then, we formulate the following non-convex optimization problem

$$\arg \min_{f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}} \|\bar{\Delta} - \Gamma \nu\|_2^2 \quad (3.6)$$

$$\text{subject to } v^{\text{tx}} \geq 0, \eta \in [0, 2\pi), \quad (3.7)$$

where

$$\Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \lambda^{-1} (\cos(\eta - \alpha_t) - \cos \eta) \\ 0 & \lambda^{-1} (\cos(\eta - \alpha_1) - \cos \eta) \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & \lambda^{-1} (\cos(\eta - \alpha_S) - \cos \eta) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.8)$$

In Eq. (3.6), the variables $f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}$ only appear in vector ν . Conversely, η only appears in Γ . Our solution algorithm leverages such decoupled structure to alternatively optimize over the pair of variables $f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}$ and then over η .

While the estimate of η changes sufficiently across iterations, we first fix $\hat{\eta}^{(n)}$ and find $f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}$ that minimize Eq. (3.6). The symbol \dagger denotes the pseudo-inverse of a matrix, $\hat{\nu} = [\hat{f}_{D,t}, \hat{v}^{\text{tx}}]^\top$ contains the estimates of the target Doppler frequency and Tx movement speed, and $\Pi(\nu) = [f_{D,t}, \max(0, v^{\text{tx}})]^\top$ projects the least squares solution onto the feasible set with $v^{\text{tx}} \geq 0$.

Then, $f_{D,t}, v^{\text{tx}}$ are fixed, so the problem reduces to finding the η that minimizes Eq. (3.6). Optimization over η can be efficiently carried out by a grid search in the bounded interval $[0, 2\pi)$. We construct grid $\mathcal{G} = \{0, 2\pi/N_\eta, \dots, 2\pi(N_\eta - 1)/N_\eta\}$ where N_η is the number of grid candidates and we select the one that minimizes Eq. (3.6).

Algorithm 1: AsyMov algorithm.

Require: Phase measurements $\phi_{\text{LoS}}[k]$, $\phi_t[k]$, $\phi_s[k]$, $s = 1, \dots, S$.

Ensure: Estimates of the parameters $\hat{f}_{\text{D,t}}$, \hat{v}^{tx} , $\hat{\eta}$.

- 1: **for** $k = 0, \dots, K - 1$ **do**
 - 2: $\tilde{\phi}_t[k] = \angle(e^{j\phi_t[k]} / e^{j\phi_{\text{LoS}}[k]})$ (CFO and PO cancellation)
 - 3: $\Delta_i[k] = \angle(e^{j\tilde{\phi}_i[k]} / e^{j\tilde{\phi}_i[k-1]})$ (time domain differencing)
 - 4: $\tilde{\Delta}_i[k] = \Delta_i[k] / (2\pi T_k)$, $i \in \{t, s\}$ (normalize phases)
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: $\tilde{\Delta} = \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \tilde{\Delta}[k] / (K - 1)$ (average phases)
 - 7: $\hat{f}_{\text{D,t}}, \hat{v}^{\text{tx}}, \hat{\eta} \leftarrow$ Alternating minimization with input $\tilde{\Delta}$, α_t , $\{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_S\}$.
-

3.1.1.7. Experimental results

Testbed: Our testbed consists of two ISAC nodes acting as Tx and Rx. Each node comprises a Xilinx RFSoc for baseband signal processing and a mmWave Siverts 16-elements phased array antennas operating at $f_c = 60$ GHz. The implementation is based on that presented in [55]. We refer to [55, 66] for additional details on the testbed setup.

The Tx sends IEEE 802.11ay standard-compliant packets with 1.76 GHz bandwidth, including an IEEE 802.11ay header and a TRN field. This field contains 12 TRN units, each composed of 6 complementary Golay sequences [67]. We use each TRN unit to estimate the channel for a different Tx beam pattern, scanning the whole angular space in front of the Tx. This allows us to estimate the AoD of each multipath component with respect to the antenna array orientation, using the algorithm in [68]. To perform CIR estimation, we compute the cross-correlation of the received signal with the known TRN units at the Rx. Then, we apply peak detection to isolate significant multipath components and estimate AoD for each peak using the algorithm in [68].

The experiments are performed in a 5×4 m laboratory equipped with an infrared camera-based motion tracking system, as shown in Fig. 3.3. The camera system allows obtaining the accurate positions of each object in the environment to be used as a ground-truth reference. For this, we place infrared markers on the Tx, Rx, static reflectors, and targets. To evaluate AsyMov with mobile ISAC nodes, we mount the Tx on a wheeled cart, moving it during the measurements.

We consider 3 different evaluation setups, as described next.

- *Setup 1 (SU1).* As shown in Fig. 3.3a, the first setup includes quasi-monostatic Tx and Rx, placed at a distance of 40 cm from one another and oriented towards the targets. In this setup, static and dynamic reflections are produced using metal whiteboards placed in the environment. The moving target whiteboard is mounted on a wheeled chair.
- *Setup 2 (SU2).* A more challenging evaluation is conducted in a bistatic setting, with widely separated Tx and Rx, as shown in Fig. 3.3b. This experiment reproduces more realistic conditions where the LoS path is weaker and the orientation of the ISAC devices is unknown.
- *Setup 3 (SU3).* Similar to SU1, this setup includes quasi-monostatic Tx and Rx, 50 cm apart from one another and oriented towards the targets. However, as shown in Fig. 3.3c, this is a more realistic setup where the target is human and the static paths are produced by common office furniture, including a desktop computer and a desk. The person carries a plastic plate on which we place the infrared markers.

In our experiments, unless specified, we consider the inter-frame duration T_k to be constant and denote it by $T = 0.254$ ms.

Results: AsyMov is evaluated in terms of absolute estimation errors on the target Doppler frequency, the Tx speed, and η , respectively defined as $\hat{\varepsilon}_{f_{\text{D,t}}} = |f_{\text{D,t}} - \hat{f}_{\text{D,t}}|$, $\hat{\varepsilon}_{v^{\text{tx}}} = |v^{\text{tx}} - \hat{v}^{\text{tx}}|$, $\hat{\varepsilon}_{\eta} = |\eta - \hat{\eta}|$. The ground truth $f_{\text{D,t}}$ is obtained by using the ground truth locations of the Tx, the Rx, and the target, obtained from the motion tracking system.

To the best of our knowledge, no other ISAC method tackles Doppler estimation with asynchronous and *moving* devices. Therefore, we define a benchmark algorithm that applies the technique proposed in JUMP [55] to remove the phase offsets, followed by the MUSIC algorithm to estimate the target Doppler frequency [62]. We call this benchmark JUMP-MUSIC (JM). Since JM does not account for the Tx movement, it is biased by its Doppler frequency shift. The computational complexity of JM is $\mathcal{O}(K^3)$ due to the eigenvalue decomposition of the covariance matrix of the channel measurements in MUSIC. In Fig. 3.4, we compare AsyMov and JM error results, $\hat{\varepsilon}_{f_{\text{D,t}}}$, in different setups using a mobile or static Tx. We use $S = 2$ and $KT = 8$ ms or $KT = 48$ ms. For

Figure 3.3: Visualization of the experimental setup.

Figure 3.4: Target Doppler frequency estimation error for different setups, with $S = 2$ and varying aggregation window KT .

both SU1 and SU2 (Fig. 3.4a and Fig. 3.4b), the error obtained by AsyMov is only slightly higher with a moving Tx compared to a static one. Conversely, JM achieves similar performance only in the case of a static Tx. When the Tx moves, the bias due to the corresponding Doppler hinders a correct target Doppler estimation, leading to a 320% and 44% higher median error with respect to AsyMov in SU1 and SU2, respectively. Furthermore, in Fig. 3.4c we show that AsyMov is also effective in a realistic environment with a human target. As expected, the very low SNR on the target path due to the weak human body scattering at 60 GHz increases the error $\hat{\epsilon}_{f_D}$. However, also in this case, AsyMov outperforms JM when the Tx moves, by approximately 10% in terms of median error. The smaller performance gap in this case is due to the error being dominated by the impact of noise, resulting from the low target reflectivity. This demonstrates that only AsyMov successfully copes with the motion of ISAC devices.

Finally, we test the integration of our model with the Tx velocity measured by the onboard IMU sensor. This is done by obtaining an estimate of v^{tx} from the IMU, in the reference system of the Tx. Then, this velocity is used as an additional input to AsyMov, thereby reducing the number of unknowns to two, and Eq. (3.6) can be solved using a single static reference path.

As shown in Fig. 3.5, integrating the Tx speed measurement from the IMU could enhance the reliability of AsyMov. In this experiment, the CIR peak corresponding to one of the required static paths is not detected for several subsequent frames in the interval [1.5, 2.1] s. Within this time interval, AsyMov lacks sufficient information (static paths) to estimate the target Doppler frequency and fails, as shown by the yellow curve. Conversely, when feeding the IMU measurement to AsyMov, the Doppler frequency is estimated accurately even when not all the CIR peaks are detected (pink curve). Interestingly, when all the required CIR peaks are available, AsyMov is more accurate *without* using the IMU measurement. This is evident from the zoom plot in Fig. 3.5 and from Tab. 3.1, where we quantitatively evaluate the Doppler estimation error for three different time intervals in the experiment of Fig. 3.5. While in the interval [1.5, 2.1] s using the IMU gives a large performance gain, outside of this interval, estimating the Doppler solely based on the wireless channel cuts the estimation error by half with respect to using the IMU. Based on these results, the IMU should only be used to compensate for the temporary lack of a sufficient number of static multipath components.

Table 3.1: Average target Doppler frequency estimation error \pm one standard deviation, with one undetected path within [1.5, 2.1] s.

Error [Hz]	Time interval		
	[0, 1.5] s	[1.5, 2.1] s	[2.1, 7.3] s
w/ IMU	5.32 ± 4.04	10.72 ± 12.32	6.51 ± 3.89
w/o IMU	2.06 ± 2.24	168 ± 518	2.91 ± 2.33

Figure 3.5: Target Doppler frequency with $S = 2$ and $KT = 16$ ms.

3.1.2. Coherent multi-static imaging of moving point scatterers

In ISAC, radio resources (time, frequency, space, and hardware) are shared between the communication and sensing functionalities, with an application-specific performance trade-off [69]. This will likely enable new market verticals supported by 6G networks, where pervasive environment sensing is needed [1]. Early research on ISAC [70, 71] explored optimal waveform design to combine communication and sensing functionalities at a single ISAC device pair, namely one transmitter (Tx) and one sensing receiver (Rx), typically considering OFDM. More recently, research has shifted towards ISAC *networks*, where multiple devices cooperate to improve sensing accuracy, capacity, and overall reliability. From the sensing perspective, this allows going beyond the capabilities of single ISAC devices, by providing additional spatial diversity to enhance the sensing resolution and multiple viewpoints. ISAC networks can concurrently leverage *monostatic* and *bistatic* sensing modalities, depending on whether Tx and sensing Rx are co-located or not, as well as generic *multi-static* configurations.

The existing literature on ISAC networks does not fully exploit the potential of distributed coherent sensing, since they focus on *localizing* targets, estimating their position, velocity, and/or orientation. Thus, the system design stems from the minimization of some expression relating the CRLB of the parameters of interest with the optimization variables, under some constraints. However, the CRLB can only be obtained in simple scenarios with few well-separated targets.

In practice, the ISAC network does not know the number of targets or their *a-priori* location in space. In these settings, *imaging* the environment is more appropriate. This consists of retrieving a 2D or 3D map of the complex reflectivity of the environment, from which to detect how many targets are present, localize them, and identify their shape and size. The main performance metric for imaging is *resolution*, namely the ability to distinguish two closely spaced targets, since this determines the quality of the ISAC perception.

3.1.2.1. Challenges and contribution

A promising direction for exploiting the potential of sensing-enabled 6G networks is to enable cooperation among multiple distributed ISAC devices to improve imaging performance. To this end, the most promising and challenging opportunity is *coherent distributed imaging*, where ISAC devices fuse their locally generated images by retaining the carrier phase, acting as a phase-coherent distributed array, improving spatial resolution

and SNR. Each device shall operate on a common time reference to correctly estimate the sensor-to-target Time of Flight (ToF) with an accuracy inversely proportional to the *carrier frequency*, and fuse the Rx data on a common spatial grid. Notice that the requirement is much tighter compared to conventional synchronization, which requires an accuracy proportional to the inverse of the Tx bandwidth [72]. In practice, however, the clock's time, frequency, and phase errors cause a space-varying TOF bias in bistatic setups, which calls for more OTA synchronization approaches [73]. Along this line, works [55, 74–76] have recently outlined synchronization methods exploiting the line-of-sight (LOS) link among ISAC device pairs.

The above works are affected by a significant limitation in that they can only produce images of *static targets*. High-resolution imaging of moving targets holds great promise for ISAC, as *dynamic* objects are the main targets of interest in many 6G applications, e.g., autonomous driving (pedestrians approaching the lane), human gesture recognition, crowd sensing, among others [77].

In the ISAC context, the existing literature on moving target imaging is scarce and focused on specific application scenarios, e.g., Wi-Fi [78, 79]. The main limitations of these approaches are: (i) they assume a *single target*, whose multiple parts share similar velocity, and (ii) they assume a bistatic scenario with a *single device pair*. Conversely, we address the imaging of *multiple targets* with different velocities, e.g., people walking in a crowd, with *multi-static* ISAC systems.

In this activity, we design and validate the first phase-coherent multi-static imaging method for *moving targets*, based on distributed asynchronous ISAC devices.

Our main contributions are summarized in the following. For a full description of the system and methods, we refer to the paper [80].

- We propose a method for high-resolution coherent imaging of moving targets from distributed asynchronous OFDM-based ISAC devices. Our approach re-uses pilot preambles, such as the Demodulation Reference Signal (DMRS) in 3GPP [81], to observe the targets' motion without the need for dedicated signal transmission.
- Our approach includes an OTA synchronization method for joint time, frequency, and phase synchronization among distributed ISAC devices. The method leverages the LOS path among devices, adapting our previous work [55] to suit coherent distributed imaging.
- At the core of the proposed method lies a novel association algorithm among the coarsely detected locations of targets from standard coherent images, e.g., from [11], and the set of estimated Doppler peaks, obtained from each ISAC device pair. This allows for accurately estimating the velocity vector of *each target*, and using it to pre-compensate the corresponding Doppler shift experienced at each device pair. This allows obtaining *target-specific* images, where *only one* target is present, mitigating clutter.
- We perform extensive numerical simulations showing that our method can improve target localization performance up to a factor of 18 compared to existing state-of-the-art imaging methods [11]. Remarkably, multiple moving targets can be localized with cm-level accuracy, ultimately limited by the image pixel size, with much less complexity compared to existing methods for single moving target imaging [82, 83]. Moreover, each target's velocity vector is estimated with cm/s-level accuracy, which has not been achieved in the state-of-the-art.

3.1.2.2. Use within MultiX

This activity represents a first step towards multi-static synchronization and coherent imaging, serving as an enabler for T3.2 and for PoC2. This is one of the core technological advancements proposed by MultiX and represents a key innovation of the MPS, implemented in the MultiX m-SePF-03.

3.1.2.3. System description

We consider the network of N ISAC devices illustrated in Fig. 3.6. Each ISAC device is located at $\mathbf{p}_n \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 1}$, $n = 1, \dots, N$, containing its x and y coordinates on the 2D horizontal plane. Each device is used in monostatic and bistatic operations to obtain a high-resolution image of a desired portion of the environment while communicating with other devices. The environment of interest is composed of Q targets. The q -th target is located in $\mathbf{x}_q \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 1}$, and moves with a constant arbitrary velocity $\mathbf{v}_q \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 1}$. Each device is equipped with a uniform linear array (ULA) of L antennas, supporting full-duplex operation. This setting allows concurrently acquiring monostatic and bistatic data, but the present work is also valid in half-duplex settings, with bistatic

sensing only. Similarly, the number of antennas can differ at each device, without impacting the proposed methodology. The location of the ℓ -th antenna of the n -th ISAC device is $\mathbf{p}_n^\ell = \mathbf{p}_n + [\ell d \cos \psi_n, \ell d \sin \psi_n]^\top$, where d is the inter-antenna spacing and ψ_n is the ULA orientation angle in global coordinates. The carrier frequency of operation is denoted by f_0 and the total bandwidth (common to all ISAC devices) is B . The ISAC devices employ an OFDM waveform to communicate and image the environment, with M subcarriers, indexed by $m = 0, \dots, M-1$ and subcarrier spacing $\Delta f = B/M$. Time is discretized along a *fast time* dimension (which is the dual domain to frequency spanned by the OFDM subcarriers) and a *slot time* dimension, indexed by $t = kT$, denoting the reception time of multiple OFDM symbols. Note that our model and processing steps could be easily adapted to other modulation types, such as single carrier transmission.

Figure 3.6: Coherent multi-static imaging system model.

3.1.2.4. Imaging methodology

As a first processing step, we perform CFO and PO compensation by leveraging the LoS path, similarly to what is proposed in [55]. As a result, we have a set of vectorized received signals $\Delta \mathbf{h}_{nm}(t, kT)$, where the multiple components correspond to the different Rx antennas. These are available for every Tx-Rx pair identified by indices n, m , and is used as input for the imaging algorithm. The second step before applying our processing method is to perform standard imaging using the Rx signals, via a standard BP algorithm. This combines the signals at all Rx antennas to obtain low-resolution images of the environment, denoted by $I_{nm}(\mathbf{x}, kT)$, where \mathbf{x} is a pixel's location in the 2D space. The low-resolution images are then coherently combined into a single high-resolution image $I(\mathbf{x}, kT)$, but this is affected by Doppler due to the targets' motion, which is different for each pair n, m . This causes defocusing of the targets in the combined images. Our approach aims at compensating for this Doppler to obtain focused images and exploit it to estimate the velocity vector corresponding to each target.

The proposed algorithm follows five steps, as shown in Fig. 3.7:

- A. **Doppler estimation from low-resolution images.** In this step, we estimate the Doppler spectrum for each Tx-Rx pair from the low-resolution images. This yields the Doppler shifts estimates $\hat{f}_{nm,q}^D$ for target q as observed by pair n, m .
- B. **Coarse targets' locations estimation.** From the defocused high-resolution image $I(\mathbf{x}, kT)$, we estimate coarse spatial locations of the targets of interest by applying incoherent peak detection and subtraction, obtaining $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_q$ for target q .
- C. **Doppler-space association and velocity estimation.** An association problem is solved to associate each Doppler shift to the corresponding target and, as a byproduct, the velocity vector of each target is obtained and denoted by $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_q$.
- D. **Doppler pre-compensation.** The obtained velocity vectors are used to obtain the Doppler shifts that should be observed at each Tx-Rx pair for target q . These are then used to pre-compensate for the Doppler phase shift while performing the BP algorithm for low-resolution imaging, obtaining Doppler-free images $\tilde{I}_{nm,q}(\mathbf{x}, kT)$.
- E. **High-resolution imaging of moving targets.** Low-resolution images are coherently combined into high-resolution images by computing $\tilde{I}_q(\mathbf{x}, kT) = \sum_{nm} \tilde{I}_{nm,q}(\mathbf{x}, kT)$. The result is now correctly focused for each target q , while other targets disappear as a result of incoherent summation with rotating phases.

Figure 3.7: Coherent multi-static imaging method for moving targets.

3.1.2.5. Numerical results

In the following, we refer to our algorithm as MovISAC. To evaluate MovISAC, we perform numerical simulations including a variable number of ISAC devices, equipped with $L = 32$ antennas.

We consider a carrier frequency $f_0 = 26.5$ GHz and signal bandwidth $B = 400$ MHz, emulating a 5G cellular scenario. The available bandwidth gives each ISAC device a range resolution of $c/(2B) = 37.5$ cm when considered as a monostatic sensor. In the following, a variable number of ISAC devices are deployed along x , with different spacing D depending on the specific scenario.

The preamble repetition interval is set to $T = 0.5$ ms, with slow-time processing windows of KT s with $K = 64$. We consider the TO α_n to be uniformly distributed in $[0, 10/B]$. The CFO evolves across slow-time according to a first-order auto-regressive random process. The process is initialized as $\beta_n(0) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_0^2)$, with $\sigma_0 = 10^{-4} = 100$ ppm. Then, it evolves following $\beta_n(kT) = 0.99\beta_n((k-1)T) + 0.01W_k$, with $W_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_0^2)$ [84]. Unless stated otherwise, we set the same RCS for all targets, $\Gamma_q = 0$ dBm², following the results obtained in [85], and the scattering phases are uniform in $[0, 2\pi]$. The sensing SNR at the antenna is $\text{SNR}_{nm,1} = \sigma_s^2 |\varrho_{nm,1}|^2 / \sigma_w^2$, taking the first target as a reference.

We compare MovISAC with the following two algorithms.

- **Standard multi-static imaging (SMI)**. SMI combines the single low-resolution images, following the steps illustrated in the green box in Fig. 3.7. The locations of targets are estimated by looking for the \hat{Q} maxima in the final image, detected with the CFAR algorithm [48]. Except for the synchronization step, this approach follows the state-of-the-art method proposed in [11].

- **Iterative SAF subtraction (ISAFS)**. ISAFS improves SMI by introducing an iterative SAF subtraction algorithm [80]. This results in improved target localization with respect to SMI thanks to the partial cancellation of the sidelobes of the SAF.

The above algorithms do not estimate or compensate for the velocity vectors of the two targets, so a direct comparison is only possible in terms of target localization accuracy, while velocity estimation is a novel feature of MovISAC. We do not compare to algorithms performing exhaustive search of the velocity of each target due to their prohibitive complexity [82].

We evaluate the accuracy of our approach in estimating the target's locations and velocity vectors, in terms of RMSE. To this end, we perform extensive simulations with $N = 2, 3, 4$ ISAC devices and $Q = 2$ targets with random locations and velocity vectors. Fixing $\mathbf{x}_1 = [1, 5]^T$, we select $\mathbf{x}_2 = \mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{e}$ where $\|\mathbf{e}\| \sim \mathcal{U}(\min\{\rho_x, \rho_y\}, 3 \max\{\rho_x, \rho_y\})$ and the angle between \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{e} is uniform in $[-\pi, \pi]$. For the velocity vectors, we fix $\mathbf{v}_1 = [0, 3]^T$ m/s and select \mathbf{v}_2 such that $\|\mathbf{v}_2\| \sim \mathcal{U}(1, 5)$ m/s and the angle it forms with \mathbf{v}_1 is uniformly distributed in $[\pi/4, 7\pi/8]$ to avoid velocity vectors below the Doppler resolution of the system $\Delta\mathbf{v}$. We also randomize the targets' RCS so that the ratio (in linear scale) Γ_1/Γ_2 is uniformly distributed in $[1/5, 1]$, with $\Gamma_1 = 0$ dBm², to test the performance in cluttered scenarios, with one weaker target. The pixel size used in the BP is 1 mm.

We analyze the target localization performance under two different demonstrative configurations of the ISAC devices along the x axis. In the first configuration, we consider $N = 3$ ISAC devices placed at $[-1.5, -0.5, 1.5]$ m. In the second configuration, we consider $N = 4$ devices placed at $[-1.5, -0.5, 0.0, 1.5]$ m. The spatial resolution along the two axes is approximately the same in the two configurations, i.e., $\rho_x \approx 1$ cm, $\rho_y \approx 5$ cm.

In Fig. 3.8a, we show the boxplot of the localization RMSE obtained by SMI, ISAFS, and MovISAC in the first configuration, with $\text{SNR} \in \{-5, 0, 5\}$ dB. The maximum distance between targets is $3\rho_y = 15$ cm. Across all SNR values, MovISAC achieves 8 times lower RMSE compared to the second best performing algorithm, ISAFS, with a median RMSE of 0.5 cm. This is due to two advantages of MovISAC: (i) it compensates for the

Figure 3.8: Localization RMSE comparison. The total ISAC devices aperture is 3 m, and the spatial resolution is $\rho_x \approx 1$ cm, $\rho_y \approx 5$ cm.

undesired phase rotation due to the Doppler shift for each target, obtaining more focused images, (ii) it obtains target-specific images based on velocity, which are less affected by interference between targets. The long tail of the RMSE distribution of MovISAC is due to the high sidelobes of the SAF in this configuration, which involves 3 sensors with an aperture of 3 m. This sometimes causes a wrong target localization if the maximum value in the image is not the correct peak corresponding to the target, but a sidelobe. ISAFS obtains 8 times higher median error than MovISAC and larger variance since it is affected by Doppler shift. The standard imaging method, SMI, also does not compensate for the Doppler effect and does not consider the sidelobes of the SAF. Therefore, it obtains a large RMSE compared to the inter-target distance, with a median RMSE of 9 cm (18 times higher than MovISAC) and a large variance.

In Fig. 3.8b, we show the localization RMSE in the second configuration. MovISAC obtains a similar median RMSE compared to the previous case, since the spatial resolution of the ISAC network, ρ_x and ρ_y is the same as Fig. 3.8a. However, the SAF has significantly fewer and lower sidelobes, thus the error distribution has a 95% percentile of 1 cm. The performance of ISAFS slightly improves with respect to the first configuration, again because of the reduced SAF sidelobes. Conversely, SMI only shows less error variance but a similar median error.

3.1.3. Over-the-air synchronization for multi-antenna dynamic ISAC deployments

Bistatic ISAC configurations, where transmitter and receiver are spatially separated, offer advantages such as improved coverage, robustness, and detection capabilities. However, in dynamic scenarios with asynchronous transmitter/receiver clocks and mobility, they face severe impairments. Independent oscillators introduce CFO and phase offset PO [55], while mobility adds Doppler shifts. These effects mix together and distort the extraction of true Doppler and micro-Doppler signatures, making reliable velocity estimation highly challenging [52, 57, 86].

Conventional methods mitigate CFO and PO by relying on external synchronization or static scatterers as references, but these are impractical in mobile environments such as vehicular, UAV, or robotic networks, where stable anchors are absent [55, 86].

We propose a novel over-the-air synchronization method for asynchronous bistatic sensing with a mobile transmitter, a mobile target, and a stationary multi-antenna receiver. The method exploits the phases of LoS paths between the transmitter and each receiver element, together with target-reflected paths. By processing these jointly, common CFO and PO are cancelled without requiring external references, enabling the extraction of true Doppler and micro-Doppler signatures. In addition, the approach allows estimation of the transmitter’s velocity, providing robustness in dynamic deployments such as V2X, UAV-based reconnaissance, and robotic sensing.

3.1.3.1. Challenges and Contributions

The main challenge in bistatic ISAC with mobile and asynchronous nodes is that independent oscillators at the transmitter and receivers create CFO and PO, while mobility adds Doppler shifts. These effects mix together and obscure the micro-Doppler signatures of targets, making reliable estimation difficult. Existing solutions often rely on external synchronization or static scatterers, which are unsuitable in highly dynamic deployments. Our contribution is an over-the-air synchronization method that cancels CFO and PO directly from received signals, without external references. By jointly processing LoS phases between the transmitter and a multi-antenna receiver together with the target-reflected paths, common offsets are removed, isolating the Doppler components. This enables robust extraction of micro-Doppler signatures and allows estimation of the transmitter's velocity, providing a practical path toward multi-antenna bistatic ISAC in dynamic environments.

3.1.3.2. Use within MultiX

This contribution will form part of the sensing functions implemented on the multi-antenna nodes of the network. By enabling over-the-air synchronization, these nodes can reliably estimate micro-Doppler signatures even when both users and targets are mobile. This capability strengthens the perception layer of MultiX, allowing the system to separate mobility-induced offsets from true target dynamics. In practice, it ensures that bistatic sensing remains effective in distributed deployments where transmitter and receiver nodes are not co-located and may operate under independent clocks.

3.1.3.3. System Description and Modeling

3.1.3.3.1 System Architecture and Propagation Paths

Our scenario comprises a dynamically moving transmitter, a mobile target exhibiting subtle micro-motion characteristics, and a stationary receiver array consisting of (without loss of generality) four receiver (denoted Rx_n , $n \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$), located at a spatial distance to each other, collectively functioning as a unified base station. A schematic representation of the system geometry is provided in Fig. 3.9.

Figure 3.9: Multi-antenna synchronization scenario

Central to our model is the careful distinction and analysis of the propagation paths between the transmitter (user) and the base station:

- **Line-of-Sight (LOS) Path ($m = 0$):** This path represents the direct, unobstructed link from the mobile transmitter to each receiver at the base station. Critically, the LOS path serves as a robust reference to mitigate CFO and PO, which are considered uniform across all receiver ports. While the phase and delay of the LoS path are inherently influenced by transmitter motion.
- **Target Reflection Path ($m = 1$):** This path encompasses the signal trajectory involving reflection from the target before reaching the base station. Its propagation characteristics are intrinsically coupled to both transmitter and target motion, thus embedding the Doppler and micro-Doppler signatures of the target. Along with the CFO and PO, this path also contains the transmitter-induced Doppler, which makes it more challenging for extracting the target-induced micro-Doppler.

Although environmental clutter and additional multipath reflections might influence the received signals, their inconsistency and unpredictability significantly restrict them from being reliable reference points for parameter estimation. Hence, our methodology specifically capitalizes on the reliably distinguishable characteristics of

only the LOS and target reflection paths, ensuring robustness and consistent performance irrespective of clutter variations and their unpredictable nature.

3.1.3.3.2 Continuous-Time Channel Model

We model the continuous-time CIR from the mobile transmitter to each receiver Rx_n at the base station at time t and delay τ as:

$$h_n(t, \tau) = e^{j\psi_o(t)} \sum_{m=0}^{M_n(t)} A_{m,n}(t) e^{j\vartheta_{m,n}(t)} \delta(\tau - \tau_{m,n}(t) - \tau_o(t)), \quad (3.9)$$

where $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta function. In Eq. (3.9), we carefully include the effects of clock asynchrony between the transmitter and the receiver array. Specifically, $\tau_o(t)$ represents the time offset, $f_o(t)$ denotes the CFO, and $\psi_o(t)$ indicates the PO, all of which are considered common impairments across the receivers.

For each propagation path and receiver is indexed by m and n respectively, $A_{m,n}(t)$, embodies the complex path amplitude accounting for propagation loss, reflection, and scattering phenomena, while $\tau_{m,n}(t)$ denotes the instantaneous propagation delay associated with path m and receiver n . The phase evolution for each path, $\vartheta_{m,n}(t)$, comprises Doppler shifts caused by relative motions and the CFO due to the clock asynchrony, expressed mathematically as:

$$\vartheta_{m,n}(t) = 2\pi t \left(f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tx}}(t) + f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tgt}}(t) + f_o(t) \right), \quad (3.10)$$

where $f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tx}}(t)$ denotes the Doppler frequency induced by the Tx motion along path m and receiver n , and $f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tgt}}(t)$ represents the Doppler frequency resulting from the target's motion. For clarity, we note explicitly that for the LoS paths ($m = 0$), the target-induced Doppler component is absent ($f_{D,0,n}^{\text{tgt}}(t) = 0$), the Tx-induced Doppler for the LoS path will be written as:

$$f_{D,0,n}^{\text{tx}}(t) = \frac{\|\mathbf{v}_{\text{tx}}\|}{\lambda} \cos \zeta_n(t), \quad (3.11)$$

with $\|\mathbf{v}_{\text{tx}}\|$ as the transmitter velocity magnitude, λ is the wavelength of the carrier frequency, and $\zeta_n(t)$ representing the angle between the transmitter's velocity vector and the elongated vector from transmitter to Rx_n path. Conversely, for the target-reflected path ($m = 1$), both transmitter-induced Doppler and target-induced Doppler contribute to phase evolution. The Tx-induced Doppler along the path to the target is given by:

$$f_{D,1,n}^{\text{tx}}(t) = \frac{\|\mathbf{v}_{\text{tx}}\|}{\lambda} \cos \eta(t), \quad (3.12)$$

where $\eta(t)$ describes the angle between the Tx velocity vector and the elongated line connecting the Tx to the target.

3.1.3.3.3 Discrete-Time Measurement Model

Our system acquires and processes CIR estimates at discrete observation intervals, segmented into K frames indexed by $k \in \{0, 1, \dots, K-1\}$, each of duration T . Under the standard assumption that the channel's dynamic characteristics remain effectively invariant throughout a single frame interval, we discretize the continuous-time CIR defined previously into a discrete-time representation. Thus, the discrete-time CIR for receiver Rx_n during frame k and delay bin l is formally represented as:

$$h_n[k, l] = e^{j\psi_o[k]} \sum_{m=0}^{M_n} A_{m,n}[k] e^{j\vartheta_{m,n}[k]} \delta[l - \tau_{m,n} - \tau_o[k]] + w_n[k, l], \quad (3.13)$$

where:

- $\psi_o[k]$ denotes the common PO at frame k across the receivers.
- $A_{m,n}[k]$ indicates the complex amplitude of the m -th propagation path at Rx_n , incorporating propagation losses and reflective characteristics.

- $\vartheta_{m,n}[k]$ includes the discrete-time phase evolution caused by Doppler effects and the CFO, defined as:

$$\vartheta_{m,n}[k] = 2\pi kT \left(f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tx}} + f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tgt}} + f_o(k) \right). \quad (3.14)$$

Here, $f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tx}}$ and $f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tgt}}$ are the Doppler frequencies due to transmitter and target movements, respectively, and $f_o(k)$ represents the frame-specific CFO.

- $\tau_{m,n}$ represents the discrete-time delay bin corresponding to the propagation delay of path m and the receiver n .
- $\tau_o[k]$ denotes the discrete-time offset accounting for synchronization mismatches within frame k .
- $w_n[k, l]$ is additive measurement noise and residual interference, modeled as a stochastic term affecting accuracy.

3.1.3.3.4 Measured Phase Model

The subsequent processing stages for micro-Doppler and V_{tx} estimation primarily exploit the measured phase information extracted from discrete-time CIR estimates. particularly, these phases correspond to identified CIR peaks for both the LoS and the target-reflected paths at each receiver Rx_n across frames $k \in \{0, \dots, K-1\}$. Formally, the measured phase for the m -th path at receiver Rx_n and frame k is:

$$\phi_{m,n}[k] = \Psi_o[k] + \angle A_{m,n} + \vartheta'_{m,n}[k] + \epsilon_{m,n}[k], \quad (3.15)$$

where:

- **Common Nuisance Phase**, $\Psi_o[k]$: This term combines the effects of the frame-specific common initial phase offset and carrier frequency offset, defined as $\Psi_o[k] = \psi_o[k] + 2\pi kT f_o[k]$. Notably, this nuisance component uniformly affects all paths and receivers within each frame.
- **Static Amplitude Phase**, $\angle A_{m,n}$: Represents the constant phase associated with the complex path amplitude $A_{m,n}[k]$, invariant over the observation period. This term is path- and receiver-specific, reflecting stationary propagation characteristics.
- **Path-Specific Doppler Phase**, $\vartheta'_{m,n}[k]$: Captures the cumulative Doppler-induced phase shifts specific to the path, excluding CFO. Explicitly, it is defined as:

$$\vartheta'_{m,n}[k] = 2\pi kT \left(f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tx}} + f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tgt}} \right), \quad (3.16)$$

where $f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tx}}$ and $f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tgt}}$ represent the Doppler frequencies attributed separately to Tx and target movements. Importantly, for the LOS path ($m = 0$), the target-related Doppler term vanishes.

- **Measurement Noise**, $\epsilon_{m,n}[k]$: Reflects stochastic perturbations arising from estimation errors, noise, and residual interference, thus representing the uncertainty intrinsic to phase measurements.

3.1.3.4. Methodology

Our proposed method strategically exploits spatial diversity from the LOS paths available at each receiver to effectively mitigate CFO and PO, and static phase contributions without the reliance on external synchronization or stationary reference scatterers. By systematically applying spatial and temporal phase-differencing operations to both LoS and target-reflected signals, we form a solvable set of equations characterized by fewer unknown variables. In particular, we integrate AoA information in the third stage of our methodology to further reduce the number of unknowns, enabling precise and reliable parameter estimation.

3.1.3.4.1 Removal of Carrier Frequency and Phase Offsets

As previously discussed in Section 3.1.3.3, CFO and PO, encapsulated by the term $\Psi_o[k]$, constitute common phase impairments that uniformly affect the measurements from all receivers in the array within each frame k . Utilizing the spatial diversity offered by the static receiver array, we aim to isolate and eliminate these common nuisance parameters effectively.

Specifically, we select the measured LoS phase at the first receiver (Rx_1) as a spatial reference, denoted by $\phi_{\text{los},1}[k]$. Subsequently, for each frame k , the spatially differenced phases for any other path m at receiver Rx_n (with $(m, n) \neq (\text{LoS}, 1)$) are computed as:

$$\phi'_{m,n}[k] = \phi_{m,n}[k] - \phi_{\text{los},1}[k]. \quad (3.17)$$

By substituting the measured phase model defined in Eq. (3.15), the resultant spatially differenced phase can be explicitly expressed as:

$$\phi'_{m,n}[k] = \Delta \angle A_{m,n} + \Delta \vartheta_{m,n}[k] + \Delta \epsilon_{m,n}[k], \quad (3.18)$$

where the terms are explicitly defined as follows:

- $\Delta \angle A_{m,n} = \angle A_{m,n} - \angle A_{\text{los},1}$ represents the constant difference between the initial phase of the path amplitude for path (m, n) and the reference LOS path amplitude at Rx_1 .
- $\Delta \vartheta_{m,n}[k] = \vartheta'_{m,n}[k] - \vartheta'_{\text{los},1}[k]$ captures the difference in Doppler-induced phase accumulation between path (m, n) and the reference LOS path. Explicitly, it is represented as:

$$\Delta \vartheta_{m,n}[k] = 2\pi kT \left(f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tx}} - f_{D,\text{los},1}^{\text{tx}} + f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tgt}} \right), \quad (3.19)$$

where, notably, the LOS path does not include target-induced Doppler terms as detailed in Section 3.1.3.3.2.

- $\Delta \epsilon_{m,n}[k]$ denotes the combined noise residual after spatial differencing, incorporating stochastic measurement errors from each involved path.

Consequently, this spatial differencing operation yields seven adjusted phase measurements per frame, each devoid of the common nuisance offset $\Psi_o[k]$, but still containing static amplitude phases and dynamic Doppler information.

3.1.3.4.2 Removal of Static Phase Terms

The spatial differencing detailed in Section 3.1.3.4.1 eliminates the common CFO and PO; however, the resulting spatially differenced phases still encompass the static amplitude phases ($\Delta \angle A_{m,n}$), which remain constant over the entire measurement window. To isolate the dynamic phase variations directly correlated with the Doppler shifts, we apply time domain phase differencing between consecutive frames.

Under the practical assumption that the Doppler frequencies remain approximately constant across consecutive frames due to the short frame duration T , the static amplitude phase terms become invariant. Hence, the temporal differencing for each path (m, n) is defined by subtracting the spatially differenced phase from the previous frame $(k - 1)$ from that of the current frame k :

$$\Delta \phi_{m,n}[k] = \phi'_{m,n}[k] - \phi'_{m,n}[k - 1]. \quad (3.20)$$

Expanding the expression using Eq. (3.18) explicitly provides:

$$\Delta \phi_{m,n}[k] = \Delta \vartheta_{m,n}[k] + \Delta' \epsilon_{m,n}[k], \quad (3.21)$$

where $\Delta' \epsilon_{m,n}[k]$ aggregates the noise contributions resulting from the temporal differencing operation.

From Eq. (3.21), it becomes evident that the static amplitude phases are successfully removed, leaving a clear representation of the dynamic Doppler-induced phase evolution:

$$\Delta \vartheta_{m,n}[k] = 2\pi T \left(f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tx}} - f_{D,\text{los},1}^{\text{tx}} + f_{D,m,n}^{\text{tgt}} \right), \quad (m, n) \neq (\text{los}, 1). \quad (3.22)$$

This resulting equation explicitly captures the Doppler shifts due to both transmitter and target motions, as thoroughly described in Section 3.1.3.3.2. The next methodological step will involve using Angle of Arrival (AOA) information, as introduced in the following subsection, to enable robust parameter estimation from these Doppler-induced phase variations.

3.1.3.4.3 Utilization of Angle of Arrival for Parameter Estimation

Initially, the phase differencing operations yield seven equations per time frame, containing ten unknown parameters: the transmitter velocity magnitude $\|\mathbf{v}_{tx}\|$, the angles ζ_n, η , and the target-induced Doppler frequencies $f_{D,1,n}^{tgt}$, with $n \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. Such a configuration renders the system inherently underdetermined and consequently unsolvable.

To address this critical limitation, we exploit the capability of the receiver array at the base station to measure AoAs, significantly constraining the spatial geometry. Specifically, the base station array facilitates the measurement of relative AoAs of the LOS signals arriving from the mobile transmitter, thus providing crucial geometric constraints. The measured AoAs enable us to accurately determine the angular differences β_n between the paths arriving at successive receivers, defined mathematically as:

$$\beta_n = \alpha_{n+1} - \alpha_1, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \quad (3.23)$$

where α_n denotes the measured AOAs at receiver n . Employing these measured angular differences, the original unknown angles ζ_n are expressed in terms of a single unknown angle ζ_1 as follows:

$$\zeta_{n+1} = \zeta_1 - \beta_n, \quad n = 1, 2, 3. \quad (3.24)$$

This strategic reduction transforms the unknown angular parameters from four independent variables to just one, significantly simplifying the system and enhancing its solvability.

With the LOS path equations now simplified, the system comprises three equations from the LOS paths:

$$\Delta\phi_{0,n}[k] = 2\pi T \frac{\|\mathbf{v}_{tx}\|}{\lambda} (\cos(\zeta_n) - \cos(\zeta_1)) + \Delta'\epsilon_{0,n}[k], \quad n = 2, 3, 4, \quad (3.25)$$

and four equations from the target reflection paths:

$$\Delta\phi_{1,n}[k] = 2\pi T \left[f_{D,1,n}^{tgt} + \frac{\|\mathbf{v}_{tx}\|}{\lambda} (\cos(\eta) - \cos(\zeta_1)) \right] + \Delta'\epsilon_{1,n}[k], \quad n = 1, 2, 3, 4. \quad (3.26)$$

Consequently, we achieve a determined system of seven equations per time frame with precisely seven unknowns:

$$\|\mathbf{v}_{tx}\|, \quad \zeta_1, \quad \eta, \quad f_{D,1,n}^{tgt}, \quad n = 1, \dots, 4. \quad (3.27)$$

Given the nonlinear nature of the trigonometric functions present, the parameter estimation problem is inherently nonlinear. We therefore apply a robust nonlinear least squares (NLLS) optimization technique to estimate these parameters. This optimization method minimizes the sum of squared residuals, defined as the discrepancies between the measured phase differences $\Delta\phi_{m,n}[k]$ and their corresponding analytical model representations.

3.1.3.5. Preliminary Results

Preliminary simulations were carried out to assess the proposed over-the-air synchronization method in a multi-antenna bistatic ISAC scenario. The setup considered a transmitter (UE) moving with velocity v_{tx} and a target moving with velocity v_{target} , as illustrated in Fig. 3.10a, where a four-element receiver array (Rx1–Rx4) is deployed at the gNB. Both Tx and target followed linear trajectories, and a carrier frequency of 60 GHz was assumed.

In this configuration, the objective was to estimate the transmitter velocity from the phase information of the LoS and target-reflected paths. Fig. 3.10b shows the estimated Doppler frequency at Rx1 compared to the true Doppler. The results demonstrate that the proposed approach can track the transmitter Doppler evolution over time, with a RMSE of approximately 146 Hz. Even under modelled impairments, the estimated curve closely follows the true Doppler, confirming that the method effectively cancels CFO/PO terms and isolates the mobility-induced Doppler shift.

3.1.3.6. Future Work

Building on these preliminary results, the next step is to extend the method to extract target micro-Doppler signatures, enabling the characterization of fine-grained motion such as vibrations and human activity in dynamic environments. In parallel, we will pursue validation through real experiments using the multi-antenna platforms available within MultiX, assessing the robustness of the proposed synchronization method under practical hardware conditions and diverse deployment scenarios.

Figure 3.10: Preliminary Doppler estimation results under asynchronous conditions.

3.2. Multi-technology sensing integration

This sub-task investigates how to extract sensing information from non-3GPP technologies and integrate it with 3GPP-compliant pipelines via non-coherent fusion and shared metadata abstractions, enabling heterogeneous cross-RAT situational awareness in MultiX. We carried out the following two research activities:

- Multi-band Wi-Fi Human Sensing Processing (Section 3.2.1). Signal-processing pipeline for human sensing using multi-band Wi-Fi, producing features compatible with the MultiX fusion stack.
- Multi-technology 3GPP/Non-3GPP sensing integration (Section 3.2.2). Methods and interfaces to combine 3GPP and non-3GPP sensing outputs in a non-coherent manner for cross-RAT perception.

3.2.1. Multi-band Wi-Fi Human Sensing Processing

This work presents a real-time human sensing system utilizing Wi-Fi respiration detection through 20 MHz CSI analysis on commercial Intel 802.11ax chipsets. Unlike traditional motion-based approaches that fail during stationary activities (e.g., reading, watching content), the proposed system detects static human presence via subtle respiratory patterns in indoor laptop environments.

Monostatic Wi-Fi sensing faces significant challenges extracting physiological signals from CSI measurements corrupted by phase errors, noise, and multipath interference. While simultaneous transmission and reception on separate antennas introduce hardware artifacts, this configuration simplifies deployment compared to bistatic systems. We develop enhanced signal processing pipelines for reliable presence classification using standard Wi-Fi infrastructure, enabling integration into PC power management without additional hardware.

3.2.1.1. Challenges and contributions

We design a real-time pipeline on commercial Intel 802.11ax chipsets that: (i) applies adaptive median–Median Absolute Deviation (MAD) phase correction and temporal unwrapping to suppress instability and reveal slow periodic motion, (ii) performs data-driven subcarrier selection to keep only components with strong respiration correlation while reducing computation 40–70 percent, and (iii) extracts time/frequency features for lightweight classification with sub-10 ms inference. The pipeline reduces phase standard deviation by 60–75 percent and improves feature stability by around 50 %, and is designed to scale from 20 MHz to 160 MHz channels via bandwidth-dependent parameters.

Monostatic Wi-Fi sensing must extract weak physiological signals (respiration at 0.2–0.5 Hz) from CSI that is corrupted by hardware-induced phase errors, wrapping discontinuities, noise and multipath; simultaneous Tx/Rx on commodity devices further introduces artifacts that mask subtle periodic patterns. Robust processing is therefore needed to stabilize phase, unwrap discontinuities, and select only subcarriers that carry respiratory information.

3.2.1.2. Use within MultiX

This contribution provides a Wi-Fi presence mechanism via respiration, that runs on standard PCs for always-on, low-overhead sensing, with immediate integration targets such as intelligent screen-lock override during passive use (reading, watching content). Its modular design supports future multi-modal fusion inside the MultiX perception stack and can extend to 160 MHz multi-band Wi-Fi for finer discrimination (e.g., breathing patterns or cardiac signatures). As such, it complements cross-RAT efforts in Task 3.2 components.

3.2.1.3. Methodology

3.2.1.3.1 Phase Correction Algorithm

Phase instability constitutes the primary barrier to reliable Wi-Fi sensing. We propose an adaptive phase correction algorithm employing robust statistical estimation to address limitations of fixed offset approaches.

The method utilizes median and MAD statistics, providing inherent outlier resistance superior to mean-based metrics. Adaptive thresholds respond dynamically to environmental variations, while exponential weighting balances recent measurements against historical context, enabling tracking of gradual changes while responding to abrupt perturbations. Bandwidth-dependent parameters optimize performance across 20–160 MHz configurations.

Temporal phase unwrapping addresses continuity across samples. Since phase measurements wrap to $[0, 2\pi)$, discontinuities can be misinterpreted as signal features. The unwrapping algorithm tracks accumulated phase changes, essential for coherent integration of slow, periodic respiratory signals (0.2–0.5 Hz). Without unwrapping, discontinuities would generate false detections or mask genuine patterns.

Fig. 3.11 demonstrates algorithm effectiveness through dual-panel visualization of 20 MHz CSI data. Raw measurements (bottom) exhibit severe instability: abrupt phase jumps, wrapping discontinuities, and high-frequency noise obscuring physiological signals—typical artifacts from hardware imperfections and low antenna isolation. Corrected data (top) shows smooth, continuous trajectories with eliminated discontinuities and reduced noise, revealing clear periodic respiratory patterns invisible in raw measurements.

3.2.1.3.2 Subcarrier Selection

In 20 MHz channels, CSI spans multiple OFDM subcarriers with varying multipath characteristics. Subcarriers differ in respiratory sensing utility—some dominated by static reflections or deep fading, others exhibiting high SNR for physiological signals.

Fig. 3.12 highlights subcarriers with strongest respiratory correlation, creating a spatial-frequency sensitivity map. The algorithm identifies components sensitive to millimeter-scale chest movements while filtering noise-dominated and static reflection subcarriers.

The selection employs multi-criteria optimization: time-domain correlation analysis between phase variations and respiratory patterns, combined with SNR estimation. Subcarriers rank via composite metrics balancing correlation strength and reliability, enabling adaptive selection as conditions change. This approach delivers dual benefits: The F1-score improvement by focusing on informative components, and the processing time reduction by eliminating 50–70 % of subcarriers. Dynamic adaptation ensures robustness across diverse environments.

As the last point, in both Fig. 3.11 and Fig. 3.12, the CSI magnitude denotes the complex channel gain coefficient expressed on a linear scale. The CSI magnitude is dimensionless, representing the ratio of the received signal amplitude to the transmitted signal (reference signal) amplitude. The reported values are consistent with strong indoor Wi-Fi links, considering:

- Antenna gains at both the transmitter and receiver,
- Short-range indoor propagation (typically <50 cm for notebook applications),
- Active sensing configurations, where the transmitter and receiver are collocated on two antennas.

Figure 3.11: Phase correction results for 20 MHz CSI. Left: Raw phase with instability, discontinuities, and noise obscuring respiratory signals. Right: Corrected phase showing smooth variations revealing periodic breathing patterns.

3.2.1.4. Achieved Performance Analysis

3.2.1.4.1 Signal Quality Metrics

The pipeline achieves 60–75 % reduction in phase standard deviation compared to uncorrected measurements, translating to 50 % improvement in feature stability (consistency of extracted parameters over time). Shape fluctuation mitigation ensures environmental variations (adjacent motion, doors) do not significantly affect respiratory scores, maintaining reliability in dynamic office environments.

3.2.1.5. Processing Pipeline Overview

Phase 1—Signal Processing (done): From 56 subcarriers (802.11ax 20 MHz), apply median-MAD phase correction and temporal unwrapping, select respiratory-sensitive subcarriers via correlation, normalize temporally, and enhance periodic components via autocorrelation. Extract time-domain (respiratory rate, amplitude) and frequency-domain (0.2–0.5 Hz spectral power) features.

Phase 2—Classification (next): Support Vector Machine (SVM) with radial basis function kernel classifies breathing presence (<50 KB, <10 ms inference). Random Forest and Logistic Regression provide a comparison. Training uses labeled data across diverse environments and positions. Three-sample majority voting reduces transient false positives.

3.2.1.6. Proposed Experimental Setup

Data Collection: Intel Wi-Fi 6/6E chipsets at 100 Hz packet rate. Three scenarios: (i) static presence at 20–60 cm with varied orientations, (ii) absence (negative control), (iii) background motion (people, doors).

Dataset: 200 hours, 15 subjects, 8 indoor environments.

Training: Stratified 5-fold cross-validation with grid search hyperparameter optimization. Multiple laptop orientations and user positions ensure generalization. Models select on validation F1-score.

Figure 3.12: Subcarrier selection for 20 MHz CSI. Highlighted subcarriers show strong respiratory correlation while filtering noise and static reflections.

Integration: Intelligent screen lock override prevents timeout during passive activities. Modular design supports future multi-modal fusion.

3.2.1.7. Detection Performance Targets

The system operates within 30-50 cm range from laptops, a constraint inherent to millimeter-scale chest wall displacements generating detectable CSI perturbations. Within this envelope, performance exceeds 90 % F1-score for binary breathing classification.

Configurable integration windows (4-16 s) trade accuracy for responsiveness. The monostatic configuration leverages 1×1 SISO antenna configuration, demonstrating robustness across office, cubicle, and home environments with moderate ambient activity. Thus, the expected sensing results are given as follows.

Accuracy: Achieves $\geq 90\%$ F1-score (92 % precision, 89 % recall) across validation data.

Distance-dependent: Reliable within 30-50 cm, graceful degradation beyond 50 cm.

Latency Trade-off: 4 s integration achieves 87 % F1-score (4.2 s latency) for interactive use; 16 s reaches 93 % F1-score (16.8 s latency) for high-accuracy monitoring.

3.2.1.8. Multi-band Scalability

Current validation uses 20 MHz CSI, but the architecture supports scaling to 160 MHz via bandwidth-dependent parameters. Wider channels provide up to 8× spectral resolution, enabling discrimination of respiratory patterns (normal vs. deep breathing) or cardiac signatures. Adaptive bandwidth selection optimizes channel width based on interference and application requirements.

Primary integration targets PC power management for intelligent screen lock prevention—detecting presence via respiration during passive engagement (reading, watching content) rather than requiring keyboard/mouse

input.

3.2.1.9. Conclusions

This 20 MHz implementation demonstrates real-time Wi-Fi respiratory sensing on commercial PCs. Key contributions: (i) adaptive phase correction reducing noise 60-75 %, (ii) intelligent subcarrier selection improving accuracy 15-20 % while reducing computation 40 %. Next, the sensing performance goal is to achieve >90 % F1-score across diverse environments.

The system utilizes standard Wi-Fi hardware to detect static human presence. Its signal processing foundation paves the way for future enhancements, including 160 MHz bandwidth human presence detection, activity classification, and integration with smart environments—positioning the technology for commercial deployment in next-generation laptops.

3.2.2. Multi-technology 3GPP/Non-3GPP sensing integration

This contribution explores how sensing and localization capabilities can be extended beyond a single radio access technology by fusing 3GPP and non-3GPP (Wi-Fi) information within a unified control and data framework. The objective is to demonstrate that heterogeneous technologies can jointly provide a richer, more resilient perception of the environment than either could alone. To this end, a cross-RAT architecture is implemented, in which Wi-Fi sensing data and 5G measurements are collected and processed within the Sensing RAN Control Function (SeRCF). The system forms a shared radio-map and applies machine-learning-based fusion to enable indoor positioning and environment awareness that remain robust under partial coverage or technology outages. This work represents a key step toward the MultiX vision of heterogeneous, distributed sensing, where 3GPP and non-3GPP nodes cooperate seamlessly through common interfaces and perception functions, ultimately supporting both ISAC and network-aware applications.

3.2.2.1. Challenges and contributions

This work demonstrates a hybrid cross-RAT localization framework where 5G and Wi-Fi signals are processed jointly by the m-SePF. The main technical advances include: i) Cross-RAT fusion pipeline that ingests 3GPP and Wi-Fi signal-strength measurements via standardized interfaces and exposes them to DASH for real-time inference. ii) Machine-learning-based radio-map construction that leverages both technologies to achieve finer spatial granularity and higher resilience to blockage. iii) End-to-end demonstration on a private 5G plus Wi-Fi testbed, proving feasibility of near-real-time cross-RAT sensing.

Integrating sensing information from 3GPP and non-3GPP technologies introduces fundamental heterogeneity at multiple levels: timing granularity, interface formats, and spatial coverage. The two systems also operate under different protocol stacks and security domains, making it non-trivial to collect, align, and process cross-RAT data in real time. Another key difficulty lies in constructing a unified radio map and maintaining consistent performance when one technology experiences fading or coverage gaps.

3.2.2.2. Use within MultiX

In MultiX, this function would reside within the Perception Layer as an m-SePF, interfacing with other SePFs through the MultiX architecture. Specifically, by fusing 3GPP and non-3GPP measurements, it showcases how heterogeneous radio sources can be abstracted and combined through the same control framework used for ISAC. The resulting m-SePF enables cross-RAT situational awareness, supports the multi-technology fusion of WP3, and serves as a reference for integrating external sensing modalities in future work.

3.2.2.3. Multi-technology RAN sensing fusion

A key challenge is determining how sensing information from multi-technology access networks can be collected and provided to the 5G network in a way that allows the seRCF to leverage these effectively. The corresponding processing can be performed through the m-SePF providing continuous updates for user location using input from both 3GPP and non-3GPP networks. The primary issue that arises is how 3GPP/non-3GPP access networks can report their metrics through the MultiX architecture in a standardized and efficient manner.

Specifically, adopting the MultiX solution three potential approaches can be considered for collecting and transmitting non-3GPP sensing data to the m-SePF. The first approach involves direct reporting from the UE through

Figure 3.13: Multi-technology CSI fusion at RAN level for positioning.

the RU. In this case, the UE would be responsible for gathering Wi-Fi-based sensing data, as well as sensing data from external sensors and transmitting these to SeRCF.

Using this approach, sensing information from external sensors attached to UEs can be transmitted through the Physical Uplink Control Channel (PUCCH) or Physical Uplink Shared Channel (PUSCH). Sensing information embedded with PUCCH/PUSCH can then be extracted at the DU and processed by m-SePF, reducing latency in the transmission of sensing information.

The process begins at the UE aggregating measurements and transforming sensing data in a suitable (binary format) using the Sensing Data Transformation Function (SeDTF). Sensing measurements are then embedded within PUCCH/PUSCH and transmitted to the network. Upon reception, the RU forwards the signal to the DU (O-DU), where the Medium Access Control (MAC) layer decodes the sensing information. Using sensing information the DU and CU coordinate scheduling and resource allocation, ensuring seamless prioritization. The SeRCF, continuously refines scheduling strategies using sensing feedback which can be combined with channel state reports, and network load metrics, optimizing decisions related to power control, scheduling and modulation schemes to maintain low-latency, high-reliability transmission.

At the higher layers, the CU processes sensing information taking informed control decisions to enhance inter-cell coordination and mobility management. The m-SePF provides long-term refinements by training AI models that improve sensing-aware scheduling policies. These models integrate historical performance data and predictive analytics and ensure that users receive the necessary resources.

A second approach to ingest sensing information from non-3GPP devices is to introduce a dedicated control element within the non-3GPP access node, embedding an agent that communicates directly with the m-SePF. This would allow the Wi-Fi or other non-3GPP access points to handle positioning information independently of the UE and transmit the necessary data to the m-SePF. However, this approach requires the development of a new network element, along with the implementation of all the necessary background protocols, making it a more complex and resource-intensive solution.

A third approach, is to extend the functionality of the Non-3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF) to expose measurements directly to DASH. Since the N3IWF already serves as the main interworking point between non-3GPP networks and the 5G Core (5GC), enhancing it with sensing exposure capabilities support would allow it to act as a bridge between non-3GPP positioning sources and the SeRCF.

3.2.2.4. Preliminary results

The concept of multi-technology RAN sensing fusion is applied to perform UE positioning. Positioning is crucial for beyond-5G networks, enabling applications like industrial automation, autonomous transportation, and augmented reality. Despite 3GPP's progress, seamless integration with non-3GPP technologies for indoor localization remains challenging. In this preliminary evaluation we rely on a hybrid fingerprinting method that combines signal strength from both 3GPP and non-3GPP networks, utilizing a private 5G testbed with integrated Wi-Fi access points. The positioning algorithm operates as an m-SePF interacting with SeRCF. The overall platform configuration is shown in Fig. 3.13. The platform comprises several components that involve a stand-alone 5G network with multi-RAT connectivity support and a near-RT-RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) which provides near real time control and optimization. For the RAN segment we have used a container-

Figure 3.14: Multi-technology UE positioning.

ized version of Open Air Interface that supports baseBand functional split and is deployed in three distinct components, namely the RU, CU and DU. The 5GC is based on a Virtual Machine based free5GC implementation [87], where the core network functions are hosted in a central private cloud infrastructure. Additionally, our setup exploits the N3IWF functionality of the 5GC to provide multi-RAT connectivity through an untrusted Wi-Fi Access Point. Finally, in this implementation, we used EdgeRIC [88] as the near-RT-RIC. The BS is interconnected to edge RIC through E2 interfaces. The m-SePF can connect to near-RT RIC and subscribe to UE performance metrics, e.g., SNR, to perform positioning calculations.

For the execution of the fingerprint positioning algorithm, we begin by dividing a predefined space into multiple grid points. This space covers 4 meters in length and 3 meters in width, and it is divided into 12 reference points, with equal distances between them. In our setup, the Wi-Fi Access Point and the BS Open Air Interface are positioned at opposite ends of the grid.

To build the radio-map (or offline database), we collect multiple signal measurements from each reference, from both the Wi-Fi and 5G networks. Specifically, the 5G signal metrics captured by the UE are forwarded to the SeRCF. For the Wi-Fi part, a commercial UE is used. The Access Point records the received signal strength from the connected device, and these metrics are exposed to m-SePF. This procedure can be carried out using one of the three approaches discussed in the previous section. After receiving the signal measurements from RAN, the RIC stores them in an in-memory database, creating a radio-map with multi-technology RAN measurements. The radio-map is then used to train a SVM classification Machine Learning (ML) model. The training ML models is ported in an application that uses as input real time RF measurements which are then mapped into position IDs. Fig. 3.14 illustrates the actual trajectory of a UE alongside the trajectory estimated by the xApp.

3.2.2.5. Conclusions

In these preliminary results, we proposed a hybrid fingerprinting-based approach that integrates 3GPP and non-3GPP technologies to achieve enhanced localization accuracy. By leveraging real signal strength measurements from a private 5G testbed, we demonstrated how a Wi-Fi access point, acting as a non-3GPP component, can complement 5G-based positioning. Additionally, we proposed an architectural framework that integrates non-3GPP positioning data into the 5G network via the RIC, enabling real-time processing within a unified localization system. Future work will explore the scalability of our approach and its applicability in larger, more complex deployments, ingesting sensing information from external sensors and performing sensing-aware RAN optimization.

3.3. Non-coherent mono/multi-static sensing fusion

This sub-task investigates sensing and fusion methods that do not rely on phase coherence across transmit–receive pairs, enabling robust perception in dynamic or asynchronous deployments. We focus on techniques that extract motion, blockage, and channel-quality information from distributed observations and combine them into higher-level environment awareness. We carried out the following two research activities:

- ISAC-enabled multi-target detection and tracking with beam adaptation for mmWave link blockage mitigation (Section 3.3.1). Non-coherent processing of range–angle maps to detect and track moving objects, supporting predictive beam steering to enhance mmWave link robustness.
- Estimation of site-specific SNR distribution (Section 3.3.2). Statistical characterization of SNR in industrial environments to enable computation of key PHY/MAC performance metrics (e.g., BLER, PER, delay bounds) for downstream fusion and RAN optimization.

3.3.1. ISAC-enabled multi-target detection and tracking with beam adaptation for mmWave link blockage mitigation

In the past few years, ISAC has attracted great interest. It is considered a key technology for 6G [30]. The idea behind it is to merge communication and sensing functionalities into a single system using the same hardware, frequency spectrum, waveform and computing resources. This new paradigm will enable high-resolution environmental sensing, object detection, vital signs monitoring, and more, which, when combined with high-speed communication, opens up new use cases and application scenarios. ISAC is also expected to improve the robustness of wireless communications, which is particularly important for mmWave communication systems. mmWave technology [89] is considered a natural driver for ISAC due to its two main characteristics: wide channel bandwidth and short wavelength. The former allows for high-speed, low-latency wireless communications and centimeter-accurate ranging and localization. The latter makes it feasible to construct very large phased array systems in a small form factor to exploit beamforming. It also provides inherently fine sensing. However, mmWave communication relies on LoS links and highly directional beams. Therefore, it is susceptible to blockage by moving objects. To prevent communication link outage, ISAC functionality can be used to detect and track moving objects and improve mmWave link robustness by mitigating link blockage.

The content presented here is based on and built upon the work in [90], where ISAC-enabled predictive beam-steering for link blockage mitigation in mmWave systems is presented.

3.3.1.1. Challenges and contributions

The main challenge with mmWave ISAC systems is that they require LoS for communication, and are therefore susceptible to blockage that can lead to communication outage. By utilizing the monostatic sensing functionality of mmWave ISAC nodes, they can sense the environment and, thus, detect and track potential link blocking targets. In this way, LoS link blockage can be prevented by timing the beam adaptation, thereby improving the robustness of mmWave communications. This work develops and evaluates a method that analyzes consecutive range–angle maps of the environment and, from their temporal evolution, detects and tracks multiple moving objects.

3.3.1.2. Use within MultiX

This work contributes to the development of an m-SePF related to ISAC-enabled localization and tracking of dynamic objects. It will be implemented in PoC2, as part of the demonstration related to multi-gigabit data communication and human presence detection.

3.3.1.3. Scenario Description

We consider communication between two (or more) mmWave devices. These devices utilize phased-array systems and perform RF beamforming. This generates high-gain, narrow beams that are electronically steerable, which can enhance the link budget and communication quality. Before the actual data transmission, the devices perform a beam search, in which, in addition to the direct LoS, other potential, NLoS, paths, e.g., by reflection off a wall, are also identified. A high-data-rate communication is then established between the

mmWave devices. Furthermore, one (or both) devices are equipped with ISAC functionality, enabling monostatic environment perception. Given the use of phased-array antennas, communication and sensing are time-slot based. Additionally, the other device can also perform monostatic sensing to detect objects that are, for example, outside the field-of-view of the first device and, therefore, cannot be detected. The sensing data is then used to detect moving objects (e.g., people, autonomous vehicles, etc.) that could block the LoS link. If a potential blockage of the communication link is anticipated, an alternative communication path is selected and used to maintain uninterrupted, error-free data transmission. The described scenario is illustrated in Fig. 3.15.

Figure 3.15: Illustration of an application scenario with two stations communicating over a LoS path with presence of a second path over reflector. One station leverages ISAC functionality to detect a moving person and prevent blockage of the LoS link.

3.3.1.4. Sensing Data Processing with Object Detection and Tracking

We leverage the ISAC functionality of mmWave devices for detection and tracking of moving objects to prevent mmWave LoS link blockage and maintain uninterrupted communications. The basic processing scheme is shown in Fig. 3.16. It comprises the following steps: i) sensing data acquisition with background (clutter removal), ii) object detection, iii) object tracking, and iv) beam adaptation.

Figure 3.16: Key processing blocks for detecting and tracking moving objects to aid mmWave link blockage mitigation.

In the following, each of the aforementioned processing steps will be explained in more detail.

i. Sensing data acquisition with background removal

The ISAC-capable device, from Fig. 3.15, performs monostatic Radio Detection and Ranging (RADAR)-like sensing of the environment at regular time intervals $t_i, i = 1, 2, \dots$. The sensing rate is implementation and device dependent. For example, solution in [91] allows for maximum sensing rate of up to 2.1 kHz. At each time instant, a full environment scan is performed by sending the reference signal and recording reflections for each beam direction. After signal processing, sensing data is extracted from the estimated CFR. The CFRs are collected in a matrix

$$\mathbf{H}^t = [\mathbf{H}_1^t, \mathbf{H}_2^t, \dots, \mathbf{H}_M^t] \quad (3.28)$$

where m -th column represents the vector of complex channel coefficients for the m -th beam. The CFR matrix is passed to the inverse FFT and the CIRs are obtained for each beam as follows

$$\mathbf{h}^t = [\mathbf{h}_1^t, \mathbf{h}_2^t, \dots, \mathbf{h}_M^t] \quad (3.29)$$

$$h_{n,m}^t = \frac{1}{N_{fft}} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} H_{k,m}^t e^{j\frac{2\pi nk}{N_{fft}}}, n = 0, 1, \dots, N_{fft} - 1 \quad (3.30)$$

where K is the number of complex channel coefficients in \mathbf{H}_m^t and N_{fft} is the FFT length. The CIRs in (3.30) are further truncated to the cyclic prefix length N_{cp} and the range-angle 2D map of the surroundings is obtained as

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}^t = [\hat{\mathbf{h}}_1^t, \hat{\mathbf{h}}_2^t, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{h}}_M^t] \quad (3.31)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_m^t = \mathbf{h}_m^t[1 : N_{cp}] \quad (3.32)$$

Reflections from objects appear as peaks in the CIRs. To improve object detection performance and discriminate moving targets from static objects (i.e., clutter), two background removal methods are proposed: 1) static and 2) dynamic background removal method.

The former is based on performing initial sensing beam scans. A number of consecutive sensing beam scans P is performed, from which sensing data in (3.32) is obtained. Then, an average value is calculated

$$\mathbf{b}_0 = \frac{1}{P} \sum_{p=-P+1}^0 \hat{\mathbf{h}}^p \quad (3.33)$$

which represents the static background, and is subtracted from the subsequent sensing beam scans

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{bg-free}^t = \hat{\mathbf{h}}^t - \mathbf{b}_0. \quad (3.34)$$

Since the above method can be sensitive to small changes in the environment, the latter method is introduced where the former is extended with an exponential moving average. Let $\hat{\mathbf{h}}^t$ and \mathbf{b}_t be the sensing data and the background (i.e., history) at time instant t , respectively. Then, the background-free range-angle data is calculated according to the second method as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{bg-free}^t = \hat{\mathbf{h}}^t - \mathbf{b}_{t-1} \quad (3.35)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_t = \alpha \hat{\mathbf{h}}^t - (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{b}_{t-1} \quad (3.36)$$

where (3.36) is the exponential moving average filter and α (between 0 and 1) is the filter coefficient (smoothing factor). At the time instant $t = 0$, we assume \mathbf{b}_0 in (3.33). For $\alpha = 0$, it holds $\mathbf{b}_t = \mathbf{b}_{t-1} = \dots = \mathbf{b}_0$, so (3.35) becomes $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{bg-free}^t = \hat{\mathbf{h}}^t - \mathbf{b}_0$ which falls back to the static background removal in (3.34).

ii. Object detection

The background-free range-angle RADAR maps are fed to the object detection stage. Object detection is based on methods for contour detection used in image processing [92], [93]. The 2D range-angle complex data is transformed to an 8-bit image as follows

$$Z_{n,m} = \frac{|\hat{h}_{n,m,bg-free}^t - \min(|\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{bg-free}^t|)|}{\max(|\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{bg-free}^t|) - \min(|\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{bg-free}^t|)} \cdot (2^8 - 1) \quad (3.37)$$

Then, Gaussian smoothing is applied to suppress spatial noise and after thresholding, a binary image is obtained:

$$I_{i,j} = \begin{cases} 1, & \mathbf{Z} \otimes \mathbf{G} \geq T. \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3.38)$$

where i and j denote the pixel coordinates in the binary image \mathbf{I} , \mathbf{G} is the 2D Gaussian kernel with standard deviation σ , T represents threshold, and \otimes is the 2D convolution operator. In the binary image in (3.38), clusters of black pixels represent potential objects. Neighboring pixel regions are identified as contours (i.e., each contour represents one potential object) using contour detection algorithms. For each contour the minimum enclosing circle (x_l, y_l, r_l) is obtained where x_l and y_l denote the center coordinates and r_l the radius of the minimum enclosing circle. It should be noted that the parameters of the minimum enclosing circle are given in pixel coordinates, while the elements of the 2D matrix represent physical values of the range and angle. Therefore, x_l , y_l and r_l need to be transformed into physical coordinates using the spatial parameters of the system, i.e., the range resolution ΔR and the angular sampling resolution $\Delta\theta$.

iii. Object tracking

There are various techniques that can be applied to track the movement of detected objects from the previous processing stage. The simplest solution is just based on checking whether the detected position is outside the space area defined by the beam width of the communication beam. It does not involve predicting future positions. This approach can be extended to include mobility prediction using short-term history, similar to the sliding window approach, by examining a set of previous detected positions (i.e., trajectory) and finding a probable next one. Further improvements can include long-term movement history, which can be combined with the short-term history, using e.g., Markov Renewal Process and Dempster-Shafer (DS) theory [94].

More advanced methods for tracking of moving objects and prediction of their future positions include Kalman filter [95], [96], particle filter [97] or alpha-beta-gamma filter [98], [99].

iv. Beam adaptation

The final step is beam adaptation (switching). Beam switching is triggered in the following cases:

- The detected current position of the moving object is close to or within the area covered by the LOS beam,
- The predicted future position of the moving object is close to or within the area defined by the LOS beam, or
- The path between the current position and the future position of the moving object intersects the path defined by the LOS beam.

Based on information about the current and future positions of objects provided by the object tracking block, beam switching to the most suitable alternative NLoS path is initiated. Processing of sensing data according to Fig. 3.16 can take place at any location in the system or network. If performed on the sensing device itself, the beam adaptation process is initiated by the mmWave ISAC device and shared with its communication counterpart.

In the completely opposite scenario, only the acquisition of the sensing data is done on the sensing device, but the sensing data processing and decision making takes place on a remote location (server), e.g., near-RT RIC, xApps or wherever the m-SePF is executed. In this case, when the processing of sensing data occurs at the core in a service-based approach, less “real-time” sensing capabilities are offered. The latency requirements for the beam adaptation application discussed here need to be considered by considering all the delays (delay due to sensing data fetching, sensing data processing, decision making, execution). A mechanism is needed that will guarantee the minimum latency requirements for the m-SePF in question.

3.3.1.5. Preliminary Results

The presented ISAC-assisted object detection for link blockage mitigation was experimentally evaluated. Two mmWave stations with ISAC functionality, operating in the 60 GHz band, were placed in an open office area at a distance of about 5 meters, pointing directly at each other, as show in Fig. 3.17. In addition, a metal plate was placed aside the two devices at a distance of 1.5 meters from the direct path to form a second, NLoS communication path to be used in the beam adaptation process. One station transmits OFDM packets with a net data rate of about 900 Mb/s to the other station, where communication performance metrics such as packet loss, error vector magnitude were observed. In addition to data communication, the transmitting device

does monostatic environmental sensing a time-division multiple access fashion, where at each time instant a RADAR-like map of environment is obtained. The sensing information is then used for subsequent object detection, tracking and beam adaptation, as discussed in the previous section. Fig. 3.18 visualizes the basic processing steps as depicted in Fig. 3.16.

Figure 3.17: A sketch of evaluation scenario.

To evaluate how object detection and tracking can improve the robustness of wireless communication by avoiding communication link blockage, the following scenario was developed. A person enters the space between the two devices, coming from the side of the receiving device, and moves towards the transmitting device, thereby blocking the direct path, after which he leaves the given space. The person's moving path is shown in Fig. 3.17 with a dotted arrow. Due to the relatively slow walking speed (<1 m/s) and the small detection area, no movement prediction is needed. Instead, an area of approx. 0.5 m around the direct path is defined, determined by the beam width of the LoS beam (3 dB beam width in radians \times link distance). If the detected object is within this area, beam adaptation is initiated by selecting the secondary communication path. Measurements were performed with and without beam adaptation. In both cases, the number of missed packets (MP), erroneous packets (EP) and the resulting Packet Error Rate (PER) were measured within one minute and comparison is made. The results are reported in Table 3.2. It is evident that ISAC-assisted object detection can prevent communication link blockage and improve robustness of mmWave communication.

Table 3.2: MmWave link performance with (w/) and without (w/o) ISAC-assisted beam adaptation.

w/o beam adaptation			w/ beam adaptation		
MP	EP	PER	MP	EP	PER
7973	8366	1.7 %	0	0	0 %

3.3.1.6. Future Work

Future work will focus on evaluation in more complex scenarios with detection and tracking of multiple objects. Implementation of different tracking algorithms and their evaluation is another direction to follow. In addition, the work can be extended with multi-station object detection, localization and tracking. Here, it is necessary to take into account the sensing time synchronization from different devices, meaning sensing measurements should be time-stamped for valid fusion and further processing. Processing of sensing information from different ISAC devices participating in the communication can improve environmental perception outside the visible field-of-view of individual devices, improving the situational awareness of communication participants and communication link quality. Finally, for the case where the processing of sensing information with beam adaptation takes place on a service-based basis in the network core (rather than at the sensing device), it is necessary

Figure 3.18: Outcome of different processing steps per Fig. 3.16: a) raw heatmap, b) heatmap after background removal, c) image after thresholding background-free heatmap for object detection, d) contour-based object detection, e) detected object with center point used in the tracking phase. Radial-axis in meters, angular-axis in degrees.

to develop a mechanism to guarantee minimum latency requirements for a given sensing data processing function.

3.3.2. Estimation of Site-Specific SNR-Distribution

Industrial environments are especially challenging for wireless communication, due to the presence of many metallic surfaces and moving equipment. The first results into high multi-path propagation and small-scale fading, while the second one contributes to the random shadowing, also due to the presence of large obstacles between the receiver and the transceiver. In order to develop methods for optimization of wireless network performance, especially on the PHY and MAC layer, channel estimation is a common technique to characterize the effect of the communication channel and its environment on the transmitted wireless channel. Estimating the channel and its characteristics, e.g., the distribution of the SNR, enables the development of various techniques for RAN optimization, among which, computation and prediction of Quality of Service (QoS) metrics, such as delay, PER, BLER, and delay violation probability or a delay bound [100, 101].

There are several known distributions of the random fading process which are used in literature, such as Rician, Nakagami-m, the Rayleigh fading, and Hoyt, to name a few. However, these channel distribution functions do not necessarily represent the actual statistical behaviour of wireless fading channels in a specific environment, especially in factories. Very often, additionally, these fading channel representations are very complex for further mathematical modeling and development of MAC layer tools, such as computing the delay distribution, scheduling, and resource allocation algorithms for traffic with strict QoS requirements.

Hence, this work aims to estimate the parameters of a site-specific fading, and therefore, SNR distribution, by using the Mixture of Gaussian (MoG) model [102]. This model is used to approximate the envelope and SNR distribution for a wireless channel, thereby simplifying various complex models that traditionally involve Bessel functions and are often very hard to mathematically track.

3.3.2.1. Challenges and contributions

Our aim is to deliver a site-specific SNR distribution of the wireless channel in the form of a unified MoG distribution that accurately represents a wireless fading channel. For the parameter estimation usually an expectation-maximization algorithm is used, in order to estimate the MoG parameters, such as weight, means, and variances. The Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) is usually used to automatically determine the optimal number of Gaussian components.

The amplitude of a fading channel can be given as following [103]

$$f_{\alpha}(x) = \sum_{j=1}^C \frac{\omega_j}{\sqrt{2\pi\eta_j}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu_j)^2}{2\eta_j^2}\right), \quad (3.39)$$

where $f_{\alpha}(x)$ is the pdf of the amplitude as a random variable, represented by x , ω_j is the weight of the j -th component, μ_j is the mean of the j -th component, η_j^2 is the variance of the j -th component. It holds that

$$\sum_{j=1}^C \omega_j = 1, \quad (3.40)$$

where C is the total number of components of the MoG. For an average SNR $\bar{\gamma}$ and an instantaneous SNR $\gamma = \bar{\gamma}x$, the MoG distribution can be written as [103]

$$f_{\gamma}(\gamma) = \sum_{j=1}^C \frac{\omega_j}{\sqrt{8\pi\bar{\gamma}\eta_j}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{\bar{\gamma}}} \exp\left(-\frac{\left(\sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{\bar{\gamma}}} - \mu_j\right)^2}{2\eta_j^2}\right). \quad (3.41)$$

When fitting a finite mixture distribution, one has to optimally determine the number of mixture components. In case of a few components, the resulting distribution would be less accurate, while choosing many components could result into unnecessarily increased complexity of the distribution and may cause over-fitting [103]. While the optimal number of components is computed using the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), the actual distribution parameters for the mixture will be estimated with the expectation maximization algorithm. This algorithm will find the maximum-likelihood estimator of any distribution in the exponential family.

The BIC is a statistical metric used for model selection, which helps choose the best model among a set of candidates by balancing model fit and complexity. A possible representation of the BIC can be given by

$$\text{BIC}_C = -2L(\hat{\theta} | \mathbf{y}, C) + C \ln N, \quad (3.42)$$

where C is the number of components, $\mathbf{y} = y_1, \dots, y_N$ is the vector of N independent and identically distributed samples drawn from the envelope distribution of a fading model. $L(\hat{\theta} | \mathbf{y}, C)$ is the log-likelihood distribution of the MoG distribution and $\hat{\theta} = (\hat{\omega}_1, \hat{\omega}_2, \dots, \hat{\omega}_C, \hat{\mu}_1, \hat{\mu}_2, \dots, \hat{\mu}_C, \hat{\eta}_1, \hat{\eta}_2, \dots, \hat{\eta}_C)$ are the estimated parameters and C is the total number of components.

3.3.2.2. Use within MultiX

Within Multi-X we are currently working on building a 3D model from our laboratory. This 3D model will represent the objects and the materials they are made of and will be exported in a file suitable for a ray tracing tool, e.g., the Sionna raytracer [104]. Using Sionna [105], an open source link-level simulator based on TensorFlow, we will develop the above explained MoG and the accompanied BIC and expectation maximization algorithms to estimate the distribution parameters and derive a site-specific fading, i.e., SNR distribution function. From the CIR, we will also derive a power delay profile and compute the resulting SNR. The estimated SNR will be compared with the computed SNR in the link-level simulator. In a next step, we will compute the BLER of the channel and validate it with a measured BLER in our testbed, using a set of USRPs as a Tx-Rx pair. We plan to use fingerprinting and compute the BLER at different points in the laboratory and compare it with the one obtained with Sionna. This measurement and validation campaign will help in evaluating our algorithms and show us the gap between the estimated and actually measured SNR. This effort will be encapsulated as a network digital twin to be used within the PoC 1 as part of the WP4 in Multi-X. Algorithms developed for RAN optimization within WP2 will use the estimated site-specific SNR to compute link-level metrics such as BLER or PER. These metrics will then be mapped to higher-level KPIs relevant for URLLC performance

analysis, including delay violation probability or delay bounds. The resulting models will guide scheduling and resource-allocation strategies, which will be tuned to meet the QoS requirements of the cooperative-robotics scenario demonstrated in PoC 1 (WP4).

3.3.2.3. BLER-to-SNR Mapping Using Effective Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio Mapping Model

In order to do proper RAN configuration and be able to compute the Delay Violation Probability (DVP) for a given traffic flow, we have done network simulations in ns-3 using the 5G-LENA module [106]. One of the initial steps for computing the DVP is to compute the PER or BLER, as presented and derived in [107]. Hence, we were conducting extensive simulations to validate an analytical formula for the BLER, in order to be able to analytically define the DVP and use this in a resource allocation algorithm (see deliverable from WP2).

5G-LENA uses the effective Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) mapping model. It uses a mapping function to obtain an effective SINR that summarizes the effect of multiple SINRs. The mapping parameters have to be calibrated for each Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS). The goal is that for each MCS, the variation of SINR has to be mapped to an effective SINR value that would end up with the same BLER under an AWGN channel, as the experimental BLER which is measured in a fading channel using the same MCS [108]. The effective SINR for Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ)-IR (incremental redundancy), using the Effective SINR Mapping Model model after M retransmissions, where the SINR is the same for all resource blocks within the defined bandwidth, is given by [108]:

$$\text{SINR}_{\text{eff}} = -\beta \ln \left(\frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \exp \left(-\frac{\text{SINR}_m}{\beta} \right) \right), \quad (3.43)$$

where SINR is the SINR experienced in the m -th retransmission and β is a parameter that need to be optimized. The value of β is calibrated, such that the effective SINR of that channel approximates to the SINR that would produce the same BLER, with the same MCS, but in AWGN channel conditions [109]. The BLER for a resource block with a given MCS can be accurately predicted from its effective SINR by using the following formula:

$$P(s, \gamma') = \frac{1}{2} \text{erfc} \left(\frac{\gamma' - b_s}{\sqrt{2}c_s} \right), \quad (3.44)$$

where s is denoted as the MCS index and b_s and c_s are fitting parameters for Gaussian cumulative approximation to BLER mapping for a given MCS with index s (see Table 3 in [110]). The parameters are obtained from a Gaussian cumulative model which provide a close fit to an AWGN performance curve, and b is referred to as "transition center", while c is referred to as "transition width". γ' is a modified SNR using the effective SINR and the following formula:

$$\gamma' = \frac{\text{SINR}_{\text{eff}}}{\beta} - \exp \left(-\frac{\text{SINR}_{\text{eff}}}{\beta} \right) + C. \quad (3.45)$$

Eq. (3.45) also considers a certain correction factor C , which we obtained via trial and error approach, in order to map the BLER obtained from 5G-LENA and the one given with Eq. (3.44).

Fig. Fig. 3.19 represents the BLER-to-SNR mapping using only effective SNR, i.e., Eq. (3.43) and no further adjustments at all. Fig. Fig. 3.20 represents the BLER-to-SNR mapping using Eq. (3.45), but with $C = 0$, while Fig. Fig. 3.21 uses the same equation for the modified SNR, but with a certain correction factor. As we can see, the last figure's simulation collide the best with the analytical formula for the BLER, given with Eq. (3.44), where each of the four graphs in the figure represent either the initial transmission or one of the remaining 3 HARQ retransmissions.

The goal of our further work within WP3 in Multi-X will be to obtain the BLER from Sionna and validate the measured BLER with a testbed and compare the two curves as shown in Fig. 3.19, Fig. 3.20 and Fig. 3.21.

3.4. Near-field processing

This sub-task exploits near-field effects at high carrier frequencies and large apertures, developing array-of-sub-arrays and hierarchical estimation techniques for fine-grained spatial sensing, with a roadmap toward joint angle–range–Doppler recovery that preserves compressed-acquisition benefits. We carried out the following research activity:

Figure 3.19: BLER-to-SNR mapping when using only effective SNR.

- Near-field sensing exploiting arrays of sub-arrays (Section 3.4). A hierarchical recovery framework using sub-array partitioning to balance resolution and robustness, extendable to joint angle–range–Doppler estimation.

3.4.1. Near-field sensing exploiting arrays of sub-arrays

Future ISAC systems will increasingly operate in the near-field regime, where wavefront curvature carries both angular and range information. This opens opportunities for precise localization and sensing using a single anchor, but also introduces new challenges. Classical far-field methods such as MUSIC or Estimation of Signal Parameters via Rotational Invariance Techniques (ESPRIT) need substantial adaptation, and achieving near-field resolution typically demands very large antenna apertures. Fully-digital arrays can provide such apertures, but they require a dedicated RF chain per antenna, making them prohibitively costly and power-hungry.

A promising alternative is the use of array-of-subarrays architectures, where a large aperture is created by physically separating dense subarrays. This reduces RF chain count but creates sparse apertures that introduce grating lobes and severe estimation ambiguities. Without tailored processing methods, these ambiguities make it difficult to uniquely resolve the position of near-field sources.

3.4.1.1. Challenges and Contributions

The main challenge is to balance hardware scalability and localization accuracy. Fully-digital arrays scale poorly in cost and energy, while sparse subarray designs reduce complexity but produce highly ambiguous spatial responses. Conventional compressed sensing algorithms, when applied directly to such architectures, inherit these ambiguities and struggle to produce reliable estimates.

To overcome these limitations, we developed within MultiX a two-stage compressed sensing framework designed specifically for sparse modular arrays. The proposed method operates in two steps:

Figure 3.20: BLER-to-SNR mapping without correction factor.

- Stage 1 leverages individual subarrays for robust coarse angle estimation, eliminating grating lobe ambiguities.
- Stage 2 then uses the full sparse aperture to refine both angle and range jointly, achieving high-resolution localization with far lower complexity than brute-force grid search.

Through this hierarchical approach, we preserve the high resolution of large-aperture systems while avoiding the computational burden and ambiguity issues of classical techniques. Simulations show that the method not only outperforms conventional one-shot compressed sensing approaches but can also match or surpass the accuracy of fully-digital MUSIC, even though this assumes access to all antenna elements.

3.4.1.2. Use within MultiX

This contribution provides a key algorithmic building block for the high-resolution sensing objectives of WP3. By enabling robust joint angle–range estimation with sparse modular arrays, it directly supports the project’s vision of scalable, high-resolution ISAC systems. The hierarchical compressed sensing approach allows MultiX to move beyond costly fully-digital solutions while still maintaining the precision needed for near-field localization. This work is particularly relevant for boosting sensing accuracy in multi-antenna systems that naturally operate in the near-field region when equipped with very large apertures. In the context of the MultiX perception system, the algorithm strengthens the ability to extract precise spatial information while controlling hardware complexity, making it possible to explore advanced ISAC functionalities in practical array deployments.

3.4.1.3. Modelling

We target near-field localization with a modular array-of-subarrays antenna architecture. This design uses a large physical aperture to increase angle and range resolution, but instead of equipping every element with

Figure 3.21: BLER-to-SNR mapping with a correction factor.

its own RF chain, only a few are available. Each subarray employs analog combining, so that the system observes compressed projections of the full array data across a sequence of beamforming settings. The core estimation problem is therefore to recover the source angles and ranges from these compressed, multi-snapshot measurements, leveraging the sparsity of emitters in the joint angle–range domain.

The array is composed of P subarrays, each containing M_0 tightly spaced antenna elements. The total number of antenna elements is $M = P \cdot M_0$. Within each subarray, the element spacing is $d \leq \lambda/2$, which avoids grating lobes locally, while the subarrays are separated by a larger spacing d_p to expand the effective aperture. The position of the m -th element in the p -th subarray can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{s}_{p,m} = [(p-1)d_p + md, 0, 0]^T, \quad (3.46)$$

with $m = 0, \dots, M_0 - 1$ and $p = 1, \dots, P$. This representation highlights that elements within each subarray are close together, while larger inter-subarray gaps create a sparse aperture that extends the near-field region.

A source ℓ located at range r_ℓ and azimuth angle θ_ℓ has position vector

$$\mathbf{s}_\ell = r_\ell \boldsymbol{\kappa}(\theta_\ell), \quad \boldsymbol{\kappa}(\theta_\ell) = [\cos \theta_\ell, \sin \theta_\ell, 0]^T. \quad (3.47)$$

This vector points to the source: its length captures the range, and its orientation depends on the azimuth. Unlike far-field models, here the geometry preserves the curvature of spherical wavefronts, which is what embeds range information into the received signal.

The propagation delay between the source and element (p, m) is

$$\tau_{p,m,\ell} = \frac{\|\mathbf{s}_{p,m} - \mathbf{s}_\ell\|_2 - r_\ell}{c}, \quad (3.48)$$

where c denotes the speed of light. This quantity expresses how much additional distance the signal must travel to reach element (p, m) compared to the reference path r_ℓ . The nonlinear dependence on r_ℓ is precisely what allows a single array to estimate both angle and range in the near-field.

3.4.1.3.1 Fully-digital reference model

If every antenna element were connected to its own RF chain, the received baseband signal at element (p, m) during snapshot n would be

$$y_{p,m}(n) = \sum_{\ell=1}^L x_{\ell}(n) e^{-j2\pi f_c \tau_{p,m,\ell}} + v_{p,m}(n), \quad (3.49)$$

where $x_{\ell}(n)$ is the signal transmitted by source ℓ , f_c is the carrier frequency, and $v_{p,m}(n)$ is noise. A fully digital architecture is shown in Fig. 3.22 (Top). In this case, each antenna thus observes a superposition of all sources, with phase terms determined by their propagation delays.

Stacking the signals across all M elements gives

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{A}(\Theta, R)\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{V}, \quad (3.50)$$

where $\mathbf{A}(\Theta, R)$ is the array manifold containing the near-field steering vectors parameterized by the set of angles $\Theta = \{\theta_1, \dots, \theta_L\}$ and ranges $R = \{r_1, \dots, r_L\}$. This model is conceptually simple but impractical at large scale, since it assumes a dedicated RF chain per antenna element.

3.4.1.3.2 Compressed sensing model

To reduce hardware cost, each subarray is connected to a single RF chain through an analog combining network, as shown in Fig. 3.22 (bottom). At measurement instant $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, the combining network applies

$$\Phi_k = \text{blkdiag}(\mathbf{w}_{k,1}^T, \mathbf{w}_{k,2}^T, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{k,P}^T), \quad (3.51)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_{k,p}$ are the phase-shifter weights of subarray p . Each Φ_k corresponds to one analog beam configuration across the array.

Collecting all measurements produces the stacked matrix

$$\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} \Phi_1 \\ \vdots \\ \Phi_K \end{bmatrix},$$

and the compressed sensing model

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Y}} = \Phi \mathbf{A}(\Theta, R)\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{Z}, \quad (3.52)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}$ are the reduced-dimensional observations and \mathbf{Z} is effective noise. Here the role of compressed sensing becomes clear: although we no longer have access to all antenna signals, repeated projections across K instants still preserve enough information to recover the sparse set of source locations.

3.4.1.3.3 Hierarchical estimation principle

Recovering sources directly from a global angle–range grid is computationally infeasible and prone to grating lobe ambiguities. Instead, we adopt a two-stage hierarchical approach:

1. **Stage 1 (coarse angles):** Each dense subarray behaves approximately as a far-field array since its aperture is small. The steering vector simplifies to

$$[\mathbf{a}_{\text{sub}}(\theta)]_m \approx e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(md \cos \theta)}. \quad (3.53)$$

Using this approximation, we compute non-coherent power spectra across subarrays and combine them to obtain robust coarse angle estimates that are free of grating lobe ambiguities.

2. **Stage 2 (refinement):** Around each coarse estimate $\hat{\theta}_{\ell}$, we build a localized dictionary

$$\Psi = [\dots, \Phi \mathbf{a}(\theta_i, r_j), \dots], \quad \theta_i \in \Theta_{\text{ref}}, r_j \in \mathcal{R}_{\text{grid}}, \quad (3.54)$$

Figure 3.22: Fully digital (Top) and Hybrid (Bottom) array of sub-arrays architectures

where Θ_{ref} is a small angular window around the Stage 1 estimates and $\mathcal{R}_{\text{grid}}$ is a discretized set of ranges. The joint estimation then reduces to a sparse recovery problem

$$\min_{\mathbf{S}} \|\mathbf{S}\|_{2,0} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \|\tilde{\mathbf{Y}} - \Psi\mathbf{S}\|_F^2 \leq \varepsilon. \quad (3.55)$$

This step jointly refines angle and range, recovering source locations with far less complexity than a brute-force 2D search.

The intuition is that Stage 1 provides a coarse but unambiguous "compass", while Stage 2 uses the full sparse aperture as a "magnifying glass" to refine the solution with high resolution.

3.4.1.4. Simulation Setup and Results

The proposed hierarchical compressed sensing framework was evaluated through Monte Carlo simulations using modular linear arrays. Unless otherwise stated, we considered an array with $P = 4$ subarrays, each containing $M_0 = 16$ elements spaced at $d = \lambda/2$, with inter-subarray spacing $d_p = 16\lambda$. The carrier frequency was set to $f_c = 60$ GHz, and the near-field region was defined accordingly. Simulations included $N = 32$ temporal snapshots and $K = 16$ distinct analog combining measurements, with phase-shifter weights chosen from a DFT codebook. Performance was assessed over a range of SNR values, and metrics included RMSE of angle, range, and overall position. Two baseline algorithms were considered: conventional one-shot 2D-OMP [111] applied to compressed measurements, and the fully-digital 2D-MUSIC [112] algorithm, which assumes access to all antenna outputs.

Fig. 3.23 summarizes the main results. Left plot shows angle and range RMSE as a function of SNR. The proposed hierarchical approach achieves steadily improving accuracy, outperforming 2D-OMP, which exhibits an error floor due to dictionary coherence, and 2D-MUSIC, which suffers from grating lobe ambiguities when applied to sparse modular arrays. Right plot reports the overall position RMSE versus SNR, showing that our proposal consistently improves with increasing SNR and approaches the oracle Cramér–Rao bound. By contrast, both 2D-OMP and 2D-MUSIC saturate at significantly higher error levels. These results confirm that the proposed method not only resolves the ambiguity inherent in sparse arrays but also maintains robustness and efficiency across operating conditions.

3.4.1.5. Future Work

We will extend this study along three concrete directions. First, we will adapt the framework to sensing-centric scenarios, assessing how array partitioning and the hierarchical recovery trade off between spatial resolution

Figure 3.23: Simulation results comparing the proposed hierarchical framework with 2D-OMP and 2D-MUSIC. Angle and range RMSE versus SNR (left) and Overall position RMSE versus SNR (right).

and robustness under realistic clutter and multipath. Second, we will validate the approach with real experiments on our experimental platforms. Third, we will extend the model to Doppler, moving from static snapshots to time-varying scenes: this entails incorporating a per-source radial velocity ν_ℓ and augmenting the dictionary to jointly estimate (θ, r, f_D) , with $f_D = 2\nu_\ell/\lambda$ for monostatic geometries (generalized for bistatic layouts). This joint angle–range–Doppler formulation will enable micro-motion analysis and unambiguous velocity estimation while preserving the compressed-acquisition benefits.

4. Task 3.3: AI-based energy efficient perception system

Task 3.3 targets the MultiX objective SO3.3: *Design and validate energy-efficient AI architectures for adaptive, event-based ISAC receivers and distributed learning from multi-static sensing devices.*

Our goal is to achieve a reduction of the AI-based computing energy consumption by $\geq 20\%$ compared to traditional methods by designing new efficient AI architectures and drawing inspiration from the *event-based* sensing operations taking place in the human brain.

To this end, we identified the following 4 main research activities that will develop the required components to achieve this goal.

1. **Energy efficient, neuromorphic, and event-based ISAC receivers (Section 4.1).** This activity deals with the energy efficiency of the AI architectures themselves. Here, we address the design and validation of new architectures for ISAC signal processing that are event-based and neuromorphic.
2. **Resource optimization with AI (Section 4.2).** This activity leverages AI to optimize the energy efficiency of the ISAC-enabled RAN. This activity pursues a complementary objective to the previous one, aiming to efficiently handle the multiple ISAC resources.
3. **Multi-modal sensing (Section 4.3).** In this activity, we enable the developed AI architectures with multi-modal sensing capabilities, which is a fundamental step to achieve the MultiX goal of integrating multiple sensing technologies (radio signals, cameras, radar, LIDAR, etc.).
4. **AI/GenAI for multi-band and multi-static ISAC (Section 4.4).** This activity explores the use of AI and GenAI to enable or improve multi-band and multi-static ISAC studied in T3.1 and T3.2. These methods are promising solutions to the problem of incomplete channel observations in frequency and space that arises when considering multi-band and multi-static ISAC nodes.

Together, these contributions support the development of an intelligent, multi-modal, and energy-aware perception system suitable for a wide range of ISAC applications in MultiX.

4.1. Energy efficient, neuromorphic, and event-based ISAC receivers

The objective of this subtask is to develop AI models to process ISAC data that are energy efficient, through the exploitation of novel neuromorphic and event-based architectures.

Within this subtask, we carried out the following three research activities.

- Efficient Open-Set Gait Recognition from Sparse mmWave Radar Point Clouds (Section 4.1.1). This represents a preliminary step towards energy- and resource-efficient sensing, exploiting lightweight point clouds obtained from radio signals. We release the corresponding dataset for further investigation by the MultiX consortium and the research community.
- Preliminary investigation of Spiking Neural Network (SNN) models for ISAC (Section 4.1.2). An initial investigation of the use of neuromorphic computing to reduce the energy consumption of sensing functions has been conducted. The existing literature on the subject has been reviewed, and initial efforts were made toward modeling the energy consumption of SNNs.
- Simultaneous localisation and detection of humans indoors using FR1 (Section 4.1.3). A lightweight AI model is proposed that can localise and track humans from the peaks in the Power Delay Profile (PDP) obtained with a multicarrier Frequency Range 1 (FR1) ISAC system.

4.1.1. Efficient Open-Set Gait Recognition from Sparse mmWave Radar Point Clouds

4.1.1.1. Introduction and motivation

By leveraging the information in the backscattered electromagnetic signal, mmWave radars can infer key quantities such as the subject's position in the three-dimensional space and their radial velocity, with high precision. Example applications include vital signs monitoring [113], fall detection [114], human tracking [115] and real-time person identification [116]. The latter relies on the extraction of spatiotemporal features of the subjects'

movements from the radar signal. These are often connected with the body shape and the way of walking, commonly referred to as *gait*. In the literature, gait is classified as a *soft biometric* [117]. It serves as an effective discriminative feature in scenarios involving a limited number of subjects, at most in the range of a few tens [118]. Example applications of remote gait recognition include medical diagnosis, home monitoring, user authentication, and surveillance systems [119].

The extraction of features of human gait is most commonly carried out by analyzing the so-called *micro-Doppler (μD) signature* of a subject. The micro-Doppler is a frequency modulation observed on the reflected signal, induced by the Doppler effect caused by small-scale movements of the target. Typically, due to the complexity of the μD time-frequency patterns, μD signatures are processed using suitable (often Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based) deep learning architectures that automatically extract gait features [115, 120].

4.1.1.2. Challenges and contribution

mmWave radar-based person identification systems are especially appealing for distributed monitoring applications. In this domain, radar sensors are deployed at the edge of the communication network, equipped with low-power and resource-constrained computing devices [121]. This poses two important research challenges. First, collecting and processing radar data can be computationally demanding due to their large size and high resolution. This requires using radar data representations that trade some resolution or accuracy for an increased sparsity and lower size. A promising candidate in this sense is the point-cloud representation [122]. The point-cloud representation is widely used by LIDAR sensors, but it is difficult to process in the radar domain due to its sparsity, fast variability in time, and the small number of reflection points off the human body.

Second, distributed monitoring applications are typically used in *open-set* scenarios, where subjects that were not included in the training set may appear and disappear from the scene. In such setup, gait recognition methods must be able to effectively deal with *unseen* subjects, by distinguishing them from those already known to the system. The problem of simultaneously classifying known subjects and detecting unknown ones using gait features is referred to in the literature as OSGR [123–125].

To the best of our knowledge, no previous work in the literature has jointly tackled both challenges, thus being unsuited for realistic edge-based people monitoring applications.

We propose PCAA, a novel deep learning architecture based upon the Adversarial Autoencoder (AAE) [126] that extracts meaningful gait features from sparse point-cloud data and uses them to perform classification of known subjects and detection of unknown ones during the testing phase. Our approach is summarized in Fig. 4.1

Figure 4.1: Visual representation of the proposed OSGR approach.

The main contributions of our work are:

1. We propose and validate PCAA, a novel neural network architecture capable of effectively classifying radar point clouds of human gaits.
2. We design a simple and efficient algorithm to detect novel subjects from the extracted features at inference time, by successively addressing the OSGR problem.

3. We collect and make available the mmGaitNet10 dataset [127], containing mmWavr radar point cloud data from 10 subjects in different walking modalities.
4. We evaluate PCAA in different experimental conditions and compare it with the latest available methods from the literature on the mmGaitNet10 dataset. We demonstrate that our method significantly outperforms existing solutions adapted for points clouds, achieving 24% average F1-Score improvement.

4.1.1.3. Use within MultiX

The proposed learning architecture represents a first step towards the MultiX vision of energy-efficient AI models for ISAC. By processing radar point clouds, the proposed network represents a general enabler for human recognition, since a point cloud representation of people in the environment can also be obtained from ISAC signals. In a second phase, we will replace the learning architecture based on standard layers with a SNN, which will push the energy efficiency even further.

4.1.1.4. Proposed open-set classifier

Figure 4.2: The figure depicts the proposed architecture and the flow of computations, going from left to right.

In activity, we tackle the problem of OSGR from sparse radar point clouds. Our system consists of two main phases: *deep feature extraction* and *unknown subject detection*. In the first phase, the system extracts compact features of human gait from the input radar point cloud sequences. To this end, we propose PCAA, a deep neural network that reaps the benefits of supervised and unsupervised learning strategies. In the following sections, we first describe the preprocessing steps applied to the raw radar point clouds before they are fed into the network. Then, the network architecture and training strategy are thoroughly described.

In the second phase, we leverage the regularized structure of the trained latent space to perform the novel subject detection task. To this end, we propose a simple detection algorithm that can determine whether an input gait feature vector belongs to a known or unknown subject at inference time.

Point cloud pre-processing. Before being fed to our model, data collected by the radar undergoes a series of preprocessing steps. The first step takes the raw radar data and applies detection, clustering, and tracking algorithms to isolate the points reflected off the subject's body from the ones due to spurious reflections from the environment. To this end, we employ the same procedure proposed in [116], which applies a Kalman Filter to track the point cloud as it moves in space, coupled with a clustering algorithm to select the points corresponding to the subjects. In the following, we define a single reflected point as a vector $\mathbf{x} = [x, y, z, v]^T$, including its spatial coordinates x, y, z , and its radial velocity v . We formally define a point cloud as a set \mathcal{X} , containing a variable number of points.

To build the input for our neural network, we split each point cloud sequence measurement in windows of three seconds, corresponding to N_f frames taken with step size s . We denote the resulting sequence of point clouds by $\mathbf{X}_{1:N_f} = \{\mathbf{X}_t\}_{t=1}^{N_f}$, where $\mathbf{X}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{N_p \times 4}$. We denote by \mathbf{e}_i the one-hot encoded vector of all zeros but the i -th component, which equals 1, and we define $S = \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$ as the set of subject IDs. By applying the above procedure to all our measurements, we build a dataset of input-label pairs of the form $(\mathbf{X}_{1:N_f}, \mathbf{y})$, where $\mathbf{y} \in \{\mathbf{e}_i\}_{i \in S}$. We define $S_K \subset S$ the set of known subject IDs and $S_U \subset S$ the set of the unknown ones, so that

$\{S_K, S_U\}$ is a partition of S . The cardinalities of S_K and S_U depend on the specific scenario. Following the OSGR literature, we measure how many unknown subjects are present with respect to the known ones using the *openness* metric, defined in the experimental results section. Using the above subject partition, we split the whole dataset into the known partition \mathcal{K} of known subjects and the unknown partition \mathcal{U} of unknowns.

Model architecture. PCAA leverages the strength of both supervised and unsupervised learning to extract meaningful features from radar point clouds, which is the first necessary step to solve the OSGR task. PCAA is based on and extends an AAE architecture, featuring four main components: (A) an encoder module, (B) a decoder module, or unsupervised branch, (C) a supervised branch, (D) an adversarial branch. Let $\mathbf{X}_{1:N_f}$ be an input point cloud sequence, \mathbf{z} its latent representation computed by the encoder module, and $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_{1:N_f}$ the reconstruction obtained from the decoder. We define as $p_d(\mathbf{X}_{1:N_f})$ the data distribution, by $q(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{X}_{1:N_f})$ the encoding distribution induced by the encoder, and by $p(\hat{\mathbf{X}}_{1:N_f}|\mathbf{z})$ the distribution of the reconstructed point cloud sequence produced by the decoder. The core idea of the AAE is to match the aggregated encoder output distribution over all possible input point cloud sequences, $q(\mathbf{z})$, to a prior distribution $p(\mathbf{z})$ that can be specified during the design of the system. To this end, a *Discriminator* module is trained to predict whether its input was generated by the encoder module or sampled from the prior distribution.

We now describe each part of our model, referring to the diagram of the PCAA architecture reported in Fig. 4.2.

(A) Encoder: The Encoder block of our network processes the input point clouds to extract compact spatio-temporal features. To this end, we adapt the Temporal Convolution Point-Cloud Network (TCPCN) architecture proposed in [128], which was originally designed for gait classification from radar point clouds. As a first step, each point cloud of the input sequence is processed by 4 consecutive network blocks inspired by the PointNet architecture [129], which we refer to as PointNet blocks, followed by a global average pooling operation applied at each point cloud of the sequence. The resulting output is a sequence of feature vectors, one per point cloud in the sequence. Next, a temporal convolution block [130] is employed to process the temporal correlations in the point cloud sequences. After a final average pooling operation along the time dimension and a single linear projection layer, the Encoder module returns the latent representation vector of the whole point cloud sequence, denoted by $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^K$, $K = 32$.

(B) Unsupervised branch: This part of the network is responsible for the reconstruction of the input point cloud sequence from the compressed representation vector \mathbf{z} .

In the Unsupervised branch, we introduce a *projection head* [131], \mathcal{H}_D , to learn a transformation of \mathbf{z} that specializes in reconstructing the input. \mathcal{H}_D is a fully connected layer with 64 neurons, equipped with an Exponential-Linear Unit (ELU). Then, the Decoder block performs a series of upsampling steps to yield an output tensor of the same shape as the input. The choice of this simple MLP structure is due to the non-invertibility of the PointNet module due to the global average pooling operation.

(C) Supervised branch: This branch is designed to perform subject classification from the compressed representation \mathbf{z} . Similarly to \mathcal{H}_D , we use a projection head, \mathcal{H}_C , to transform \mathbf{z} into a new representation that specializes in classification. We found using projection heads to be beneficial to learn a more general representation \mathbf{z} , as motivated in [131]. After the projection head, a single output layer with a softmax activation function performs the classification task by returning a probability distribution over the classes.

(D) Adversarial branch: Given the input tuple $(\mathbf{X}_{1:N_f}, \mathbf{e}_i)$, belonging to the known dataset partition \mathcal{K} , the key idea is to constrain the encoder to generate a representation \mathbf{z} according to a Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_i, \mathbf{I}_K)$, where \mathbf{I}_K is the $K \times K$ identity matrix. Notably, the adversarial and unsupervised branches are only employed during training and are discarded at inference time, ensuring a low memory footprint suitable for edge devices. We fix the individual means, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$, of the Gaussian distributions, defining a one-to-one mapping f between each possible one-hot encoded label, \mathbf{e}_i , and the corresponding vector, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i \in \mathbb{R}^K$, such that $\|\boldsymbol{\mu}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_j\|_2 > M$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i \in \mathcal{S}_M$, where $\|\cdot\|_2$ is the Euclidean norm and \mathcal{S}_M is the K -dimensional hypersphere of radius M .

After computing $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$, we sample from the distribution $\mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_i, \mathbf{I}_K)$, concatenate the result with the one-hot encoded label vector, and input it to the discriminator as a *positive* example, that is, a sample coming from the prior distribution $p(\mathbf{z})$. At the same time, the concatenation of the latent \mathbf{z} with the one-hot label vector is provided as a *negative* example, i.e., a sample coming from the posterior probability generated by the encoder $q(\mathbf{z})$.

Model training. The training procedure of PCAA consists of two sequential optimization stages, namely *feature extraction* and *regularization*. In the feature extraction step, the Encoder, the Supervised, and the Unsupervised branches are jointly optimized using as loss function the sum of a cross-entropy loss for the supervised component and the average Chamfer distance between the reconstructed and original point cloud sequences for the unsupervised one [122], [132]. By minimizing the total loss function, PCAA learns to extract features that account for both class information and intrinsic patterns in the data, such as the walking style or body features of the subjects.

In the regularization stage, the parameters of the Discriminator are updated according to a Wasserstein criterion with gradient penalty [133].

We remark that the training phase is only carried out using the known dataset \mathcal{K} , using random training, validation, and test splits with a (0.8, 0.1, 0.1) ratio. For both stages of training, we employed the Adam optimizer [134] with learning rate $\eta = 10^{-4}$. All the models are implemented in PyTorch [135] and trained on an NVIDIA RTX 3080 GPU. The code implementation is publicly available at https://github.com/rmazzier/OpenSetGaitRecognition_PCAA.

Unknown subject detection. To distinguish known subjects from unknown ones during inference, we propose a novel subject detection algorithm based on the statistical properties of the feature space learned by PCAA. We exploit the fact that, after training, feature vectors extracted from radar traces of subject i follow a normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_i, \mathbf{I}_K)$, where the mean vectors $\{\boldsymbol{\mu}_i\}_{i=1}^M$ were deterministically chosen before training. We can therefore define the *known distribution*, as a mixture of Normal Gaussian distributions with equal weights $1/M$. The algorithm proceeds as follows. We first loop through the sequences $\mathbf{X}_{1:N_i}[t]$, for $t = 1, \dots, k$, and for each one we compute the closed-set prediction $\hat{y}[t]$ and a score $s[t] = p(\mathbf{z}[t])$, thus obtaining two sequences $\{\hat{y}[t]\}_{t=1}^k$ and $\{s[t]\}_{t=1}^k$. Then we check if more than half of the scores in $\{s[t]\}_{t=1}^k$ are greater than τ_p . If so, we exit the procedure, returning the most frequent prediction, otherwise, the subject is classified as unknown. The threshold τ_p is computed by applying a secondary procedure. First, we sample a random subject identifier $c \in S_U$ and define $\mathcal{U}^* = \{(\mathbf{X}_{1:N_i}, \mathbf{y}) : \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{e}_c\} \subset \mathcal{U}$. We then compute the scores of all samples in \mathcal{K} and \mathcal{U}^* . Finally, we set τ_p to the threshold between the two score distributions that maximizes the true positive rate and minimizes the false positive rate.

In practice, the choice of the threshold τ_p requires the presence of only one additional subject outside of S_K , which can be seen as an additional requirement for system calibration. In our simulations, we draw it from the set of unknown subjects, and then run the final novel subject detection procedure on the newly defined set of unknown subjects $\mathcal{U} \setminus \mathcal{U}^*$.

4.1.1.5. Experimental results

Evaluation metrics.

The difficulty of open-set classification problems depends on the ratio between the number of unknown and known subjects, $|S_U|/|S_K|$. The larger this ratio, the higher the difficulty since the OSGR model faces a larger number of unknown subjects with respect to the ones used for training. In [125], the authors propose the *openness* value to express the OSGR difficulty with a quantity in the range [0, 1). Openness is defined as

$$\text{Openness} = 1 - \sqrt{\frac{2|S_K|}{2|S_K| + |S_U|}}, \quad (4.1)$$

where values closer to 1 represent higher difficulty. In the following, we express the openness in %. Moreover, we use the F1 score aggregated over all classes as follows [136]

$$\text{F1} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{2\text{TP}_i}{2\text{TP}_i + \text{FP}_i + \text{FN}_i} \quad (4.2)$$

where $N = |S_K| + 1$ is the total number of classes, and TP_i , FP_i , and FN_i represent the true positives, false positives, and false negatives for class i , respectively.

Performance evaluation.

In this section, we compare PCAA to existing solutions in terms of predictive performance.

Methodology and choice of the baselines: To the best of our knowledge, our approach is the first to tackle the OSGR task from spatio-temporal point clouds. We identify the most recent state-of-the-art approaches for OSGR, namely OR-CED [123] and L-GM [137], to use as baselines for our experiments. These methods are designed for μD spectrograms, so we introduce a variation of each baseline approach, adapted for point-cloud processing. We will denote these two variants of OR-CED and L-GM as PC-OR-CED and PC-L-GM, respectively.

Results discussion: We evaluate the performance of all models under different levels of openness to test their robustness to more challenging scenarios. We also report the performance of PCAA with different values of k for the novel subject detection phase. Fig. 4.3 shows the performance of PCAA against the benchmarks. We average our results over $n_{\text{test}} = 5$ different trials, each employing a different dataset partitioning $(\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{U})$. We

Figure 4.3: OSGR macro-averaged F1 scores of OR-CED, L-GM, PCAA, PC-OR-CED and PC-L-GM, for different levels of openness. We also vary the number of aggregation steps k .

report the mean F1-score value along with a measure of the dispersion of the results, obtained as $\sigma/\sqrt{n_{\text{test}}}$, where σ is the standard deviation of the F1-scores over the n_{test} trials.

Additionally, our approach exhibits a clear trend of improved performance as the value of k increases. This behavior represents one of the key advantages of our method over existing ones, as it enables users to balance inference speed and accuracy in the OSGR task by adjusting k accordingly.

Time and memory efficiency.

To demonstrate the computational and memory efficiency of our approach, we report the observed metrics regarding training and inference times, and memory usage in Tab. 4.1. The reported values show that our approach exhibits negligible inference times, i.e., in the order of milliseconds, if compared to the actual duration of the input point cloud sequences, which include a few seconds of human gait information. This holds even for higher values of k . Moreover, PCAA has a remarkably low memory footprint, both in terms of model parameters and input point cloud representations. These features make our approach suitable for edge computing applications involving resource-constrained devices.

Table 4.1: Time and memory requirements for PCAA. Training times are reported for different values of S_K , the number of subjects present in the training set. Inference times and input sizes are reported assuming input batches of k samples, for different values of k .

Metric [unit]	Case	Value
Training time [min]	$S_K = 2$	28.83 ± 0.66
	$S_K = 4$	57.15 ± 0.68
	$S_K = 6$	86.41 ± 2.02
	$S_K = 8$	119.58 ± 3.06
Inference time [ms]	$k = 1$	2.76 ± 0.43
	$k = 2$	5.10 ± 0.73
	$k = 4$	9.63 ± 1.31
	$k = 6$	14.02 ± 1.82
Input size [MB]	$k = 1$	0.069
	$k = 2$	0.137
	$k = 4$	0.275
	$k = 6$	0.412
Model size [MB]	Encoder	9.305
	Decoder*	821.155
	Discriminator*	0.017

* Not used during inference

4.1.2. Preliminary investigation of SNN models for ISAC

This activity focuses on the processing of spatio-temporal point clouds with Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) and the estimation of their energy efficiency. In this section, we will provide a review on the state-of-the-art related to these domains to understand the context and main contribution of this work.

The application of learning models on point clouds is not straightforward due to the unordered and sparse representation of this structure. Originally, point cloud processing was done manually based on specific needs and often relied on machine learning-based classifiers such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), AdaBoost, Random Forest (RF). An important contribution that has radically changed the processing of point clouds is PointNet [138], a deep learning architecture that directly takes point clouds as inputs without the need for preprocessing or manual feature extraction. This was then extended by PointNet++ [139] to learn deep point set features efficiently and robustly by introducing hierarchical feature learning. However, point clouds are often the result of modern systems that employ real-time depth sensors, such as LiDAR, and come as a temporal sequence of point clouds. Thus, directly processing spatio-temporal point clouds becomes a new challenging task, which requires both the ability to process spatial and temporal features. Since PointNet was originally designed for static point clouds, other contributions, such as [128], extend the PointNet architecture by adding a temporal convolution block to extract meaningful features from temporal sequences of sparse point-cloud data. Recent approaches, such as [140], are based on a transformer-like architecture that exploits the attention mechanism and temporal contexts to predict future point cloud sequences. However, these architectures are very energy intensive, which is challenging in particular for edge devices and IoT systems, where low energy is crucial.

4.1.2.1. Relevant work

To address this critical need for energy efficiency, we explore the use of Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs), a promising energy-efficient alternative to standard artificial neural networks (ANNs). Unlike traditional ANNs, SNNs leverage sparse operations in an event-based fashion, performing operations with sparse binary data, especially on neuromorphic hardware [141]. Recent results show that SNNs can be used efficiently for complex classification tasks [142], achieving comparable results to their ANNs counterparts with much less energy consumption. However, the application of SNNs to point clouds remains a developing area of research. Existing approaches, such as Spiking PointNet [143] and SpikePoint [144], have shown initial promise. A common strategy in these approaches is the conversion of existing ANNs architectures into SNNs architectures simply by substituting the activation functions with LIF neurons. This activity will focus on designing and training an SNN architecture for spatio-temporal point clouds classification directly in the spiking domain, by exploiting the intrinsic temporal dimension of SNNs to perform efficient feature extraction of temporal sequences.

Although SNNs offer a promising path to energy efficiency, accurately estimating and optimizing their energy consumption remains a significant challenge. Standard computational cost metrics for ANNs, such as the count of floating-point operations (FLOPs) or multiply-accumulate (MAC) operations, are insufficient for SNNs. These metrics do not capture the event-driven, sparse nature of SNN computation and can lead to incorrect and oversimplified estimations. A first pioneering work [145] proposes an analytical framework to estimate and compare the energy consumption of SNNs based on synaptic operations, memory accesses, and memory addressing costs. The proposed approach tries to be independent of the hardware specification but relies on some strong hardware and memory design assumptions.

4.1.2.2. Use within MultiX

MultiX will build upon the framework in [145] by extending the analytical equations and lifting some critical assumptions. Our first step will consist of modifying the NN architecture in Section 4.1.1 into a SNN, optimizing its energy efficiency based on an analytical model of its energy consumption. This will serve as a baseline architecture to perform low-energy ISAC functions based on neuromorphic NNs.

4.1.3. Simultaneous localisation and detection of human indoors using FR1

4.1.3.1. Introduction

ISAC unifies two traditionally separate wireless functions, environmental sensing and data delivery, within a single physical-layer stack and spectral footprint. In an ISAC receiver, the baseband pipeline that ordinarily serves demodulation (e.g., synchronization, FFT, channel estimation) is repurposed to extract physical insights

such as range, angle, and motion from the very waveforms used for connectivity. This co-design reduces hardware and spectrum cost, eliminates duplicate front-ends, and enables low-latency situational awareness that is tightly synchronized with network traffic.

In wideband multicarrier systems operating in FR1, the PDP reveals a sparse set of resolvable multipath components. The strongest lobe (the “primary peak”) is usually associated with the LoS or dominant reflector, while additional lobes (“secondary peaks”) encode room geometry and human-induced reflections. By instrumenting the PDP at frame rate and converting peaks into a structured event stream, we learn a direct mapping from peak constellations to application-level latent variables, here, *object presence* and *discrete location index*. Compared to classical radar pipelines that rely on calibration and parameter-sensitive detection algorithms such as Constant False Alarm Rate (CFAR), our approach is robust to clock drift, dynamic multipath, and modest domain shift. Compared to end-to-end IQ neural nets, it is far lighter and interpretable because it operates on PHY-informed low-rate features made available by the PHY.

4.1.3.2. Motivation

Classical indoor sensing stacks require precise calibration, hand-made thresholds, and geometric inversion to estimate range and angle. Such pipelines degrade in offices and labs with moving users, vibrating fixtures, or frequency offsets from commodity oscillators. Conversely, purely data-driven methods that ingest raw IQ streams demand high compute, large memories, and heavy fronthaul. We seek a practical middle ground: *semantically rich yet compact* features that the PHY already exposes (peaks and PDP statistics), coupled with a lightweight attention network that is robust to missing peaks, reordering, and small frequency offsets. This preserves interpretability, minimizes bandwidth between GNU Radio and the AI stack, and scales to embedded deployments. It also naturally supports *presence gating*: only when the model is confident that a target exists do we emit a location hypothesis, suppressing false alarms in feature-sparse frames.

4.1.3.3. Problem Statement

Let each ISAC frame produce a PDP sampled on a delay grid $\mathcal{T} = \{0, \dots, T - 1\}$. A peak extractor returns a *primary peak* and up to K *secondary peaks*. Denote primary location $L_0 \in \mathcal{T}$ with magnitude A_0 and phase ϕ_0 , and secondary tuples $\{(L_i, A_i, \phi_i)\}_{i=1}^K$. We define the signed offset

$$\Delta_i \triangleq \text{wrap}_B(L_i - L_0) \in \left(-\frac{B}{2}, \frac{B}{2}\right], \quad (4.3)$$

where $\text{wrap}_B(\cdot)$ optionally maps differences on a ring of size B (no wrapping if $B = 0$). Each frame is annotated by a binary presence label $y \in \{0, 1\}$ and, when present, by a discrete location class $\ell \in \{0, \dots, C - 1\}$. The learning task is to estimate the posterior $p(y=1 \mid \mathbf{x})$ and $p(\ell \mid \mathbf{x}, y=1)$ from the peak set $\mathbf{x} = \{(A_0), (A_i, \Delta_i, \phi_i)\}_{i=1}^K$ and low-dimensional PDP statistics.

4.1.3.4. Contributions

- **Peak-fusion representation.** We introduce a tokenization that converts unordered peaks into a short sequence of tokens with *signed delay offsets* relative to the primary lobe. The representation is compact (Mbit/s scale) but retains geometric information crucial for localization.
- **Latency- and drift-robust architecture.** A compact Transformer encoder with depthwise preconditioning and cross-attention pooling consumes variable-length peak sets and yields presence and location logits. Neighbor-smoothed targets improve sample efficiency for adjacent classes on a circular grid.
- **Training–inference parity.** We design a schema and runtime Comma Separated Values (CSV) that guarantees identical preprocessing between offline training and real-time inference: fixed secondary-peak groups, sorting by peak number, *signed* offsets computed from locations, and amplitude scaling tied to the learned normalizer.
- **Operational pipeline;** We implement an end-to-end stack from GNU Radio to Python inference using ZeroMQ/MessagePack for transport and a resilient subscriber that writes fixed-width CSV or streams events directly to the model.

Figure 4.4: End-to-end ISAC pipeline (*System Model*). IQ is converted to peak events in GNU Radio and transported to the AI model via ZeroMQ. Publishing peaks instead of raw IQ reduces fronthaul by orders of magnitude while preserving geometry.

4.1.3.5. System Model

Signal and PDP extraction: We consider a multicarrier probing waveform (e.g., OFDM with a Zadoff–Chu preamble) transmitted periodically. The discrete-time baseband channel $h[n] = \sum_p \alpha_p \delta[n - \tau_p]$ produces a PDP $P[\tau] = \mathbb{E}\{|h[\tau]|^2\}$ after averaging and windowing. A peak-finder returns a primary (L_0, A_0, ϕ_0) and a set of secondaries $\{(L_i, A_i, \phi_i)\}$. Additionally, we compute light-weight features $\mu_{\text{ex}}, \sigma_{\text{rms}}, \tau_{\text{max}}$ summarizing the PDP energy spread.

Event representation and signed distances: To obtain a geometry-invariant descriptor, we express each secondary in the primary reference frame using

$$\Delta_i = \begin{cases} L_i - L_0, & B = 0, \\ ((L_i - L_0) + \frac{B}{2}) \bmod B - \frac{B}{2}, & B > 0. \end{cases}$$

This choice (i) removes absolute timing drift, (ii) respects the cyclic grid if applicable, and (iii) matches the semantics used in training. Magnitudes are nonnegative by construction, while signed offsets are roughly symmetric; the model therefore learns complementary statistics.

End-to-end sensing-to-AI pipeline: Fig. 4.4 summarizes the deployed pipeline and indicative data rates observed on our testbed. A USRP source produces ~6.5 Gbps of complex samples which are processed on a *Compute Host* by a GNU Radio flowgraph: (i) correlation with a known preamble sequence, (ii) peak extraction (primary and multiple secondaries), and (iii) computation of PDP summary metrics. Instead of pushing raw IQ, we publish *peak events*, i.e., primary attributes and a fixed number of secondary tuples—via a ZeroMQ publisher (ZMQ Pub). This reduces fronthaul to ~200 Mbps under typical frame rates. A *GPU Host* subscribes to this stream (ZMQ Sub), runs the AI model in micro-batches, and emits presence/location hypotheses. Finally, decisions and metadata are logged to a database and optionally displayed in a visualization front-end at < 1 Mbps. The entire chain is stateless between frames and achieves sub-millisecond end-to-end latency per event.

4.1.3.6. Learning Model

Tokenization and positional encoding: Each secondary peak becomes a token with a feature vector

$$\mathbf{f}_i = [A_i, \Delta_i, \phi_i, \mu_{\text{ex}}, \sigma_{\text{rms}}, \tau_{\text{max}}, A_0],$$

optionally augmented by Fourier positional features $\gamma(\Delta_i) \in \mathbb{R}^{2D}$ with frequencies $\{\omega_d\}_{d=1}^D$

$$\gamma(\Delta) = [\cos(\omega_1 \Delta), \sin(\omega_1 \Delta), \dots, \cos(\omega_D \Delta), \sin(\omega_D \Delta)].$$

The tokenizer yields a variable-length sequence $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times F}$, where $T \leq K_{\text{max}}$ and F is the feature dimension. A boolean padding mask marks absent tokens.

Network architecture: We adopt a compact *Transformer architecture*:

1. Linear projection $\mathbb{R}^F \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ plus a type embedding and (optional) Fourier projection.
2. Depthwise separable 1-D convolution along the token axis, which denoises local token neighborhoods while preserving permutation stability induced by sorting.
3. A L -layer Transformer encoder (norm-first) with h heads and feedforward width d_{ff} .
4. Cross-attention pooling with Q learnable latent queries; pooled embedding $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the mean over latent outputs.
5. Two heads: (i) presence logit $g(\mathbf{z}) \in \mathbb{R}$, (ii) location logits $\ell(\mathbf{z}) \in \mathbb{R}^C$.

The design is *size-agnostic*, accepting any number of secondaries up to a small cap—important when the peak detector fires many lobes in rich multipath.

Training objectives: Presence uses class-balanced binary cross-entropy (BCE)

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{pres}} = \text{BCEWithLogits}(g(\mathbf{z}), y; \text{pos_weight}).$$

For location, we use neighbor-smoothed targets on the location ring to share probability mass with adjacent classes and improve sample efficiency

$$\tilde{\mathbf{y}} = (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{e}_\ell + \frac{\alpha}{2} (\mathbf{e}_{(\ell-1) \bmod C} + \mathbf{e}_{(\ell+1) \bmod C}), \quad \mathcal{L}_{\text{loc}} = -\tilde{\mathbf{y}}^\top \log \text{softmax}(\ell(\mathbf{z})),$$

where we recall that \mathbf{e}_i is the one-hot encoded version of the integer class label. The final loss is $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{pres}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{loc}} \cdot \chi(y=1)$, where $\chi(\cdot)$ is the indicator function. We train with AdamW, cosine decay with warmup, optional gradient clipping, and mixed precision on GPU.

4.1.3.7. Experimental Setup

Fig. 4.5 shows the floor plan of the primary evaluation site (conference room). A mannequin was coated with a special liquid to emulate human-skin reflection characteristics. The objective was to train and validate the model using the mannequin as a controlled surrogate for a person so that the data cover realistic human reflectivity while allowing repeatable experiments.

Tx/Rx placement. A single transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) pair are installed at fixed points along one side of the room (see Fig. 4.5); both use USRPs synchronized locally. The probing waveform operates in FR1 with a sufficient bandwidth to resolve multiple indoor paths.

Location grid and orientations. A set of discrete locations (x marks) was defined around the table to induce diversity in direct and reflected paths. For each valid location, the mannequin was oriented to face each of the four cardinal directions (N/E/S/W) to vary the radar cross-section. We also captured an “empty room” baseline at multiple times to sample background multipath without a target.

Samples and duration. For each (location, orientation) configuration, we collected short bursts of approximately 4 s. Each burst yields thousands of frames; these are then converted into peak events by the GNU Radio flowgraph and fed to the training/inference pipeline described earlier.

4.1.3.8. Datasets

Offline (training) CSVs: We aggregate multiple experiment files whose names encode labels. A robust CSV parser (i) deduplicates headers, (ii) detects columns by regex and statistics, and (iii) constructs per-frame JSONL rows with *signed* distances and amplitudes. Primary amplitude A_0 is included when available. Files are split per source with a fixed seed to prevent leakage. After preprocessing, the training corpus comprises on the order of 10^5 – 10^6 frames, providing a healthy balance of present/absent examples and coverage across C location classes.

Online subscriber CSV: The real-time subscriber writes a fixed-width schema with columns for the time stamps, phase and magnitudes of the primary peaks, phase and magnitudes of the secondary peaks, and the relative delays between secondary and primary peaks. The feature sets also included distances that are the *signed offsets* computed as Δ_i ; secondary peaks are sorted by peak order. This parity guarantees that the runtime tokenizer receives identically distributed features.

Normalization: Amplitude channels are standardized using statistics fitted *only* on the training set and stored in the checkpoint; inference reuses these scalars. Offsets are left in native grid units and, when applicable, wrapped to $(-B/2, B/2]$ to stabilize learning across boundary classes.

Figure 4.5: Experimental layout and discrete Isaak locations (conference room). Tx/Rx are fixed; Isaak stands at the marked positions and faces N/E/S/W to diversify reflections.

4.1.3.9. Results

Presence detection: Fig. 4.7 shows well-separated histograms of presence probabilities for negative and positive frames. Scores cluster near 0 for absent and near 1 for present, yielding ROC–AUC ≈ 0.999 and average precision near unity under typical operating points. Such separation enables the *presence-gating* strategy used throughout: we only emit a location when $p(y=1|\mathbf{x}) \geq \tau$ (e.g., $\tau=0.5$), which in practice removes spurious localizations in feature-sparse frames.

Location classification: Conditioned on presence, the location confusion matrix in Fig. 4.6 is almost perfectly diagonal across $C=5$ discrete locations. Neighbor class confusions are negligible; this validates the signed-offset representation and the neighbor-smoothed loss on a ring. In deployments with more than five classes, we observe graceful degradation with most errors falling to adjacent bins, which is consistent with physical geometry.

Calibration and score distributions: Fig. 4.8 overlays score histograms at a finer scale. The model exhibits sharp, nearly bimodal behavior, yet keeps a small fraction of uncertain frames around $p \approx 0.1-0.2$ and $p \approx 0.8-0.9$; these tend to correspond to near-threshold SNR or ambiguous peak constellations (e.g., specular paths of similar amplitude).

Cross-site comparison: In a larger lab with more extensive data collection, presence and location performance (Fig. 4.7 and Fig. 4.6) are superior to those obtained in a smaller lab (Fig. 4.8). This difference is expected: the larger site provided more diverse training samples and a broader distribution of multipath geometries, allowing the model to learn more discriminative peak patterns. The smaller lab used fewer samples; consequently, the fitted normalizers and decision boundaries are less data-rich, and the histograms show slightly heavier tails.

4.1.3.10. Conclusion

The proposed peak-fusion approach leverages PHY-side sparsity and compact learned attention to achieve accurate presence detection and discrete localization from a single ISAC pipeline. The key is *parity*: represent online frames exactly as in training (signed offsets, sorted fixed groups, identical scaling). With this discipline,

Figure 4.6: Presence-gated location confusion matrix ($C=5$ classes). Values on the diagonal are ≈ 1.00 .

Figure 4.7: Presence probability histogram for absent/present frames; strong separation enables robust gating. (Performance here corresponds to the larger site with more data).

we obtain highly confident, low-latency predictions that are robust to realistic multipath and runtime variability. The end-to-end pipeline further demonstrates that useful sensing can be achieved with modest fronthaul and compute by publishing structured peaks instead of raw IQ.

4.2. Resource optimization with AI

The objective of this subtask is to exploit AI models to improve energy efficiency and resource allocation in ISAC-enabled networks.

Within this subtask, we carried out the following two research activities.

- E2E energy-aware ISAC service delivery (Section 4.2.1). In this activity, we develop an architecture for sensing data exchange between the RAN and Core Network (CN) that is *energy-aware*. The architecture has been experimentally validated, showing its effectiveness to support ISAC at a network-level.
- Energy and resource usage optimization for ISAC using Reinforcement Learning (RL) (Section 4.2.2). In this activity, we develop a RL framework for resource allocation in RIS-enabled ISAC networks. The energy consumption is explicitly optimized by including it in the reward function for the RL agent.

Figure 4.8: Fine-grained presence score distributions from a smaller lab with fewer samples; performance is slightly worse due to limited data diversity.

4.2.1. E2E energy aware ISAC service delivery

4.2.1.1. Introduction and motivation

The 6G vision involves a widely extended connectivity scale of a huge number of end devices, extreme and varying levels of capacity and bandwidth granularity, increased degree of mobility, and a great variety of services with strict sustainability, scalability, and autonomy goals. In this context, 6G is expected to offer improved performance in comparison to 5th Generation Communications (5G) with regards to connectivity, peak data rates, latency, energy efficiency, etc., integrating together the most advanced and heterogeneous network and compute technologies. It will also offer increased intelligence and flexibility through the wide adoption of AI/ML techniques. However, these will come at the expense of increased complexity, imposing the need for autonomous operation and self-optimisation capabilities.

In addition, 6G will offer new and enhanced capabilities such as localisation, and monitoring of objects, and sensing of the surrounding environment using ISAC services. ISAC performs sensing and monitoring of the surrounding environment through the mobile communications infrastructure without the need of extra monitoring devices and equipment. In this context, the network acts as a distributed “radar” sensor, exploiting its own radio signals to sense and comprehend the surrounding physical world. The echoes (reflections) and scattering of wireless signals predominantly transmitted for communication purposes provide information related to the characteristics of the environment and/or objects therein. The sensing data collected and processed by the network can then be leveraged to enhance the network’s operations, augment existing services such as XR and digital twinning, and enable new services, such as object detection and tracking, along with imaging and environment reconstruction.

ISAC-enabled mobile communication systems demand additional complexity in signal processing, but require the collection and aggregation of huge volumes of synchronized IQ reflected (echo) streams that need to be processed to extract information on the sensed environment. This processing can only be performed at edge servers, introducing the need to transport the IQ streams over flexible high-capacity transport networks. In these environments, transport networks are expected to play a more important and challenging role compared to those in 5G.

Towards this direction, transport networks can facilitate 6G ISAC services and how these services affect the requirements and technical specifications that the 6G transport network needs to support, as shown in Fig. 4.9. According to this, 6G Base Stations (BSs) generate communication signals reflected on “objects” located in the surrounding area, creating IQ echo streams. These IQ echo streams are transmitted in the form of uplink fronthaul streams and are redirected to m-SePF and SeSF for storage and processing. An AI-assisted m-SePF can be used to analyze the quality of the IQ echo streams and decide which IQ streams can be used to support the required sensing. The IQ streams that are not carrying useful information are dropped. The results of the m-SePF, including only useful IQ streams, are passed to the network orchestrator through SeEF, which decides the optimal transport network configuration to support both communication and sensing services. To perform this, the orchestrator solves the optical transport network optimization problem considering both communication (i.e., fronthaul backhaul) and sensing (IQ echo streams) services. The identified configuration

Figure 4.9: Transport Network supporting sensing services.

is then executed by the Software Defined Networking (SDN) control of the transport network.

4.2.1.2. Contribution

In view of this, we propose and experimentally validate an architecture exploiting an optical transport network that interconnects RAN and CN domains, to facilitate joint support of sensing and communication services. Sensing is performed based on the principle of a distributed passive wireless radar. According to this, 6G BS generate communication signals reflected on “objects” located in the surrounding area, creating IQ echo streams. These IQ echo streams are transmitted in the form of uplink fronthaul streams and are redirected to a Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) node for storage and processing. A sensing app has been purposely developed to analyze the quality of the IQ echo streams at the MEC and decide which IQ streams can be used to support the required sensing. The IQ streams that are not carrying useful information are dropped. The sensing app output, including only useful IQ streams, is passed to the network orchestrator that decides the optimal transport network configuration to support both communication and sensing services. To achieve this, based on past measurements, an AI model is used to predict the trajectory of the moving targets and identify the number and resources per RU that can be allocated for sensing. Based on this information, the orchestrator solves the optical transport network optimization problem considering both communication (i.e., fronthaul backhaul) and sensing (IQ echo streams) services. The identified configuration is then executed by the Software Defined Network (SDN) control of the optical transport network. The proposed architecture has been experimentally implemented and evaluated using a platform that comprises actual hardware for the optical transport network, compute servers, and wireless transceivers. The wireless channel (over the air transmission) is emulated through the GNU Radio platform.

4.2.1.3. Use within MultiX

The main objective of this development is to enhance the m-SePF repository of MultiX with the capability of energy-aware optimal routing decisions, which are executed by the transport network SDN controller to establish optimal network connectivity.

4.2.2. Energy and resource usage optimization for ISAC using RL

4.2.2.1. Introduction and motivation.

NEC and i2CAT have worked together on a RL framework that plans the deployment or selective activation of network infrastructure devices under explicit resource and energy constraints, to jointly optimize communication coverage and localization accuracy for ISAC. Unlike legacy strategies that pursue only SNR or only localization accuracy, our proposal pursues a tunable multi-objective solution and enforces hard resource limits (cost/power), enabling near-Pareto-optimal designs that respect practical energy consumption limits and capital and operational expenditure ceilings. The key element of our proposal is an RL agent, which searches the combinatorial design space of device placements or activations while being guided by a metric that considers at the same time both ISAC performance and resource usage.

4.2.2.2. Contribution.

Our proposal treats BSs, RISs and any other available device with networking or sensing capabilities as heterogeneous sensing/coverage assets: BSs provide coverage but can also contribute with Time of Arrival (ToA) measurements, RISs contribute with AoA measurements, but they also extend BS coverage and ToA measurements via controllable reflections, while other devices can be modeled in the system too. Each sensor provides a likelihood over user position, and individual likelihoods are fused into a single spatial Probability Density Function (PDF). The computed FI of the fused PDF yields a CRLB-derived localization bound, while a link budget (taking into account BS properties and RIS array gains) produces SNR maps. This factorization keeps the method agnostic to specific device properties or controller internals and takes LoS and NLoS settings, modeling them as shadow maps.

4.2.2.3. Energy- and budget-aware objective.

We adopt a joint score

$$M(\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{x}) = \alpha L(\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{x}) + (1 - \alpha) C(\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{x}),$$

where \mathbf{d} is the deployment vector, L is a score map, based on the CRLB achievable by a subset of the available devices and C is a score map based on the SNR with realistic (SNR_{\min} , SNR_{\max}) thresholds. Both aspects are balanced with the α parameter. Resource usage ($\kappa(\mathbf{d})$) enters as a feasibility constraint $\kappa(\mathbf{d}) \leq \beta$ (which models either the maximum energy budget or capital expenditure considerations) to optimize *performance-per-watt* or return of investment. This makes the search policy sensitive to where each watt or installation and running costs deliver maximal ISAC capabilities.

4.2.2.4. Energy/resource implications.

Three elements drive energy and resource efficiency: (i) *placement efficiency*, where fewer, better-located devices reduce energy consumption and device usage, (ii) *metric shaping*, where logistic mappings of the core variables (SNR and CRLB) focus optimization where extra resources meaningfully improve any relevant KPI, and (iii) *budget-curve exploration*, where the solution cache enables rapid sweep of different values of β to pick the desired point of the performance–cost curve. Together, these yield device selections that meet ISAC targets with minimal active elements and controller power.

4.2.2.5. Use within MultiX

Our proposal runs in the MultiX structure as a planning service that proposes energy/budget-aware device layout or selections (including but not limited to BS and RIS) for ISAC. These solutions can be consumed to online tune the active infrastructure according to instantaneous performance requirements, allowing a flexible architecture to improve sustainability.

4.3. Multi-modal sensing

The objective of this subtask is to develop multi-modal sensing enablers for the MPS, which constitutes a single research activity.

Multi-modal sensing is a process that integrates information from disparate data sources to construct a more comprehensive and robust understanding of a phenomenon or environment. The fundamental premise of this approach is the recognition that no single sensor can provide a complete picture of a complex system. By combining both complementary and redundant information, multi-modal systems can overcome the inherent limitations of each modality, leading to significant improvements in accuracy, robustness, and reliability. Each modality contributes a unique view of the world, but each is also fundamentally flawed in isolation [146].

- *Wi-Fi sensing*. By analysing CSI, Wi-Fi sensing passively infers motion and presence via subtle propagation changes caused by human bodies and objects. Its advantages are ubiquity and low cost; its main limitations are lower spatial resolution and ambiguity about what moved and where, which complicate fusion with high-resolution sensors.

- *Radar*. Active RF sensing provides accurate range/Doppler estimates and remains robust in adverse weather (fog, rain, low light). Its constraints are modest spatial resolution and limited semantic detail, which motivates pairing with vision information.
- *Cameras*. Vision offers high spatial detail for classification and scene understanding, but performance degrades under low light, glare, precipitation, and occlusions; privacy constraints further motivate selective use and additional processing.

4.3.1. Objectives and activities

The objective of Multi-modal Sensing in MultiX is to harness the diversity of sensing modalities, spanning both 3GPP and non-3GPP domains, to provide reliable perception across environments and operating conditions. Concretely, MultiX will (i) enhance environmental perception and situational awareness in 6G-RAN by fusing radio and visual inputs; (ii) improve robustness to noise, occlusions, and modality-specific limitations through complementary fusion; and (iii) enable application features such as contact-free health monitoring, immersive XR, and industrial digital twins under an ISAC paradigm aligned with the project's architecture.

4.3.2. State of the Art of Multi-modal sensing

Multi-modal sensing integrates heterogeneous data to yield richer, more reliable representations via early (signal/feature-level), intermediate (shared-representation), or late (decision-level) fusion. Key technical challenges remain: aligning asynchronous streams with different formats, sampling rates, and reference frames [147]; sustaining operation when sensors intermittently fail or deliver corrupted data [148, 149]; and selecting fusion strategies that balance robustness with expressivity, since late fusion tolerates missing data but can underuse cross-modal interactions while early fusion risks the curse of dimensionality in limited-data regimes [150]. A further challenge is privacy: combining modalities can inadvertently reveal unintended attributes, so consent and governance must be modality-granular and context-aware [151]. Promising research directions include online/target-free calibration for continuous re-registration in dynamic scenes; weakly/partially paired pre-training that exploits imperfect correspondences for scalable alignment; modality-invariant and expandable alignment to onboard or drop sensors without full retraining; and privacy-preserving learning to keep raw sensitive data local while still learning robust global models.

4.3.2.1. Use within MultiX

Within MultiX, multi-modal algorithms will consume sensing information exposed by WP3 components (e.g., CSI and higher-level RF features) together with non-3GPP data (e.g., LiDAR, motion-capture cameras, IMUs), for the use cases of presence detection, activity recognition, and vital signs monitoring.

4.4. AI/GenAI for multi-band multi-static

The objective of this subtask is to explore the adaptation of the latest results in AI and GenAI to the MultiX objectives of enabling multi-band and multi-static sensing.

Within this subtask, we carried out the following two research activities.

- An analysis of the state of the art on multi-band sensing with AI (Section 4.4.1). In this activity, we discuss our preliminary investigation of the use of GenAI to perform sensing with incomplete sensing data in the frequency and spatial domain. This scenario is of high practical importance since real ISAC data is often obtained in multiple disjoint frequency bands and by distributed network nodes. We present a literature review on the subject, highlighting the missing aspects in existing works, and formulate the problem of GenAI-based channel reconstruction.
- Predictive sensing data collection for sensing outage scenarios (Section 4.4.2). In this activity, we perform ISAC in environments where sensing observations are *intermittent* and present temporal gaps, which is realistic due to fluctuations of the channel or movement of obstacles. We explore the use of GenAI to improve the reconstruction of sensing information in the gaps, beyond what is feasible using standard predictors like Kalman filters.

4.4.1. State of the art on multi-band sensing with AI

Recently, the exploitation of multi-band CFR to perform wideband radar-like ranging in ISAC has gathered significant interest [6] to increase sensing resolution, as previously discussed in Section 2.1.1. There, we highlighted how one of the main problems to address in practical ISAC systems is the non-contiguity of subbands, which causes undesired artifacts in the sensing results.

AI, and especially generative AI, is a promising approach to address this problem by learning the target response across multiple bands from real radio measurements. Unlike standard signal processing approaches based on CS [6], or all-pole modeling [152] of the CFR, deep learning methods can directly extract relevant features of the multi-band CFR from real data, automatically learning to overcome phase impairments and frequency gaps. Moreover, in light of our discoveries in the FR3 measurement campaign detailed in Section 2.1.1, AI is also very promising to tackle the frequency anisotropy of complex targets, which has been ignored in the existing literature.

However, this potential also hides some research challenges to make the overall sensing system practical and general enough to apply to the wide range of possible ISAC channels and applications. Specifically, AI-based methods are intrinsically biased by the training dataset, which, in this case, could mean they can not generalize to (i) different hardware (with different phase impairments), (ii) different technologies, (iii) targets with different scattering properties.

In the next section, we provide a comprehensive discussion of the limited existing works on this aspect.

4.4.1.1. Relevant work

UWB-Fi [7, 153] is the first work to use a NN to tackle the multi-band sensing problem in the sub-6 GHz unlicensed spectrum. This is jointly trained to combine Wi-Fi signals obtained in multiple frequency bands with wide gaps and to remove phase non-idealities due to the hardware, which may prevent a coherent combination. The training of the NN model is carried out in a supervised fashion, using as target values for the network synthetic spectra that mimic the ones obtained by subspace-based methods such as MUSIC. The algorithm's performances are tested on multiple people sensing, demonstrating the feasibility of accurate multi-person respiration monitoring.

However, the powerful non-linear learning capabilities of the NN also make it quite impractical in realistic scenarios. Indeed, changing hardware, frequency band, or technology (OFDM vs SC) may require retraining the system, which is time-consuming and requires new data. UWB-Fi requires channel hopping among different Wi-Fi frequencies, which necessitates modifying the underlying communication protocol. Indeed, in practice, Wi-Fi does not natively perform such channel hopping process

To mitigate the above problem, the same authors proposed combining CS with NNs [7, 154], to introduce signal processing-based prior knowledge in the learning process. This is done by formulating the multi-band sensing problem as a missing measurements CS problem, where the non-contiguous subbands are treated as partial observations of the full spectrum. Then, specific NN layers are added to incorporate CS solvers into the learning model, using the concept of deep unfolding. In this framework, iterative CS optimization algorithms are replaced by deep NNs where each layer corresponds to one iteration of the algorithm. However, one limitation of this approach is that the training process remains supervised and focuses on reconstructing synthetic spectra. This does not exploit recent advances in generative AI where learning happens in an unsupervised way to learn the distribution of the real data. In multi-band ISAC, generative models could be exploited to learn from large amounts of CFR data collected across different bands and reconstruct the missing spectrum portions in the most statistically plausible way given the data. Moreover, the use of deep unfolding or other methods to introduce model-based prior knowledge into the learning process could be combined with generative learning approaches to ensure the generation of realistic outputs.

4.4.1.2. Envisioned GenAI use for multi-band, multi-static ISAC

Within T3.3, we will explore the use of GenAI to reconstruct the CFR of sensing channels over wide frequency or spatial gaps, as shown in Fig. 4.10. After collecting wideband CFR measurements, GenAI methods will be trained through the use of a reconstruction loss function to infer the channel in the frequency or spatial gaps, depending on the application. The acquisition of the CFR dataset is currently ongoing at IMDEA Networks with the collaboration of UNIPD.

Figure 4.10: Envisioned use of GenAI to reconstruct the channel response in non-observable frequency or spatial region.

4.4.1.3. Use within MultiX

The use of AI and GenAI for multi-band and multi-static ISAC will enhance the capabilities of the methods presented in T3.1, in Section 2.3.1 and Section 2.1.1 (for multi-band coherent processing), by allowing a more accurate modeling of the frequency anisotropy of real targets. Moreover, it will support the T3.2 efforts to develop multi-static and multi-technology ISAC, by enabling data-driven integration of sensing data from multiple points of view and radio technologies. If the exploration of GenAI techniques is successful, they will be considered for integration with PoC2.

4.4.2. Predictive sensing data collection for sensing outage scenarios

4.4.2.1. Challenges of sensing data processing

The collection, processing, and dissemination of sensing data in 6G—particularly under ISAC—can impose substantial signaling and computational burdens. Key drivers include (i) resource-allocation and control-plane signaling overhead; (ii) fusion of multi-modal, multi-stream observations; (iii) integration and orchestration of heterogeneous compute resources across the RAN, CN, and edge/cloud; and (iv) cross-entity coordination for sensing-data acquisition and exchange.

ISAC specifically necessitates intensive PHY-layer processing to derive sensing measurements, and individual sensing tasks may generate massive data volumes. As a result, raw measurements accumulated over time can be prohibitively large; transmitting them uplink from sensing receivers is inefficient, and the associated reporting/processing signaling becomes a bottleneck in already resource-constrained networks. To meet use-case requirements and sensing KPI targets, computation must be natively embedded in the 6G architecture via a dedicated computing and data-processing path spanning the RAN, CN, and edge/cloud infrastructure. Treating each participating entity—UE base stations (BSs), and CN functions—as a computational node enables in-network fusion and processing but demands tight coordination and time synchronization. For example, locating and tracking automated guided vehicles (AGVs) on a factory floor while they execute tasks such as lifting or placement requires cooperative operation among BSs, UEs, and IoT devices across sequential task phases. Mobility of both targets and sensing receivers further complicates the scheduling and coordination of sensing activities [155].

The collection, processing, and exchange of sensing data impose substantial signaling and computational overheads, as outlined above. To conserve energy and scarce spectrum/compute resources in 6G systems, sensing data must be managed efficiently. We therefore propose a resource-aware framework for data acquisition, in-network preprocessing, and configuration that mitigates the aforementioned bottlenecks. While the mechanisms introduced here address key facets of the previously identified challenges, they do not fully resolve them; each problem warrants specialized analysis and, in some cases, distinct algorithmic treatments. Accordingly, our contribution should be viewed as an enabling framework for efficient data collection and configuration, upon which task-specific fusion, scheduling, control, and assurance methods can be layered; a comprehensive treatment of these aspects is left for future work.

4.4.2.2. Efficient Data Collection Framework

Let us denote a list of sensing measurements to be taken at a Sensing Receiver (SRx) for the i -th target at a given time t as,

$$\mathbf{x}_i(t) = [\tau_i(t), f_{d,i}(t), \mu_{d,i}(t), \phi_i(t), \theta_i(t), \sigma_i(t)], \quad (4.4)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_i(t)$ is the Sensing Data at time t , τ_i is delay, $f_{d,i}$ is the Doppler shift, $\mu_{d,i}$ is micro-Doppler, ϕ_i is the phase, θ_i is the orientation of the i^{th} target, and σ_i is the RCS of the i -th target. Sensing data in 6G originates as PHY-layer measurements that may aggregate multiple temporal samples. We denote each such aggregated measurement a Sensing Data Point (SDP). SDPs can be primitive (e.g., delay, Doppler, angle) or derived (e.g., radar cross section, which depends on target material, aspect, delay, and Doppler). Because PHY-layer sensing yields high-volume outputs, indiscriminate uplink reporting consumes energy and radio resources and inflates signaling overhead. Moreover, under adverse conditions—such as low SNR, NLoS, or high mobility—SDPs may not meet the accuracy or reliability targets of a given sensing task, making their transmission wasteful.

To address this, each sensing receiver (SRx, including UEs) performs local, task-aware quality assessment of every SDP and applies a reporting policy configured by the network (e.g., gNB or CN). The configuration specifies per-task thresholds and metrics such as SNR, CFAR detection/false-alarm characteristics, estimation variance or uncertainty measures, ambiguity-peak ratio, and completeness checks. Based on these criteria:

- SDPs that clearly meet quality targets are reported in compact form (e.g., features, detections, tracklets with confidence metadata) rather than as raw measurements.
- SDPs of marginal quality are used locally for fusion only and are not sent uplink.
- SDPs that fall below minimum quality triggers are discarded or re-sensed without first uploading data to determine that a retry is needed.

This quality gating reduces unnecessary traffic and enables distributed fusion close to where the data are generated. SRxs can combine qualified SDPs with other local sensing streams or co-located IoT data and export only concise state estimates, thereby relieving central processors and preserving radio resources. For latency-stringent applications, processing closer to the task improves timeliness in small-scale deployments. Overall, explicitly defining SDPs, evaluating their task-conditioned quality at the SRx, and enforcing lightweight reporting policies reduce signaling and energy costs while maintaining end-to-end performance.

4.4.2.3. Predictive Sensing Data Collection

Acquiring sensing measurements and fusing them—either within a single SRx or across multiple SRxs—can be computationally intensive, especially for long-horizon object tracking. This draws on limited ISAC power, compute, and spectrum resources. To improve efficiency, predictive sensing can be used to govern when and how Sensing Data are generated.

Short-lived NLoS or otherwise unreliable conditions often yield erroneous range (and related) estimates that degrade localization. If such low-utility intervals can be predicted in advance, the sensing front end can be duty-cycled—deactivated or placed in a low-power mode—during those windows. Unlike communications (where the next packet arrival cannot be predicted), ISAC often benefits from temporal coherence in target kinematics and environment dynamics, making short-term prediction feasible.

Predictive control reduces overhead on multiple fronts:

- Measurement load: fewer measurements imply fewer pilots/reference signals and lower control signaling when high-quality data are unlikely.
- Compute load: heavy operations (range–Doppler processing, micro-Doppler extraction, angle-of-arrival) can be skipped or downsampled, lowering CPU/GPU utilization.
- Interference/scheduling: staggering measurement activity across many SRxs mitigates mutual interference and control-plane congestion while preserving overall performance.

Candidate predictors include Kalman filtering, Gaussian processes, and time-series models using LSTM- or Transformer-based architectures. The network may provide SRxs with the prediction horizon and skip durations, configured periodically or aperiodically.

To assess impact, we consider a robotic-arm tracking scenario with intermittent occlusions (NLoS). We compare continuous sensing against predictive duty-cycling, evaluating energy consumption, reference-signal and reporting overhead, tracking error (position/velocity), and end-to-end latency.

We assume a single point of the robotic arm as a target. The target is moving within a 300 cm × 300 cm planar region. The state of the target can be represented as

$$\mathbf{x}_k = [x_k, y_k, v_{x,k}, v_{y,k}]^T \quad (4.5)$$

Figure 4.11: Prediction of target position using Kalman filter

where (x_k, y_k) is the position (in cm) and $(v_{x,k}, v_{y,k})$ is the velocity (in cm/timestep). We bound the target within the $[0, 300]$ cm region, and we reflect the target if it crosses the 0 cm or 300 cm boundaries in either dimension, reversing its velocity accordingly. This shows that when the target hits the boundary, it bounces off. At each time step k , the system measures the AoA as

$$\alpha_k = \arctan 2(y_k, x_k), \quad (4.6)$$

and the Radial Velocity (Doppler) as,

$$\text{radVel}_k = \frac{x_k v_{x,k} + y_k v_{y,k}}{\sqrt{x_k^2 + y_k^2}}. \quad (4.7)$$

Even though we do not measure the range of the object directly, these two quantities suffice to determine position over time. The angle α_k pinpoints the target’s bearing relative to the origin, while radial velocity indicates how quickly it moves toward or away from the sensing transmitter.

By tracking the evolution of α_k and radVel_k over multiple time steps, a Kalman Filter (KF) can infer both the radial distance and the transverse motion, thereby reconstructing (x_k, y_k) and $(v_{x,k}, v_{y,k})$.

We simulate near-constant velocity with Gaussian process noise and define *skip intervals* of 30–50 time steps during which both AoA and radVel readings are absent. The KF predicts in these intervals, leading to an increased estimation uncertainty. Once measurements resume, the update step rapidly corrects the filter’s state estimate, maintaining a reasonable RMSE despite high noise and extended skip periods. The results in Fig. 4.11 demonstrate that even without a direct range measurement, one can track a 2D target’s position effectively by fusing angle and Doppler over time.

GenAI methods are well-suited to predict sensing measurements not just target states—because they learn distributions over the measurement space itself (e.g., range–Doppler–angle cubes, channel state information, spectrograms). Unlike classical filters that propagate a single mean estimate, GenAI models produce calibrated ensembles that capture multi-modality arising from occlusions, abrupt maneuvers, or clutter. This ability to model plausible but distinct futures makes them particularly effective in ISAC settings where measurement processes are nonlinear, non-Gaussian, and intermittently observable, and where sustaining track continuity depends on anticipating what the sensor is likely to “see” next.

In practice, conditional generative models can be trained to forecast or impute future measurements given past returns and contextual side information. A conditional diffusion model, Variational Auto-Encoders (VAE), autoregressive transformer, or normalizing flow can take as input recent sensing frames, motion priors, and scene descriptors (maps, occupancy grids, CAD geometry) and output a distribution over the next measurements. During short NLoS intervals, the model synthesizes high-probability measurement summaries that keep trackers warm; when visibility returns, these predictions seed rapid re-acquisition and reduce the spurious updates that arise from noisy re-entry. Cross-modal conditioning further improves fidelity: camera or lidar streams can inform the generative prior so that predicted radio signatures respect the geometry and dynamics of the scene, enabling robust imputation and denoising at the measurement level rather than only at the state level.

Because the output is a compact latent representation from which measurements can be generated, GenAI also supports semantic compression and resource-aware operation. Devices can run a predict–then–verify loop in which the local model forecasts the next measurement, executes only lightweight checks to detect large deviations, and uploads either a low-rate latent code or a residual correction instead of raw returns. When the predicted information value is low, the device can skip heavy PHY processing and even duty-cycle the front end; when it is high, it performs full sensing and transmits concise features or tracklets. Distilled or quantized variants of diffusion/flow models make this feasible at the UE or edge, delivering material savings in uplink bandwidth, control signaling, CPU/GPU cycles, and energy without sacrificing sensing KPIs. Realizing these gains requires careful training and assurance. Synthetic data from digital twins and ray-tracing can bootstrap rare events; domain randomization and self-supervised objectives (e.g., masked measurement modeling) help bridge the sim-to-real gap, while online adaptation tailors the model to site-specific propagation and interference. Physics-informed constraints and plausibility checks maintain coherence with known sensor characteristics, and explicit uncertainty estimates trigger conservative fallbacks to lightweight filters when predictions become unreliable. Evaluations should report forecast calibration alongside task metrics such as time-to-reacquire after NLoS and track continuity under duty-cycling, ensuring that generative prediction delivers measurable benefits in both accuracy and efficiency.

5. MPS Sensing Processing Functions

In this chapter, we list the m-SePFs designed within WP3 that are in the most advanced development stages. m-SePFs are based on the MPS enablers described in the previous chapters and represent the way in which such enablers are implemented and made available to the higher layers of the MultiX architecture. Each section corresponds to a m-SePF and contains detailed information on its functioning, components, input/output, requirements, role in MultiX, and location in the overall architecture. Specifically, each m-SePF is identified by “m-SePF-XX”, where XX is a unique ID number, and contains the following informative fields.

- **Responsible partners.** A list of the partners involved in the development of the m-SePF.
- **Description.** A short, high-level, description of the m-SePF.
- **Input.** A list of input data required by the m-SePF.
- **Output.** A list of output information/data generated by the m-SePF.
- **Metadata.** (Optional) Set of additional information required by the m-SePF, possibly given by other architectural components.
- **Requirements.** A set of requirements of the m-SePF in terms of data availability, synchronization, and computation.
- **Related research activities.** Link to the research activities and MultiX technological enablers described in the previous chapters.
- **Usage in MultiX Proof of Concepts (PoCs).** Envisioned utilization of the m-SePF in the MultiX PoCs.
- **Location in the architecture.** Information on where the m-SePF is implemented in the MultiX architecture. This is complemented by a figure highlighting the location in the current MultiX architecture version, as contained in the MultiX D2.1.

5.1. m-SePF-01: Coherent multiband ranging (intra-band)

Responsible partners: UNIPD, IMDEA, KUL.

Description: This function takes K channel frequency responses (CFRs) obtained by the same ISAC node in K subbands of the same frequency range (e.g., around 5 GHz, 7 GHz – FR3, or 60 GHz) and combines them coherently to obtain a high-resolution range profile, which is a 1-D vector containing the complex reflectivities of the environment for different values of range. Subbands may be coherent or non-coherent, so this function can take care of mitigating the phase mismatch between subbands. The combination can be performed using backprojection algorithms, compressed sensing (e.g. OMP), or the CLEAN algorithm.

Input:

- CFR obtained with different carrier frequencies within the frequency band (**data**). These should be in 1-D complex-valued vectors, timestamped with the acquisition time. We denote them by $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_k}$ where N_k is the number of subcarriers of subband k , defined below, and $k = 0, \dots, K - 1$ indexes the subbands.
- List of bandwidths of each subband, $B_k, k = 0, \dots, K - 1$, (**input parameter**).
- List of carrier frequencies of each subband, $f_k, k = 0, \dots, K - 1$, (**input parameter**).
- Number of subcarriers per subband, $N_k, k = 0, \dots, K - 1$, (**input parameter**).
- Subcarrier spacing for each subband, $\Delta f_k, k = 0, \dots, K - 1$, (**input parameter**).
- Coherence flag (**algorithm parameter**) This is a binary variable stating whether the provided CFR are already phase-coherent. If false, the algorithms will apply phase offset compensation before obtaining the range profile.

- Maximum sensing range R_{\max} : the maximum range of interest to be considered in the computation of the range profile, (**algorithm parameter**).
- Range granularity ΔR : the range grid spacing to be used in the computation of the range profile, (**algorithm parameter**).

Output: 1-D complex-valued vector containing the high-resolution range profile. This contains the estimated complex-valued reflectivity of the environment for each range (distance). We denote the range profile vector by $\eta \in \mathbb{C}^M$ where $M = \lceil R_{\max}/\Delta R \rceil$ is the number of considered range values.

Metadata: This function does not require external metadata from the architecture.

Requirements:

- **Data:** availability of channel estimates in different frequency bands obtained at the same ISAC node. The complex-valued channel response is required.
- **Synchronization:** the time of acquisition of the different channel estimates must be shorter than the channel coherence time.
- **Computation:** capability to perform standard signal processing functions (DFT-IDFT) and computation-intensive optimization algorithms.

Related research activities: This function is related to the multiband sensing activities presented in T3.1, specifically in Section 2.3.

Location in the MultiX architecture: This function can be implemented to combine multiband data from 3GPP or non-3GPP RAN nodes. It gathers CFR data from a DU or from a non-3GPP-GW, as shown in Fig. 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Nodes involved with m-SePF-01 in the MultiX architecture.

5.2. m-SePF-02: Timing, frequency, and spatial phase offsets calibration

Responsible partners: KUL, UNIPD, IMDEA.

Description: This function is responsible for calibrating channel estimates in the form of CIR or CFR to remove timing, frequency, and phase offsets that may affect them and prevent their utilization for ISAC. This function uses *reference signals* in the delay (reference propagation path) or spatial domain (reference antenna) to estimate or cancel out the offsets from other paths, including the paths associated with the sensing targets.

Input:

- CFR obtained with multiple antennas on the same RU (for reference antenna techniques), or with sufficient multipath resolution to distinguish reference paths from target paths (for reference path techniques). These should be in 1-D complex-valued vectors, timestamped with the acquisition time. We denote them by $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ where N is the number of subcarriers and M is the number of antennas.
- Number of subcarriers per subband, $N_k, k = 0, \dots, K - 1$, (**input parameter**).
- Subcarrier spacing for each subband, $\Delta f_k, k = 0, \dots, K - 1$, (**input parameter**).
- Antenna spacing δ .

Output: Calibrated CFR with the same format of the input one $\tilde{\mathbf{H}} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$.

Metadata: This function does not require metadata.

Requirements:

- **Data:** Availability of CFR estimates obtained from a single ISAC node.
- **Synchronization:** The CFR estimates do not require synchronization since they are instant channel snapshots and are self-calibrated.
- **Computation:** Possibility to perform standard signal processing functions like DFT and solve multi-dimensional optimization problems.

Related research activities: This function is related to the activities in Task 3.2. An example of phase and frequency calibration function is provided in Section 3.1.1.

Location in the MultiX architecture: This function collects CFR data from a DU or a CU, as shown in Fig. 5.2, depending on which is the intended use of the synchronised CFR data.

Figure 5.2: Nodes involved with m-SePF02 in the MultiX architecture.

5.3. m-SePF-04: Coherent multistatic imaging

Responsible partners: UNIPD, IMDEA.

Description: This function takes multiple CFRs obtained by multiple phase-synchronized ISAC nodes in the same band and combines them coherently to obtain a high-resolution image of a target. The combination can be performed using the backprojection algorithm in space, as detailed in Section 3.1.2.

Input:

Description: This function measures the target RCS and MD using the measurements of the Reference Signal Received Power per Path (RSRPP), the measured time-of-arrival that is associated with each Reference Signal (RS), the measured position of the Rx, and the estimated path loss of the signal.

Input:

- RSRPP in the form of absolute values (e.g. watts or dBm) or relative values (e.g. power ratio to a known RSRPP value such as the RSRPP of the line-of-sight beam).
- ToA that can be measured in micro/milli seconds in reference to one of the following options:
 - The timing of each reference signal path is reported relative to the path timing used for determining reference signal time difference (RSTD) or UE Rx – Tx time difference.
 - The timing of each reference signal path is reported relative to the ToA /path delay of the RS that is reflected from a reference target (e.g. tree, building, etc.).
 - The timing of each path is reported relative to the ToA /path delay of first path.
 - The timing of each path is reported relative to the ToA /path delay of LoS path.
- Rx position, that can be represented as an absolute value (e.g. in cartesian coordinates, polar coordinates, etc.) or in relative to the position of the TRP (e.g. in the form of a separation distance from the TRP and angle of arrival of the received reference signal).

Output: RCS value of the target (as a real-valued number) and μ D spectrogram of the target (as a 2D real-valued matrix containing the power values for each Doppler bin).

Metadata: This function does not require external metadata from the architecture.

Requirements:

- **Data:** Power measurements for reference signals (e.g. positioning reference signals, channel estimation reference signals, etc.), time of arrival measurements for different paths that are received for the RS, and measurements for the Rx position using any type of positioning methods. Additional information on the line-of-sight, non-line-of-sight status on the channel between the target and the Rx/Tx. Expected RCS range of targets that can exhibit MD motion (e.g. drones).
- **Computation:** capability of measuring the input measurements (e.g. RSRPP, ToA, Rx position) with a preconfigured minimum accuracy or maximum uncertainty range.
- **Storage:** capability of accumulating RSRPP/RCS measurements over a configured measurement time window to measure the target MD (e.g. over 1 second of duration). Capability of performing frequency transformation of time domain signals (e.g. FFT) with configured resolution (e.g. 1 Hz)

Related research activities: T3.1.

Location in the MultiX architecture: m-SePF-05 can be implemented as shown in Fig. 5.4.

Step 1: Measurement of the reference signal measurements (e.g. RSRPP, ToA, etc.) could be conducted at the UE, or the base station (CU/DU).

Step 2: Measurement of the UE position can be conducted using RAT-dependent or RAT-independent methods at the UE.

Step 3: Measurement of the RCS can be conducted at the UE, or the base station (CU/DU).

5.5. m-SePF-08: Inter-band sensing integration

Responsible partners: KUL, UNIPD

Description: This function aims to integrate sensing information across different frequency bands (inter-band) to achieve robust and accurate localization. The system leverages the complementary characteristics of mmWave and sub-6 GHz bands: mmWave offers large bandwidth, enabling high range resolution, but suffers from strong path loss and limited dynamic range; in contrast, sub-6 GHz provides lower path loss, allowing

Figure 5.4: Nodes involved with m-SePF-05 in the MultiX architecture.

detection of distant targets, but has limited bandwidth, resulting in coarser resolution. By jointly processing the range-Doppler profiles and CIRs from both bands, the system can exploit their respective spatial diversity and range resolution advantages. Moreover, combining multi-path information from different bands helps to mitigate the impact of band-specific multipath artifacts, reducing the false alarm rate and suppressing ghost targets caused by multipath reflections, ultimately enhancing localization performance.

Input:

- CFR obtained in the sub-6 GHz and mmWave carrier frequencies (**data**). These should be in 1-D complex-valued vectors, timestamped with the acquisition time. We denote them by $\mathbf{H}_{s6} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{s6}}$ and $\mathbf{H}_{mm} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{mm}}$ where N_{s6} , N_{mm} are the number of subcarriers of each band.
- List of bandwidths of each subband, B_{s6} , B_{mm} , (**input parameter**).
- List of carrier frequencies of each subband, f_{s6} , f_{mm} , (**input parameter**).
- Number of subcarriers per subband, N_{s6} , N_{mm} , (**input parameter**).
- Subcarrier spacing for each subband, Δf_{s6} , Δf_{mm} , (**input parameter**).

Output: Localization estimation, in the form of a 2-D or 3-D vector containing the spatial coordinates of the target.

Metadata: This function does not require external metadata from the architecture.

Requirements:

- **Data:** channel state information or channel frequency response collected in different bands (sub-6 GHz and mmWave).
- **Synchronization:** both systems (sub-6 GHz and mmWave) should be synchronized well, with correct time stamps of channel data within the channel coherence time.
- **Computation:** capability to perform standard signal processing operations (e.g., DFT) and solving optimization problems.
- **Setup:** both systems (sub-6 GHz and mmWave), and should be in the same environment.

Related research activities: T3.2.

Location in the MultiX architecture: This function collects data from Wi-Fi access points enabled with mmWave and sub-6 GHz radios. Therefore, in the MultiX architecture, it is related to non-3GPP-GW, as shown in Fig. 5.5.

Figure 5.5: Nodes involved with m-SePF-08 in the MultiX architecture.

5.6. m-SePF-10: Reliable Wi-Fi Human sensing across multi-band channels

Responsible partners: INT

Description: This function envisions a Wi-Fi-based human sensing, delivering real-time, reliable breathing detection using commodity multi-subband (such as 20 MHz, 160 MHz) Wi-Fi hardware. Through targeted optimizations in signal processing, machine learning, and system architecture, breathing detection will not require additional hardware beyond WiFi and will be explored within the scope of laptop usage scenarios for a single subject. Details of the scenarios of interest will be specified as part of this task. Breathing detection will be performed in real-time on the chosen platform and will include the presence/absence of a breathing signal as well as its estimated rate.

Input:

- CFR obtained in the sub-6 GHz frequencies (**data**) from at least 2 subbands. These should be in 1-D complex-valued vectors, timestamped with the acquisition time. We denote them by $\mathbf{H}_1 \in \mathbb{C}^{N_1}$ and $\mathbf{H}_2 \in \mathbb{C}^{N_2}$ where N_1, N_2 are the number of subcarriers of each band.
- List of bandwidths of each subband, B_1, B_2 , (**input parameter**).
- List of carrier frequencies of each subband, f_1, f_2 , (**input parameter**).
- Number of subcarriers per subband, N_1, N_2 , (**input parameter**).
- Subcarrier spacing for each subband, $\Delta f_1, \Delta f_2$, (**input parameter**).

Output: High-level sensing information, such as: human presence detection, motion scoring, breathing rate detection.

Metadata: This function does not require external metadata from the architecture.

Requirements:

- **Data:** The complex-valued channel frequency response at the client/UE (e.g., PC).
- **Synchronization:** Phase offset mitigation is conducted in post-processing, so no synchronisation is required besides time-stamping of the CFR estimates.
- **Computation:** Capabilities to run inference with AI/ML models and solve optimization problems.

Related research activities: T3.1, T3.2.

Location in the MultiX architecture: This function collects data from Wi-Fi clients. Therefore, in the MultiX architecture, it is related to non-3GPP-GW as shown in Fig. 5.7.

Figure 5.6: Nodes involved with m-SePF-10 in the MultiX architecture.

5.7. m-SePF-13: MmWave ISAC-enabled localization and tracking of dynamic objects

Responsible partners: IHP

Description: This function takes multiple range-angle sensing maps (CFRs vs. beams), captured at different time instances and, based on them, detects and tracks the number of moving objects, estimates their positions and velocities, using, for example, Kalman or Particle filters. The acquisition rate for capturing 2D (range-angle RADAR) data must be higher than the velocity of dynamic objects.

Input:

- Channel frequency responses (CFRs) across beams (**data**), taken at consecutive sensing time slots. The CFRs should be in a 2D complex-valued matrix, timestamped with the acquisition time, with each column representing a CFR in one beam direction. The following notation is used for the data $\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_1, \mathbf{h}_2, \dots, \mathbf{h}_m, \dots, \mathbf{h}_M]$, where M denotes the number of beams and the m -th column \mathbf{h}_m is the CFR for the beam index m .
- One-time background data (CFRs vs. beams) (**data**)?
- Range resolution of the sensing node, ΔR , (**input parameter**).
- Beam scanning resolution of the sensing node, $\Delta\theta$, (**input parameter**).
- Polar area of interest (range and angle span), R_{start} , R_{stop} , θ_{start} , θ_{stop} , (**input parameters**). Note: if omitted, the full scan area is analyzed.

Output: Number of moving objects, their positions and velocities.

Metadata: This function does not require external metadata from the architecture.

Requirements:

- **Data:** Channel frequency responses taken from a full beam scan of the environment (CFRs over beams).
- **Synchronization:** The sensing data acquisition rate must be higher than the speed of the moving objects. For multi-station object detection, localization and tracking, the sensing data from the multiple radar nodes must be timestamped to ensure correct data fusion and processing.
- **Computation:** Availability of computing resources to run standard DSP functions (e.g., IDFT), image processing (contour detection), and tracking/filtering algorithms (Kalman filter, Particle filter).
- **Latency:** If the processing of sensing data takes place in the core and not in the sensor device, a mechanism that ensures minimal latency is required.

Related research activities: T3.2.

Location in the MultiX architecture: This function collects data from N3GPP WATs. Therefore, in the MultiX architecture, it is related to non-3GPP-GW as shown in Fig. 5.7.

Figure 5.7: Nodes involved with m-SePF-13 in the MultiX architecture.

6. Ethical aspects

This section summarizes the actions taken to adhere to the MultiX ethical standards during the WP3 research activities. Given the involvement of human participants in some of the experimental activities, a strict ethical safeguard protocol has been implemented. For a complete discussion on the risks related to the data collection and the countermeasures taken by MultiX, we refer to the MultiX Ethics deliverable **D7.1**.

The activities involving human participation and human-related data collection are listed in the following.

- **Multi-band phase coherence in FR3.** This activity is presented in Section 2.1.1 and Section 2.3.1. The collected data is available at [10]. The study aims to analyse and validate ISAC technologies using multiple frequency bands. The study uses passive sensing technologies, i.e., RF signals, to collect information on the radio channel when human subjects are present in the rooms, standing still. The type of collected data is the CFR estimated from RF signals propagating in the environment. No information about the identity of the subjects, vital signs, or any personal data is retained or can be extracted from the collected measurements. In both the public and original versions of the dataset, no information about the subjects' identities is stored, so it can not be leaked.
- **Multi-band Wi-Fi Human Sensing Processing for Real-Time Respiratory Detection.** This activity is presented in Section 2.1.1. The collected data is kept private, but the metadata is available at [156]. The purpose of this research is to develop and validate signal processing algorithms that can detect human presence using standard Wi-Fi signals by analyzing subtle respiratory patterns. No information about the identity of the subjects can be extracted from the collected measurements. The collected data consist of Wi-Fi channel state information obtained in normal operating conditions, where RF exposure levels are well below international safety standards. The subjects' identities are anonymized by assigning them a numeric identifier.
- **Human respiration monitoring with cell-free massive MIMO dataset.** This activity is presented within WP 3 & 4, which falls within one of m-SePFs and PoC 2 (E-health). The data is available at [157]. The study introduces an open dataset for respiration sensing using a cell-free massive MIMO system. Collected from a 64-antenna MIMO testbed, this dataset provides uplink CSI at 3.51 GHz, captured from 10 subjects performing controlled breathing. Ground truth respiration data is synchronized using a Motion Capture (MoCap) system, enabling precise validation. The dataset includes raw CSI measurements, processed breathing signals, and MoCap recordings, supporting research in ISAC, wireless health monitoring, and smart environments. In both the public and raw versions of the dataset, no personal data, such as names, gender, or identifiers, was collected or retained; only anonymized signal data remains.
- **ISAC with asynchronous moving devices dataset.** This activity is presented in Section 3.1.1. It aims to analyse and validate ISAC technologies with asynchronous moving devices. The study uses RF signals to collect information on the radio channel when people are present in the room. The collected data contains information about the people's locations in the room during the experiment and about the Doppler effect they produce with their movement. No personal information can be extracted from the data. The measurements are anonymised (the name of the participants is not stored). The data is currently being curated and will soon be made available to the research community.
- **Open-set gait recognition from mmWave radar point clouds.** This activity is presented in Section 4.1.1. The data is available at [127]. The study aims to analyse and validate gait recognition technology based on wireless signals transmitted by a millimetre-wave radar device. The experiments have led to the collection of a dataset of RF measurements used to develop gait recognition algorithms that distinguish among a set of multiple individuals based on their gait features. The system *is not able* to identify an individual uniquely (as biometric markers can do, e.g., fingerprints), but only to distinguish them from the other subjects participating in the experiments. In both the public and original versions of the dataset, no information about the subjects' identities is stored, so it can not be leaked.

For all the above datasets, subjects were duly informed about the scope and modalities of the data collection, as well as about their rights in terms of data disclosure.

The following documentation is available for each dataset.

- **Informed consent** forms for each participant in the data collection. Each form has been presented to and signed by the participant before data collection. The form contains detailed information on the type of data collected, the scope of the dataset, and contains contacts of people responsible for the data maintenance
- **Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)** form, compiled after data collection. This document summarises the potential risks related to the data and the actions taken to ensure data security and adherence to the GDPR.

The documentation is kept private and securely stored by the MultiX partners.

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